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Aim and Scope of the Journal

Globalization and modernization are causing a constant change in coexistent and intercultural relationships. The daily interconnectedness around the world makes it increasingly clear that people of different religious and cultural backgrounds need to continually and consistently research what makes for unity in diversity across the board. Over the years, a lack of intercultural integration and communication has resulted in promoting tribalism, and ethnoreligious and political disunity in many human communities. It is, therefore, imperative for thorough, unbiased, and sound academic research to promote religious, social, political, and economic integration in the face of religious and cultural diversity. To this end, *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication* aims to address practical issues that make for unity and national integration for sustainable development through a peer-reviewed academic journal that serves as a venue for publicizing research findings on subjects relating to religious and intercultural studies. The journal creates a forum for researchers to publish their research works on all aspects of religious and intercultural studies. It will pursue the promotion of critical research and original scholarship on issues related to all aspects of religious and intercultural studies generally – historical, hermeneutical, exegetical, theoretical, empirical, or comparative.

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From the Editors

Dear Colleagues and Esteemed Academics,

As we embrace the opportunities of the digital age, we are proud to mark a significant milestone in our department's journey with the launch of our first academic journal: *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication (LCJRIC)*. The journal represents not only our commitment to scholarly excellence but also our determination to ensure that our research reaches a wider, global audience. Through this journal, we are establishing a vital digital presence that will enhance our contributions to academic discourse.

Development, in all its forms, is fundamentally concerned with the holistic transformation of individuals, fostering both their physical and spiritual well-being. Religion plays a pivotal role in this process, serving as a source of social capital that contributes to the overall development of society. The exploration of religion, theology, and intercultural communication is essential in addressing the diverse challenges our world faces today.

Religion serves multiple functions within society, including:

- Giving meaning and purpose to life,
- Reinforcing social unity and stability,
- Acting as a social control mechanism for behaviour,
- Promoting physical and psychological well-being, and
- Motivating individuals to work towards positive social change.

It is with great pride that we celebrate the successful publication of the first two volumes of the *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication*, the official journal of the Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies, Faculty of Arts, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria.

We extend our deepest gratitude to the leadership of our university: The Pro-Chancellor and Chairman of the Council, Prof. Jide Owoeye; the Vice Chancellor, Prof. Kabiru A. Adeyemo; the Registrar, Dr. Oyebola Ayeni; the Provost of the Postgraduate College, Prof. Afolakemi Oredein; the Dean of Arts, Prof. Anjola Robbin; and the Dean of Education, Prof. Abidemi D. Odeleye. I also want to acknowledge our dedicated editors – Dr. Oluwaseun Afolabi, Dr. Emmanuel Adetunji, Dr. Peter Oderinde, Dr. Joseph Dayo Makanjuola, Rev'd. Abiodun Owoade – and especially the Corresponding Editor, Dr. Adebayo Afolaranmi, for his expertise and invaluable contributions.

I sincerely appreciate the exceptional work of our reviewers, who have meticulously evaluated the papers, ensuring the highest standards of scholarship. Congratulations to all the authors whose papers have been published. Your contributions are integral to our academic community.

Finally, I wish to extend my heartfelt thanks to our Chief Editorial Consultant, Prof. Anjola Robbin, and all of you for your continued dedication to advancing scholarship. Together, let us celebrate the maiden edition of the *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication* and our collective achievements.

Congratulations to us all!

Ayo Atowoju
Editor in Chief

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Capacity Building and Administrative Skills Development Among Church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

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Abstract

Administrative skills that contribute to the effectiveness of church pastors in administering the church have witnessed a steady decline in recent times among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. Therefore, this study examined capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. The study employed a descriptive research design. Two sets of questionnaires were designed as instruments for pastors and church members. The sample was one hundred and sixty. Eighty church pastors and eighty church members responded respectively. Split-half method of calculating the reliability coefficient was used to check the reliability of the research instruments which yielded 0.786 and 0.740 respectively. Data collected were analysed using the SPSS package to get descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference give good attention to professional conferences like ministers' Conferences. The study also revealed that the extent of practicing administrative skills is high. The study disclosed that the prominent factor that affects capacity building is that some churches have policies that hinder their pastors from further training until after some years. Furthermore, capacity building improves the overall performance of pastors as a result of the administrative skills developed. Therefore, it can be concluded that capacity building leads to the development of administrative skills and this will bring

improvement to performance of the pastors. It is recommended that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should explore other opportunities like workshop, in-service training, to build their capacities and churches of Oyo Baptist Conference should make funds available to assist their pastors in capacity building.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Administrative Skills, Development, Oyo Baptist Conference, Church pastors

Introduction

Every organisation exists for specific purposes or objectives. Certain individuals must serve as administrators or managers to achieve the objectives. The church as an organisation exists for the work of mission, and to accomplish the church's purpose for existence, effective church administration is required (Ishola-Esan, 2014:33). In other words, any improvement and progress that is bound to happen to any organisation is a function of how that organisation is being administered (Ayandokun, 2016:8). This implies that to achieve the goal or purpose of the church excellent and effective church administration must be in place. There is an increase of knowledge in every area of life in the contemporary world, and that calls for a local church pastor to be competent and versatile in church administration (Fatiloro, 2018:1). Church administration that will be effective must not be devoid of administrative skills.

Church is the assembly of the redeemed persons, the called-out ones (West, 1963:3). These are the people who have experienced circumcision of the heart, having obtained salvation by grace through faith, and through forgiveness of their sins, and have decided to join the membership of a local church (though belonging to different denominations) (Akintola, 2020:193). From the perspective of another scholar, the church is seen as "the community of all true believers for all time" (Grudem, 1994:578). Church administration is the leadership that prepares the church to be the church and to do the work of the church. It is the guidance, and the usage of resources to move the church toward reaching its objectives (Tidwell, 1985:27). This definition points to the

considers it appropriate to investigate capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Statement of the Problem

Administrative skills that contribute to the effectiveness of church pastors in administering the church have witnessed a steady decline in recent times among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. This is reflected in the way some pastors are running activities of their churches. Furthermore, previous works around church administration have focused on diverse directions but none of these previous works have produced an empirical platform for the theoretical relationship between capacity building and administrative skills development among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference; hence, a gap to be filled. Therefore, the researcher examines capacity building and administrative skills development among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This work sought to examine capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. The specific objectives were to: examine the nature of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference; find out the extent to which church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administration skills; identify factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference and investigate the benefits of capacity building to administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

Research Questions

This study attempted to provide answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the nature of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

2. To what extent does the church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administrative skills?
3. What are the factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?
4. What benefits does the capacity building have on administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Review of Literature

The Concept of Capacity Building

Every organisation that desires effectiveness and good results in particular areas must embark on developing the people that are working there. This cannot happen overnight, but it takes deliberate and conscious efforts to achieve this. Capacity building is an investment that most non-profit organisations like the church must invest in if they must produce good results after all profit-making organisations are doing well as far as this area is concerned. Yamoah (2014:139) affirms that human resources remain the greatest assets of any organisation, and as such, a considerable amount of resources must be voted for their development. Noort (2012:10), while quoting UNDP, opines that capacity building is the process “through which persons, organisations, and societies obtain, strengthen, and maintain the capacities to set and achieve their development objectives over time.” Odu, Ayodele, and Adebayo (2014:3) posit that capacity building is “all activities which can strengthen the knowledge, skills, abilities, and behaviours of an individual and improve institutional structures and process such that the organisation can proficiently sustainably meet its mission and goals.”

Again, Khan (2014:6), while citing Kuhl suggests that capacity building leads to building up new capacities. This relates to the position of Yamoah (2014:139) who insists that capacity building is “closely related to education, training and human resources development. Capacity building is a continuous process of adding values to individuals, organisations, and society so that they can be adequately prepared to

identify problems and formulate dynamic strategies to meet and solve the challenges.

Chatira and Mwenje (2018:110) and Andrews and Roller (2011) assert that the church is both a spiritual entity and an organization, and this implies that the pastor of a local church has the responsibility to lead both aspects of ministry (spiritual and organization). To do this, the pastor of a local church would need to develop more management and administrative skills because these skills will lead to effectiveness in ministry (Griffin, 2015:5 & Woodruff, 2004).

Pastoral periodic training is non-negotiable in building capacity among pastors of local churches. Chatira and Mwenje (2018:111) had earlier postulated that it is essential for pastors to improve themselves occasionally to keep up with the demands of ministry because a lot of damages have been caused by pastors who refused to upgrade or develop themselves. Furthermore, continuous learning by pastors of local churches to build their capacities especially in administrative skills line will help them to gain more knowledge, avoid limitation of scope, enhance their effectiveness, help them to relate with their parishioners on other aspects of life apart from spiritual matters, thus making them more relevant in ministry (Chatira & Mwenje, 2018:111).

Benefits of Capacity Building

There are a lot of benefits that follow every individual that takes a conscious effort to their capacity. Chatira and Mwenje (2018:111) claim that capacity building improves the effectiveness of pastors and making them more relevant in the ministry. Odu et al. (2014:3) also posit that capacity building strengthens the knowledge, skills, and abilities of individuals within an organisation. The position of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7) also corroborates with this statement when they argue that capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation and system improvement. Another benefit of capacity building through training is that it increases staff morale and motivation. Other benefits of capacity building include: Leaders become more relevant within the organisation (Griffin, 2015:5 & Woodruff, 2004); prevention of burn-

out (frustration) (Ojokuku & Adejare, 2014:7); expansion (growth) of the organisation; build competent individuals that is, beneficiary moves from one level of competence to a higher one (Biswas, 1996:401), to mention but few.

Nature of Capacity Building

Capacity building usually takes some nature/forms, which include In-service training, workshop/seminars, professional conferences, staff /workers meetings, refresher/further courses (Okenjom et al., 2017:477), and personal development through the reading of literature to mention but few.

In-Service Training- This is a mean for continuous professional growth. It is an integral part of the workers' development programme which is usually organised while in service (Nakpodia, 2011:290). Okenjom, et al. (2017:477) while reporting on the significance of in-service training to school administrators, also assert that in-service training provides a platform for regular updates of knowledge and competencies that are required for the implementation of school policies and curriculum. Osanwonyi (2016:83) believes that in-service training enhances job performance and the absence of it will retard professional growth. It is designed to fill the gap of professional inadequacies through regular participation.

Workshop/Seminar is another mean through which pastors can build their capacities. According to Ogbonaya (2011), a workshop/seminar serves as a training device for upgrading professional efficiency. It brings administrators together for the intent of learning new approaches to problem-solving in an organisation. The stance of Okenjom et al. (2017:477) corroborate that of Ogbonaya and claim that workshop/seminar makes administrators professionally more devoted to their work in the case of giving professional guidance to teachers in the various aspect of their specialisation for effective teaching and learning.

Staff/Workers Meetings- This is another on-the-job training platform that creates an opportunity for workers/staff to meet and discuss issues

of interest, which also serve as a way of building their capacity. Staff/Workers meetings are normally arranged to discuss definite matters. It is a forum through which administrators become more familiar with problems and events that occur outside their immediate context of assignment which proffer them the opportunity to learn from others. In this kind of meeting, workers interact together on areas of needs and specialization (Nworgu, 2006:77).

Refresher Courses/Further studies- This is another form of capacity building. In this case, workers, administrators, are released or granted leave to attend specific training and courses that are relevant to their job descriptions. The acquired knowledge and skills are usually in consonance with contemporary development in their areas of specialisation (Imhabekai, 1998:54).

Professional Conference- Conference is a meeting of several people with a common goal, and it is usually organised to discuss a particular topic or issue. Attending a conference avails participants to receive first-hand innovative ideas and new information is exchanged among experts in attendance.

The Concept of Administrative Skills

There are several administrative skills that church pastors can acquire or develop for effective church administration though their possessors are not given automatic success, it will continue to contribute to the effectiveness of their leadership, and their absence will also continue to limit their effectiveness. This work will discuss only planning, organising, directing, and controlling.

Planning

Planning is the most basic and essential skill for administration and leadership effectiveness. “It involves the gathering of information, identifying and describing possible problems. It demands to make decisions today, which will shape realities tomorrow” (Tidwell, 1985:204). Ayandokun (2016:8-9), said that “planning involves the preparation of things to be done and the methods in which it will be

measurement that is required to achieve the planned goal (Ogunbangbe, 2002:130).

Conceptual Framework

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Capacity Building

DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Administrative Skills Development

Figure 1: Conceptual Diagram for the Study

The diagram above shows the conceptual framework between capacity building which is the independent variable and administrative skills development which is the dependent variable. The parameters of the independent variable are the elements that stimulate capacity building. These parameters reflect the relationship between the strategies of capacity building to the development of administrative skills of the church pastors.

Theoretical Framework

This work, capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference, is anchored on Human Capacity Theory (HCT). The centre idea of this theory is that people are great assets to any organization and any investment to improve their capacity will generate a meaningful return. Human Capacity Theory tries

to explain that formal education and training is remarkably essential in enhancing the productive and creative capacity of a population (Aladejebi, 2018:16). This theory also posits that an educated population is a productive and great asset to any nation and organization. Human capacity theorists assert that there is a positive relationship between formal education/training and productivity (Aladejebi, 2018:16).

Yamoah (2014:140) further explains that since there is a positive relationship between capacity building and productivity, thus, it is imperative to invest in human capital through education and training which can be obtained through diverse means such as workshops, In-service training, conferences, seminars, leaders and workers seminars, and personal development so that productivity gains can be made. Capacity building theorists also postulate that when people are subjected to education and training, it will impact on the workers' useful knowledge and skills, hence raising their productivity (Becker, 1964). Training and developing individuals within an organization is a mean of getting a better return from them (Nwankwo et al. 2015:20). Schuller (2000) also lends his voice to human capacity theory and states that skills, knowledge, and competence acquired through the capacity building will determine whether an organization or nation will prosper. Therefore, this theory suits this work because it emphasizes that an organization should focus on increasing the capacity of individuals or workers within that organization to increase their productivity or performance. In other words, if the pastor of a local church increases their capacity to acquire administrative skills through education and training, it will bring better performance to their pastoral ministry.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. The research instrument used for this study was questionnaire. Two questionnaires were designed for this study. The first questionnaire was designed for church pastors, while the second questionnaire was designed for church members. The questionnaires were developed by the researcher and partly adapted from the work of Okenjo *et al.* (2017:479) and Ojokuku

questionnaire was 94%. These questionnaires were sent to an analyst for data analysis. Responses gathered through the questionnaire were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to find percentage, mean scores, and standard deviation. Also, content analysis was also done for the open-ended question for proper interpretation.

Table 1: Shows Number of Sample Collected in Each Association

Association	Number of Pastor	Number of Church Member	of Total
Oyo North	10	10	20
Oyo South	10	10	20
Oyo West	10	10	20
Oyo East	10	10	20
AanuOluwwa	10	10	20
AyoOluwa	10	10	20
Bowen	10	10	20
Okediji	10	10	20
Total	80	80	160

Source: Field Work, 2024

Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: What are the natures of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Table 2: Nature of Capacity Building among Church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

S/N	Statements	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Capacity building entails adding values to already acquired competencies.	50	22	3		3.62	0.57	3 rd

2	It is enhanced through attending workshops.	34.7	60.0	4.0	1.3	3.28	0.6 1	8 th
3	Capacity building can be achieved through engaging in in-service training for pastors.	45.3	45.3	9.3		3.36	0.6 5	7 th
4	Attending professional conferences like ministers conference gives pastors opportunities to breed new ideas that increase Pastor's administrative capacity.	74.7	22.7	1.3	1.3	3.71	0.5 4	1 st
5	Engaging in further studies/training in pastoral ministry and professional courses assist in building capacity for administrative skills of pastors.	61.3	32.0	5.3	1.3	3.53	0.6 6	5 th
6	Organizing leaders and workers meetings/seminars contribute to capacity building.	66.2	28.4	1.4	4.1	3.57	0.7 2	4 th
7	Engaging in personal	48.6	47.3	2.7	1.4	3.43	0.6 2	6 th

8	development through selection of relevant literature improves capacity building. Capacity building entails sacrifices, patience, and endurance for some time.	69.3	24.0	5.3	3.67	0.60	2 nd
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Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 2 shows the opinions of the respondents on the nature of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Research Question 2: To what extent does the church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administrative skills?

Table 3a shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing administrative skill (planning) among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Table 3a: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Planning

S/ N	Statements on Planning	VO (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	R a n k
1	Preparing ahead for activities/ <u>programmes</u> to be done in the church.	68.7	25.3	4.7	1.3		4.61	0.64	1 st
2	Doing long-term, short-term, and immediate task planning.	34.9	45.6	15.4	4.0		4.11	0.81	3 rd
3	Readjusting plans periodically in the light of new information and changes in operating conditions.	26.4	33.8	31.1	8.1	0.7	3.77	0.96	5 th
4	Gathering information, identify and describe possible problems.	28.7	46.0	20.0	4.0	1.3	3.97	0.88	4 th
5	Considering possible options of solution to identified problems.	36.7	45.3	13.3	4.0	0.7	4.13	0.84	2 nd

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3b: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Organising

S/ N	Statements on Organizing	V (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Connecting members into mutually beneficial relationships, specifically those with a common task or purpose.	26.0	41.3	23.3	4.7	4.0	4.15	4.30	2 nd
2	Grouping related activities together and setting up a line of authority for operational effectiveness.	22.7	46.0	19.3	8.0	4.0	3.75	1.02	5 th
3	Arranging people within the church to get a particular task done.	42.7	39.3	12.0	4.7	1.3	4.17	0.91	1 st
4	Setting up certain rules for teamwork to enable people to work harmoniously together under all possible circumstances.	38.7	34.7	18.0	4.7	4.0	3.99	1.06	3 rd
5	Establishing platforms that will help meet the social needs of people doing the work of the Lord.	30.7	40.7	18.7	4.0	6.0	3.86	1.09	4 th

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3b shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing organizing as part of the administrative skills among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Table 3c: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Directing

S/N	Statements on Directing	VO (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Having a good grasp of what people are to do.	43.0	43.6	10.1	2.0	1.3	4.24	0.82	1 st
2	Indicating what others are to do.	32.7	42.7	22.0	1.3	1.3	4.04	0.85	5 th
3	Providing an agreed agenda of what people are to do.	38.7	42.7	12.0	5.3	1.3	4.12	0.91	3 rd
4	Taking time to explain the method to get the job done.	40.7	36.0	14.7	8.0	0.7	4.08	0.97	4 th
5	Directing subordinates to understand and contribute effectively and efficiently to the attainment of church goals.	48.7	34.0	10.7	5.3	1.3	4.23	0.94	2 nd

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3c shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing directing as part of the administrative skills among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Table 3d: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Controlling

S/N	Statements Controlling	VO (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Directing, guiding, restraining, and keeping people within the limit.	25.2	43.5	21.1	7.5	2.7	3.81	0.99	5 th
2	Measuring the progress of the planned programmes.	27.2	51.7	16.3	2.0	2.7	3.99	0.88	3 rd
3	Correcting deviations from standard practices.	31.5	42.3	14.8	8.1	3.4	3.91	1.04	4 th
4	Introducing the right ideas at the right time to achieve the goal of the church.	52.7	31.8	10.8	4.1	0.7	4.66	4.26	1 st
5	Displaying integrity to exercise necessary control.	51.0	32.9	11.4	3.4	1.3	4.29	0.90	2 nd

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3d shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing controlling as part of the administrative skills among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Research Question 3: What are the factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Table 4: Factors Affecting Capacity Building for Administrative Skills Development among Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

S/N	Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Lack of incentives often discourages Pastors to	21.3	61.3	16.0	1.3	3.03	0.66	5 th

	build capacity.							
2	Inadequate funding often incapacitate pastors to build their capacity	42.7	49.3	5.3	2.7	3.32	0.70	2 nd
3	The environment where the pastor lives also affect the pastor's capacity building.	41.3	41.3	13.3	4.0	3.20	0.82	3 rd
4	Some churches have policies that hinder their pastors for further training until after some years.	39.2	51.4	9.5		3.84	4.77	1 st
5	Some pastors are badly influenced by their friends from building their capacity.	20.0	60.0	18.7	1.3	2.99	0.67	6 th
6	Nature of some pastors' homes	22.7	62.7	13.3	1.3	3.07	0.64	4 th

	sometimes debars them from building their capacity.							
7	The workload in some churches prevents some pastors from attending further training.	25.3	44.0	25.3	5.3	2.89	0.84	7 th

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 4 shows the opinions of the respondents on the factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Research Question 4: What are the benefits of capacity building to administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Table 5: Benefits of Capacity Building to Administrative Skills Development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

S/N	Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Capacity building improves the overall performance of a pastor as a result of	64.7	30.0	4.7	0.7	3.61	0.65	1 st

	administrative skills acquired							
2	Capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation, church ministries, and human resources development.	57.3	38.7	4.0		3.55	0.61	2 nd
3	Capacity building increases pastors' morale and motivation.	59.0	34.2	6.0	0.7	3.53	0.66	3 rd
4	Capacity building helps to prevent frustration and burn-out in ministry.	49.3	42.0	7.3	1.3	3.41	0.71	7 th
5	Capacity building causes the growth of the church ministries (expansion).	58.6	34.0	4.7	2.7	3.50	0.73	5 th
6	Capacity building moves a beneficiary	56.7	38.7	3.3	1.3	3.51	0.64	4 th

7	from one level of competence to a higher one. Leaders involved in the regular capacity building become more relevant with developments and information for solving complex daily problems at workplace.	58.7	33.3	8.0		3.51	0.65	4 th
8	Those engaged in constant capacity building have more opportunities for promotion or occupying higher official positions.	55.7	38.3	4.0	2.0	3.48	0.68	6 th

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 5 shows the opinions of the respondents on the benefits of capacity building to administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one examined the nature of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. This study reveals that Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference give good attention to professional conferences like ministers' conferences which give them an opportunity to breed new ideas that increase Pastors' administrative skills as ranked first in this study. This finding agrees with a finding that attending a conference avails participants to received first-hand innovative ideas and new information that are normally exchange among experts (Available Online: <https://evenues.com/event-planning-guide/what-is-a-conference>,). This implies that Pastors who avail themselves opportunities to professional conferences stand to gain first-hand innovative ideas that will help them in ministry especially in the area of administrative skills that are pertinent for effectiveness in ministry. The findings also reveal that capacity building entails: sacrifices, patience, and endurance for some time; adding values to already acquired competencies. The implication of these findings is that the making of a leader is not a day job apart from the fact that it would cost the beneficiary money, patience, and endurance. And for any pastor to remain relevant in ministry, these aforementioned sacrifices must be made so that he or she can add values to already acquired competencies. Another discovery from this study is that organising workers' meetings contribute to capacity building. This discovery corroborates the finding of Nworgu (2006:77) that workers meeting create an opportunity for workers to meet and discuss issues of interest, which also serve as a way of building capacity. Nworgu furthers that workers meeting is a forum through which administrators become more familiar with problems and events that occur outside their immediate context of assignment which proffer them the opportunity to learn from others. An on-line source (Available Online:<https://www.getmunite.com>,) also testifies that workers' meeting gives room for information sharing; creating a solution to existing problems, educating others, building relationship; and source of inspiration. Pastor of a local church serves as the administrator of that church; hence, workers' meeting is essential as this will avail such pastor

to share certain information, familiar with problems within or without, and create appropriate solutions to the identified problem, and in doing these, other would get some inspiration on how to lead.

Also, it is cleared from the findings that In-Service training received a low ranking (7th). This shows that Pastors from Oyo Baptist Conference has a poor attitude to in-service training. This implies that they are not used to in-service training as a way of developing their capacities and the capacities of their members. According to Osanwonyi (2016:83), in-service training enhances job performance, and the absence of it retards professional growth. Now, the implication of not having in-service training by Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference is that their ministerial job performance would have been hindered, and at the same time their professional growth retarded.

Furthermore, findings from research question one also indicates that many Pastors in Oyo Baptist Conference do not attend workshop as this was rated least among other nature of the capacity building. That means they do not believe so much that capacity building can be enhanced through attending workshops. The result of this finding is not in consonance with the submission of Ogbonaya (2011) and Okenjom et al. (2017), who assert that attending workshops serves as a device to upgrade professional efficiency. Therefore, attending workshops by the Pastor of Oyo Baptist Conference is critical as this would help then to improve them as far as pastoral ministry is concerned.

Research question two found out the extent to which Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administrative skills. Regarding planning as one of the administrative skills, this study indicates that Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference usually prepared ahead for activities to be done in the church as this was ranked first. This finding agrees with the opinion of Ayandokun (2016:67), who states that “planning involves the preparation of things to be done and the method in which it would be achieved.” This suggests that these Pastors would have imagined things or activities to do and how others would be influenced to achieve the expected results. Again, on the issue of planning, the findings also reveal that Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference rarely readjust their plans

periodically in the light of new information and changes in operating conditions. This finding opposes the view of Tidwell (1985:204) that planning involves identifying and describing possible problems and at the same time finding solutions to them. That means since they hardly readjust their programmes or activities, they might not be able to proffer necessary solutions to the identified problem.

The result of organising as part of the administrative skills discloses that Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference engage in arranging people within the church to get a particular task done as this was rated first among other statements. This result is in agreement with the take of Ishola-Esan (2014:32) that “organising is a way of establishing effective interpersonal relationship that enables a particular organisation to work. That is, the arrangement of people to get the job done.” Becker (1964:102), Mincer (1974:34), and Barney (1991:105) postulate that people are assets to any organisation, and any investment to improve their capacities will generate a meaningful result. The implication of the statements of Ishola-Esan, Becker, Mincer, and Barney is that church members must be seen as assets God has deployed to the church to do the work of the church and they must be arranged based on certain factors to establish interpersonal relationship and to do a particular job or assignment given to them. The issue of interpersonal relationships is essential because if the relationship among them is not cordial, the expected job or duty will not be done.

Similarly, the result of organising also shows that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference are lagging in grouping related activities together and set up a line of authority for operational effectiveness. This finding is an excellent pointer to the fact that some of these pastors might be weak administratively because they rated themselves low when it comes to the grouping of activities or jobs to be performed by their members and on who reports to whom. That is, setting a line of authority. This result contradicts the position of Wedel (1966:33) who submits that organising involves grouping of related activities and setting up a line of authority. Therefore, for these pastors to become more effective in the usage of

organising skill, they need to know how to group activities and individuals that would champion those activities together.

Another finding that this study discovered is the extent of practicing directing. The results obtained indicate that the respondents (Pastors) have a good grasp of what people are to do. They also direct their subordinates to understand and contribute effectively and efficiently to the attainment of church goals. This finding supports the claim of Ogunbangbe (2002:121) who affirms that church leaders and administrators ought to know and communicate their followers and other members for effective performance of their duties.

Further discovery in this aspect of directing is also alarming in the sense that, the results point to the fact that these church pastors have good grasp of what people are to do, they even direct their subordinates to understand and contribute effectively and efficiently to the attainment of the church goal, but they do not indicate well what others are to do as rated least from the result. This is contrary to the belief of scholars like Tidwell (1985:210) who states that a good director is expected to indicate what others are to do in the group in a way that gets the job done. Since people remains the great assets of any organisation, therefore it is expected that what they are to do must be well communicated. This is what is usually called a job description in the modern-day business world. Telling church members what to do and how to do it will allow them to unleash their energies, resources, and their abilities toward the realisation of the missions of the church.

Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference also displayed controlling as part of administrative skills. This work indicates that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference introduce the right ideas at the right time to achieve the goal of the church. This finding agrees with the position of Ogunbangbe (2002:130) that when leaders introduce the right ideas at an appropriate time, it will lead to a certain measure of control. This suggests that people should not be administered by using force; rather the introduction of what to do at the right time will lead to a certain measure of control. Further discovery about controlling is the fact that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference display integrity to exercise necessary control.

Adetunji's (2010:70) opinion corroborates this discovery and claims that "Integrity is the quality of being honest and firm in one's moral principle." It is the quality of standing for what one knows is right.

The opinion of Tidwell (1986:216) that "one of the ways to uphold control is to maintain integrity" also supports this finding of display of integrity by the Pastor of Oyo Baptist Conference. People tend to follow a leader whose yes is yes and whose no is no. Lack of integrity will cause pastors to lose grip over their members, and once that happens, control is gone. Another finding is that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference measure the progress of the planned programmes. This finding goes along with the claim of Ogunbangbe (2002:131) who posits that "control is used to monitor the advancement of the programme and procedures in the plan. Through control system, deviations from the standard practice are detected." The implication is that control remains a powerful instrument in the hands of pastors who wish to check some deviations from standard practices so that the organisation's goals can be realised.

Research question three identified factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. This work reveals that some churches have policies that hinder their pastors for further training until after some years. The reason for this could be as a result of the experiences of some churches in the past whereby some pastors were given the opportunities for further studies, and after their training they opted for what seems to be "greener pasture" - "better church." This has really taught some churches lessons before they came up with the idea that for some years when a pastor resumes work, there will not be an opportunity for further study. But the era we are in now has gone beyond going into four-walled institutions before building capacity. There are a lot of online courses that could be done with reputable schools that will not cause any travelling.

Similarly, this work also shows that inadequate funding often incapacitates pastors to build their capacities. The take-home of some pastors incapacitates some pastors to engage in further studies that

might lead to building capacities that would help them to develop necessary administrative skills. In addition to this, this work also indicates that the environment where some pastors live also affects pastors' capacity building. Oyo Baptist Conference has almost fifty percent of their churches in the rural area. For instance, the association that this researcher belongs to has twenty-one (21) churches, and out of these, ten (10) are located in the villages where there is bad or no network at all. For this set of pastors, it might be a bit difficult to build their capacities especially through further studies, workshops, seminars and conferences. But they can also improve themselves through reading of related literature that can help to develop their capacities with regard to administrative skills. Books on leadership and Church Administration can assist.

Another critical finding of factors that affect capacity building for administrative skills development is the nature of some pastors' homes sometime debar them from building their capacities. This factor is equally real. The nature of some pastors' homes especially those who still have growing children who are still in dependent age brackets, might find it difficult to excuse themselves from homes for further study owing to the fact that people look up to pastors' homes to be an ideal home. So, the fear of who will assist in the upbringing of the children grip many pastors and prevent them from further studies.

Research question four investigated what benefits capacity building has on administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. It was discovered that capacity building improves the overall performance of a pastor as a result of administrative skills acquired. This finding is in line with the finding of Chatira and Mwenje (2018:111), who submit that capacity building improves the effectiveness of pastors and making them more relevant in the ministry. Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7) also agree with the same view and presents that capacity building improves the overall productivity of workers in any organisation. In the findings of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7), 40.94% of the respondents indicated strongly agreed (SA) and 37.80% indicated agreed (A) compared with 64.7% (SA) and 30% (A) obtained in this

result. Okenjom et al. (2017:479) also obtained 77% (SA) and 22 (A) on the fact that capacity building improves the overall performance of the workers in any established organisation. The implication of this discovery is that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference must give attention to various activities that will lead to capacity building because this result indicates that it will improve their performance as a result of administrative skills acquired. It is also safe to infer that building capacity would bring about the development of administrative skills.

In the same vein, this work reveals that capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation, church ministries, and human resources development. This finding agrees with the argument of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7) that capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation and system commitment. Their result points out that their respondents indicate 40.50% (SA) and 37.80% (A) respectively and this work got 57.30% (SA) and 38.7% (A) correspondingly. It is certain that the world we live in today is not stable, is ever dynamic. This calls for pastors involving in ministries to give heed to capacity building so that various innovations that will move the church forward can be birthed. Not only this but also leading to the development of other human resources in the church because people remain the great asset of any organisation, and it is not possible to give what people do not have. Hence, building capacity is indispensable.

Furthermore, this work reveals that capacity building increases pastors' morale and motivation. The position of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6) supports this finding and argues that capacity building through training and attending workshops will increase staff morale and motivation. Also, this result shows that capacity building has the tendency to permit a beneficiary to move from one level of competence to a higher one.

This finding also agrees with the stance of Biswas (1996:401), who argues that capacity building moves competent individuals from one level of proficiency to a higher level. This statement of Biswas finds expression in Matthew chapter twenty-five in the parable of talent where the master gives commendation to those two servants that traded with five and two talents to gained five and two more respectively. This

implies that those two servants move from one level of proficiency to a higher one. This is also expected of pastors who desired to satisfy the master.

Similarly, this work also reveals that leaders who involve in the regular capacity building become more relevant with developments and information for solving a complex daily problem at work. This finding aligns with the assertion of Graffin (2015:5) and Woodruff (2004) who declare that leaders who engage in capacity building become more relevant within the organisation. Pastors need to strive to become more relevant in ministry. This is very crucial. The master (Jesus) wants that. This could be inferred from Jesus' statement in Matthew 4:19, that says "Come, follow me, and I will make you fishers of men." This statement of Jesus is a statement to make his followers relevant to his ministry here on earth. Therefore, it is safe to make this statement that pastors who engage in capacity building stand to become more relevant in the ministry and the kingdom business at large.

Conclusion

This research acknowledged that capacity building by church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference with respect to administrative skills development occurred majorly through attending professional conferences like ministers' conference, though few of them have a poor attitude to in-service training and workshops as other means of building their capacities. Also, it is established that the extent of practicing administrative skills by Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference is high. Furthermore, the findings have established the fact that capacity building with respect to administrative skills development improves the overall performance of a pastor and church policies have been discovered to be the prominent factors, among others that affect capacity building. On the contribution to knowledge by the outcomes of this study, the following facts are deduced. There exists a relationship between capacity building and administrative skills development. Capacity building through attendance of professional conferences, in-service training, and workshops would lead to the development of

administrative skills which would in turn bring about improvement in the overall performance of a pastor and, enhance the quality of services provided by the church. As much as these discoveries are real, capacity building calls for patience, endurance, and sacrifices from the aspect of pastors

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should explore every opportunity that would lead to the building of their capacities. They should not limit themselves to ministers' conference programme alone;
2. Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should learn more about administrative skills through the reading of relevant literature so that the way they administer the church would be improved;
3. Churches of Oyo Baptist Conference should create platforms and encourage their pastors to engage in capacity building rather than using policies that would not allow them to build their capacities; and
4. Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should also explore internet facility to shuffle the net and discover some on-line courses that may be free, and at the same time that would lead to the building of their capacities.

References

- Adetunji, O. G. (2010). *Leadership in Action: A Sourcebook in Church Administration for Students and Ministers*. Ibadan: Baptist Press Limited.
- Andrews, B., and Roller, R. (2011). *Pastoral Preparation for Ministry Management and Leadership*. Available Online: <http://studylib.net/doc/5231671/pastoral-preparation-for-ministry-management-and-leadership>,
- Akintola, S. O. (2020). *New Testament Theology: An African Perspective*. Ibadan: Baptist Press.

- Ayandokun, E. O. (2016). *A Manual on Educational Administration in the Church: Growing the Church through Effective Teaching Ministry Using all Church's Educational Ministry*. Lagos: Gloryline Christian Publication.
- Barney, J. (1991). "Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage." *Journal of Management*, Vol. 17 (1), 99-120.
- Becker, G. S. (1964). *A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to Education*. New York: Colombia University Press.
- Biswas, A. K. (1996). "Capacity Building for Water Management: Some Personal Thoughts." *Water Resources Development*, Vol. 12(4), 399-405.
- Chatira, F., and Mwanje, J. (2018). "The Development of Management Skills for Effective Church Management in Pastoral Preparation Programmes in Zimbabwe." *Africa Journal of Business Management*, Vol. 12(5), 103-120.
- Claussen, C. (2011). Capacity Building for Organizational Effectiveness. Available Online: <https://www.calgaryumtedway.org>,
- Fatiloru, O. (2018). "Influence of Church Administration to the Pastoral Functions of Pastor in Churches of Ogbomoso Baptist Conference." Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, Submitted to Faculty of Education, The Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso.
- Graffin, R. W. (2015). *Management*. USA: Cengage Learning South-western.
- Imhabekai, C. (1998). *Programme Development and Programme Management in Adult and Non-formal Education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Anfitop Books Nigeria Ltd.
- Ishola-Esan, H. (2014). "The Use of Basic Skills of Administration for Church Growth." *Asia-Africa Journal of Mission and Ministry*, Vol.13 (35), 31-51.
- Khan, A. (2014). "Education Role in Capacity Building." *International Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 05-11.
- Mincer, J. (1995). "Schooling, Experience, and Earnings." In McLean, J.E. (Ed.). *Improving Education through Active Research: A Guide for Administrators and Teachers*. Thousand Oaks: Corwin Press Inc.
- Murphey, C, and Chand, S. (1996). *Futuring: Leading your Church into Tomorrow*. Wheaton: Tyndale House Publishers.
- Nakpodia, E. D. (2011). "Teacher Factors in the Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Junior Secondary Schools in the South

- Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria.” *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, Vol.3 (10), 286-293.
- Noort, M. (2012). Building Capacity Strategy. Available Online: webapps.itc.utwente.nl/librerywww/paper_2012/general/noort_capacity.pdf,
- Nworgu, B. G. (2006). *Educational Research: Basic Issues and Methodology*. Second and Enlarge Edition. Ibadan: Wisdom Publishers Ltd.
- Odu, B. K., Ayodele, C. J., and Adebayo, J. O. (2014). “Empowering the Youth for Sustainable National Development through Vocational Education in Southwest Nigeria.” *International Journal of Research and Development*, Vol. 3 (1), 001-005.
- Ogbonaya, C. (2011). “Evaluation and Supervision of Instructions in Nigeria School.” In E. A. Beson and Nwokocha, L. K. (Eds) *Educational Administration and Management in Nigeria: The Salient Issues*. Owerri: Soletech Press.
- Ogungbangbe, J. A. (2002). *Church Administration: A Practical Approach*. Lagos: CSS Limited.
- Ojokuku, R. M., and Adejare, T. A. (2014). “The Impact of Capacity Building Development on Staff Performance in Selected Organizations in Nigeria.” *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, Vol. 11(5), 1-9.
- Okenjom, G. P., Laura A., Ikurite, N., and Ihekoronye, J. I. (2017). “Capacity Building Programme Needs for School Administrators in Secondary School in Cross River State, Nigeria.” *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol. 2 (7), 478-482.
- Osanwonyi, E. F. (2016). “In-Service Education of Teachers: Overview, Problems and the Way Forward.” *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol. 7(26), 83-87.
- Savitskaya, I. S. (2015). “Refresher Courses for School Teachers of English at Tomsk State University.” *Procedia-Social and Behaviour Science*, No.200, 366-371.
- Tidwell, C. A. (1985). *Church Administration Effective Leadership for Ministry*. USA: Broadman Press.
- What is Conference? Available Online:, <https://evenues.com/event-planning-guide/what-is-a-conference>,
- Woodruff, T. R. (2004). Executive Pastor’s Perception of Leadership and Management Competencies needed for Local Church Administration.

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Ph.D. Thesis. The Southern Baptist Theological Seminary. Available
Online: [https://
www.xpastor.org/wpcontent/uploads/2012/12/woodruff_competencie
s_needed.pdf](https://www.xpastor.org/wpcontent/uploads/2012/12/woodruff_competencies_needed.pdf),

Yamoah, E. E. (2014). "The Link between Human Resource Capacity Building
and Job Performance." *International Journal of Human Resource
Studies*, Vol. 4 (3), 139-146.

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Supervised Ministry as a Pedagogical Tool in Theological Training of Baptist Student Pastors in Nigeria

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Abstract

Theological education is fundamental to the life of religious organizations. The ministry and service of any Christian denomination are a reflection of the quality of theological education given to its leaders. Pastors play significant roles in nurturing the faith and guiding their congregants which requires some special skills, and supervised ministry, a structured mentoring programme integrated into theological training of pastors to help them to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world ministry settings is central in acquiring these skills. This study explores the significance of supervised ministry as a pedagogical tool in the theological training of Baptist student pastors in Nigeria, emphasizing its indispensability in impacting requisite skills in intending church pastors. It highlights the components of supervised ministry that contributed to the overall ministerial developments of student pastors in the Nigeria Baptist Convention theological institutions. The study adopts a systematic literature review of scholarly articles, journals, books, and other academic resources to explore the indispensability of supervised ministry as a pedagogical tool. The findings reveal that pedagogy is broadly connected with the theory and practice of imparting knowledge and the science of teaching. Supervised ministry served as a pedagogical tool through its comprehensive frameworks like experiential learning, reflection and integration, skill development, formation, and identity

development, cultural competence and contextual awareness, professional accountability and ethics, pastoral care skills, feedback and evaluation, relationship skills, and spiritual and character formation. By using supervised ministry as a pedagogical tool in theological training, pastors in training are not only exposed to the practicals and complexities of pastoral ministry, it also allows them to develop a deeper understanding of their vocational ethics, enhance their commitment to serving their congregants within the contextual setting and with empathy and integrity. Supervised ministry should be seen as an extension of classwork in theological training of Baptist student pastors in Nigeria, and therefore should be awarded a course code and with reasonable course units every semester to emphasize its importance in ministerial training of pastors.

Keywords: *Mentorship, Pastoral Education, Reflective Practice, Supervised Ministry and Theological Training*

Introduction

Theological Education is fundamental and central to the life of a living and growing Church. Since the Church is an organism, theology serves as its life to keep it growing, better and stronger. Phiri, & Werner, (2013) states that the ministry and service of any Church are a reflection of the quality of theological education given both to its leaders and members. Experience has shown throughout the history of the Christian Church that weakness or slackness in the life of any Church can be traced to its theological seminaries. Quality theological education that is accessible and relevant is not a strategic option for any Church – it is the only imperative choice”. This is the reason serious attention should be given to the theological education of any denomination. In an organized and structured denomination, theological institution produces the leaders of churches which constitute the denomination as a whole. In a situation whereby people in the name of divine call without proper theological training are allowed to lead churches in any denomination, there will be serious theological chaos at the end of the day.

Jesus Christ, before handling the affairs of his church to his disciples, his twelve apostles were with him for the space of three years or more. They

were properly groomed in the things of the kingdom and that was the reason they could succeed after Jesus ascended to heaven. While he (Jesus) was about to leave finally after his resurrection, he commanded the disciples to go into all the world and make disciples of all nations. He did not stop there, he told them to teach their converts all that he had taught them after their public confession through baptism. It means passing on what they received to others. The early church continued in that trend.

In the early church, we see that theological instruction played a vital role. The disciples gathered together regularly for the purpose of exhorting one another and instructing new converts in the teachings of their Master, Jesus Christ (Acts 2: 42, 46; 5: 12; 6: 3 and 4). In the same vein, the apostle Paul expressly instructed Timothy, his beloved son in the Lord, to devote himself to the study of the Word, to teach, preach, and to commit the same to trustworthy men, who will in turn teach others (1 Tim 4: 1, 2, 13-16; 2 Tim 2: 1-2) (Olatoyan, 2014).

This goes on and on from generation to generation. In the Old Testament, this is the method the LORD commanded the Israelites to pass the knowledge of Yahweh, the God of their forefathers: Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob, and God who redeemed them from the land of slavery in Egypt from generation to generation. By the age of 12, a Hebrew child already knows the Pentateuch.

The Old Testament is not only the first textbook of Church history, it is the oldest programme of theological education on record. Addressing originally a single Mesopotamian clan, the programme, which lasted many centuries, was extended to a group of related tribes and then to a whole nation. ... the Torah was understood as an instrument of education. Paul called it the *paidogogos*, the slave entrusted with the formation of God's children (Martin, 2010).

Theological education has been in existence for a very long time. According to Marbaniang (2023), in the apostolic age, there is no evidence of formal theological education, in the form of schools or

seminaries like today. However, this does not mean that there was no theological training of any form whatsoever. Among the Jews, we read about the schools of Hillel and Shammai. Gamaliel I, a grandson of Hillel, was the teacher of Paul (before his conversion) in his pharisaic training.

Historically, there is no formal theological institution as it is being practiced virtually all over the world in those days. Sometimes later, there is a formal theological school believed to belong to Mark the Evangelist.

Some historians believe that the first theological school (known as the Catechetical School) was founded by Mark the evangelist at Alexandria. Jerome (347-420) in his *De Viris Illustribus* (On Illustrious Men), Letters 8 and 11, wrote that Mark was the first who preached Christ at Alexandria and formed a church so admirable in doctrine and continence of living that he constrained all followers of Christ to his example (Marbaniang, 2023).

The quest to know God and understand biblical text for better interpretation and development of the right doctrine for the church would have led to embracing and establishment of theological schools for proper reflection of biblical teachings. Martin, (2010) states that Origen's work opened new pathways in Christian theology. As a teacher, first in Alexandria and then in Caesarea, he explored the relations between the Bible and Greek thought, developed the biblical commentary, worked out an intellectual framework for Christian use of the Old Testament, and carried out the first exercises in biblical textual criticism". Martin (2010) further stressed that during the Romans' political dominance, theological education, then, was instrumental to the Church's functioning in the Roman Empire in the days of persecution. It was directed equally to self-acknowledged Christians and interested outsiders – the kind of people who would frequently attend philosophical schools or take part in philosophical discussions.

Over the years, the gospel spread to our contemporary time. The Western world embraced the gospel and embarked on serious

missionary works to many parts of the world and Africa inclusive. There was a need to train missionaries for mission work and raise theologically inclined labourers to spread the good news of the kingdom. Therefore, there was an increase in founding of the theological institutions within and outside the western world. For the Western Church, Catholic or Protestant, national or denominational, the formation of the clerical class became the key to the Church's welfare. And theological education became the teaching of the Church's teachers – the training of the ministry" (Martin, 2010).

The tradition continues to this day. Theological education is the lifeline of Christianity and the church. It is through it that church leaders are trained and equipped for effective ministry and pass the same to the coming generation. The truth and doctrine of Christian faith are preserved through theological education. "Theological education is the process of enabling the practice of theological and biblical wisdom in leadership events so that contemporary faith communities fulfill their mission to be salt and light in our world and maintain the repository of truth for the next generation" (Easley, 2014). The case is not different in Nigeria as prominent denominations invest heavily in theological education to preserve the beliefs and traditions of their faith.

Previous researchers explore the relevance of supervised ministry in shaping pastoral leadership skills and competencies, but there is a paucity of research specifically addressing it as a pedagogical tool and its impact within the Nigerian Baptist Convention context. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the significance of supervised ministry as a pedagogical tool in the theological education of Baptist pastors in training in the Nigerian Baptist Convention theological institutions.

Concept of Supervised Ministry

Supervised ministry is a structured learning approach within theological or pastoral training programmes where students engage in practical ministry experience under the guidance and supervision of experienced pastors or mentors; they are referred to by the seminary as field supervisors. These pastors in training are prepared and involved in the

work of the ministry in preparation for the likely encounter in the ministry. The purpose of supervised ministry is to integrate academic learning with practical ministry skills, providing students with opportunities for practical engagement, reflection, growth, and development as future leaders in their respective religious communities. “Preparation for Christian ministry cannot be completed solely in the academic context of a theological seminary. In the contemporary ministry context, practitioners must develop capacity for ongoing learning and creative adaptation to a changing world of church and community, all while staying rooted in the soil of sufficient theological and biblical depth” (Christian Reformed Church in North America, 2022). Supervised ministry is an integral part of theological education. The theoretical framework for the study is Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory. Kolb’s experiential learning theory sees experience as the source of learning and development. The theory emphasizes that knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combination of grasping and transformation experience. The essence of the theory is to explain the role experience plays in the learning process. Experiential learning involves learning by doing or actively participating in the learning process. The model was published by David Kolb in 1984. He is an American psychologist, professor, and education theorist. “Kolb’s experiential learning theory was influenced by the work of other education theorists, including Jean Piaget, John Dewey, and Kurt Lewin” (Practera, 2021). David Kolb submits that learning is a cyclic process comprising concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. For effective learning to take place, the whole process must be completed by the learner.

Supervised Ministry as a Pedagogical Tool

For a better understanding of the subject matter and why supervised ministry can be a pedagogical tool, there is a need for a definition of pedagogy. “Pedagogy is derived from *paidagogos*, a Greek word meaning teacher of children... Educationally pedagogy has been viewed

as a combination of knowledge and skills required for effective teaching” (Chiroma, & Cloete, 2015). Pedagogy is largely connected with the theory and practice of imparting knowledge, most especially concentrating on the methods, and strategies used in teaching. It has to do with the principles, techniques, and approaches employed by educators to facilitate the learning process and foster intellectual, social, and emotional development in students. According to Twomey et al (1999), Pedagogy refers to the theory and practice of education, specifically focusing on how knowledge and skills are imparted, transmitted, and acquired by learners. It encompasses various methods, strategies, and approaches used by teachers or educators to facilitate learning. Pedagogy is not only concerned with what is taught but also how it is taught and how learners engage with the material. Another scholar quoting an author said, “Pedagogy is defined as the science of teaching”; he continues “pedagogy as a way of being with people. It involves: joining with them to bring flourishing and relationship to life (animation) being concerned about their, and others’ needs and wellbeing, and taking practical steps to help (caring); and encouraging reflection, commitment and change (education)” (Matthew, 2020).

Judging by these two definitions, and most especially the last one which described pedagogy as being with people, joining with them to bring flourishing and relationship to life... and taking practical steps to help and encourage reflection. Therefore, supervised ministry fits into this context. Supervised ministry, also known as supervised pastoral education (SPE) or theological field education, is a pedagogical tool commonly used in theological institutions or seminaries, mission schools, and other religious education institutions to train future clergies or religious leaders. It provides students with hands-on experience and mentorship in real-world ministry settings under the guidance of experienced supervisors. These are some of how supervised ministry serves as a pedagogical tool:

- (a) *Experiential Learning*: “Experiences gained in the practical arena of the local church are considered a vital and integral part of the ministry formation” (House, & Robertson, 2010).

Supervised ministry offers theological or seminary students the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge learned in the classroom to practical ministry situations. By engaging or participating in real-life pastoral care, counselling, preaching, teaching, visitation, and other ministry activities with experienced pastoral leaders, students will gain invaluable experiential learning.

- (b) *Reflection and Integration*: “A key pedagogical strategy for transformational learning is the utilization of reflection. The practice of reflective learning is widely accepted in educational circles as a means to cultivate deep and lifelong learning, as well as professional practices” (Ayers, 2020). House, & Robertson, (2010) think that through reflective practices such as journaling, group discussions with fellow students, and a faculty adviser as moderator during the discussion, and supervision sessions, students are motivated to process their experiences, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and integrate their theological learning with their practical ministry experiences acquired on the field. Reflective practices are seen as a means to foster awareness, empathy, collaboration, deep listening, engagement with diverse perspectives, and improved and creative responses toward sustainability. As opined by Blodgett & Floding (2014), ministerial reflection forms students’ thoughtful. by slowing down the explanatory process, letting the affective dimensions of experience become revealing, and hindering untimely inferences. It “integrates the knowledge gained from the classic disciplines of theological study with whole-person knowledge” (Blodgett & Floding, 2014). It also allows insights emerge and wisdom accumulate in the process. Reflection gives theological learning meaning and is practicable with exposure to practical learning. “Theological reflection is a cornerstone of all field education programs, where it is a pedagogical practice leveraging the experiences of students to form them as ministers” (Ayers, 2020). The end goal of supervised ministry is achieved through

theological reflection. The researcher concludes his thoughts on the subject of ministerial reflection this way. “In the end, ministerial reflection also shapes students’ sense of identity, their very being as ministers. Pastoral imagination becomes stretched and invigorated by the discipline of ministerial reflection” (Ayers, 2020).

- (c) *Skill Development*: There are many skills a pastor needs to possess for him/her to function effectively in the discharge of his/her duties. Supervised ministry helps students to develop a wide range of pastoral skills including listening, communication, care and counselling, preaching, prayer, baptism, leading worship services, conducting ceremonies (e.g., naming, weddings, funerals, etc), and managing conflicts. They receive constructive feedback from supervisors and peers to enhance their skills. These enhance their effectiveness in ministry. “Pedagogically speaking, the heart of most field education programs is the time students spend actually practicing ministry in the field. The accumulated and assorted experiences from that practice become the “assigned text” within this area of the theological curriculum” (Ayers, 2020).
- (d) *Formation and Identity Development*: Beyond acquiring technical skills, supervised ministry facilitates the formation of students' professional and personal identities as religious leaders. They begin to know who they are and what it calls for. They explore their theological beliefs, practices, values, ethics, and pastoral styles, while also gaining insights into their strengths and areas for growth along the line. Being involved in supervised field education in a congregation offers trainees firsthand opportunities to assess their aptitude for ministry. Taking on leadership and pastoral responsibilities in their church assists them in acquiring valuable self-understanding and dependence upon God for success in future ministry. Trainees become aware of the strengths they bring to ministry in terms of their calling, spiritual giftedness, commitment, spiritual formation, character, personality, temperament, leadership ability, and experience. By contrast, they

also become aware of those areas of their lives that need particular attention and nurture if, in the future, they are to become fully effective, transformational leaders in a local church (Matthew, 2020).

- (e) *Cultural Competence and Contextual Awareness*: Working in diverse ministry contexts different from what they are used to expose students to different cultural, social, and religious realities. They learn to appreciate and traverse cultural differences sensitively, develop cultural competence, and adapt their ministry approaches to effectively serve diverse ethnic groups and communities. Bush Jr., (2017) maintains that field education was structured to keep students on the move through multiple contexts. Each student is required to have five kinds of placements: a congregation representing their own culture, a cross-cultural placement in a congregation, and a social services agency to have a taste of different cultures. This will help the students to minister effectively within any cultural context. “The aim of a field education programme is not just competence, but capacity. Field education programme helps students to develop as a reflective practitioner so that they can develop theologically informed and contextually relevant ministry practice in whatever context they are called to minister” (Trist, 2023).
- (f) *Professional Accountability and Ethics*: Every profession has its ways and manners in which professionals in that field conduct themselves in a professional way that is consonant with the ethics of their profession. The same applies to pastoral ministry. “Ministry practitioners should meet the standards of professional, safe, and ethical practice. Most denominations will have their codes of ethics for ministers” (Bush Jr., 2017). Supervised ministry provides a structured setting where students are held accountable for their actions and decisions. They are aware of the rules guiding their profession. They learn about professional ethics, boundaries, confidentiality, and ethical quandaries commonly encountered in pastoral ministry.

- (g) *Pastoral Care Skill*: Matthew (2020) is of the opinion that pastoral attitude, pastoral visitation, caring for new members, caring for non-attendees, caring for the hurting, caring for the unchurched, crisis intervention, and mentoring are all parts of supervised ministry. During their studies in the seminary and as part of their supervised ministry experience, students are also given the assignment to visit hospitals, homeless homes, and other places relating to offering care and counselling. Students engage in pastoral care activities during this exercise, offering emotional support to those who are down psychologically, rendering spiritual guidance, and practical assistance to individuals and communities facing various life challenges. Through these encounters, they deepen their understanding of human experience, suffering, resilience, and spirituality.
- (h) *Feedback and Evaluation*: One of the reasons students are not just allowed to grow on their own and are placed under the supervision of a faculty adviser and field supervisor in the course of their seminary training is for proper growth, control, and feedback. “Feedback, combined with effective instruction, can have a powerful influence on accelerating students’ learning, and a critical determinant of whether feedback is effective is how students engage in feedback processes” (Vathey, 2020). Supervisors offer regular feedback and evaluations by having discussions with the students from time to time to help them assess their progress, set learning goals, and identify areas for improvement. “The capacity to monitor the quality of one’s own work throughout the learning process has been acknowledged as a central driver of effective feedback processes” (Trist, 2023). This ongoing assessment contributes to the students’ professional growth and leadership development.
- (i) *Relationship Skills*: pastors deal with people every day and therefore need to develop a good relationship with them. Pastoral ministry is built on relationships and there are different kinds of people in the church with different characters. Pastors should be

able to relate well with all of them. Right from the seminary through supervised ministry, seminary students are exposed to likely people they may deal with in the future assignment. “Supervisors and mentors exploring with students the importance of relating to people effectively; showing how we either facilitate or inhibit ministry by our attitude to others” (Hillman Jr., 2008). Students are helped on the best way to deal with congregants for impactful and impeccable ministry.

- (j) *Spiritual and Character Formation*: recently, theological schools have proved amplified attention in educational models that not only convey knowledge and skill to learners but also make them to have the character needed to effectively navigate the moral challenges that they may face in their future ministry (Wang et al, 2023). Supervised ministry is a tool in the development of spiritual and character formation of seminary students. Students are advised to participate in the spiritual activities of the church they are posted to regardless of the volume of their academic work to help them improve on their spiritual life. “Christian spirituality is experienced through personal prayer, devotions, and sitting under the preaching of the Word of God” (Hillman Jr., 2008).

Proper disciplinary measures are also meted out to students who go against the ethics of the profession for them not to put pastoral ministry into disrepute. Students are under close monitoring and supervision to tutor them in the proper character befits one who is called by God. “Spiritual formation is growth and development of the person into the likeness of the humanity of Christ—the true human in attitude, character, and action” (Hillman Jr., 2008).

Blodget (2008), while comparing field education (supervised ministry) and critical pedagogy, revealed the assumption of educators regarding critical pedagogy in relation to his discussion on field education. “Critical pedagogues, or critical theorists, see the purpose of education as not only preparing students for the world as it is but also empowering them to create the world as it should be. They are concerned about the kind of leaders and change agents schools are producing” (Blodget,

2008). This can be said of supervised ministry as a pedagogical tool in shaping the ministerial leadership skills in student pastors and instilling the ability to adapt to changing situations and environments and change or put things in proper perspective in the course of doing ministry. Summarily, supervised ministry serves as a transformative pedagogical tool that prepares students for the complex and multifaceted responsibilities of religious leadership by combining academic study with practical experience, reflection, and mentorship.

Conclusion

Theological institutions are set up to achieve particular goals, if these will be accomplished, supervised ministry must be given its rightful place in theological training. “To fully accomplish the aim of theological education, classroom experience may not be enough; hence the call to incorporate mentoring (supervised ministry) as a supportive pedagogy that will promote the integration of classroom experience with the spiritual formation of theology students” (Practera, 2021). To produce well-baked theologians and pastors, the supervised ministry should be seen as a pedagogical tool in shaping and molding the next generation of pastors. By using supervised ministry as a pedagogical tool in theological training, pastors in training are not only be exposed to the practical and complexities of pastoral ministry, it also gives them the opportunity to develop a deeper understanding of their vocational ethics, enhanced their commitment to serving their congregants within contextual setting and with empathy and integrity.

Recommendations

1. Supervised ministry in the Nigerian Baptist Convention theological institutions should be seen as an extension of classwork in theological training of pastors, and therefore should be awarded a course code and with reasonable course units every semester to emphasize its importance in ministerial training of pastors.

2. Baptist theological institutions and theological educators must pay due attention to supervised ministry and emphasize its indispensability in forming well-rounded Baptist pastors who are adequately equipped to meet the demands of contemporary pastoral ministry.
3. There should be a periodic meeting between the theological institution authorities, field supervisors and student pastors for proper feedback and evaluation of the supervised ministry programme.
4. Baptist student pastors should pay more attention to supervised ministry and be committed to it. They must also be ready to be molded by field supervisors in the course of their theological training rather than seeing it as a means to get financial support, as it may determine their success or failure in ministry.

References

- Phiri, I. A. & Werner, D. (Ed.) (2013). *Handbook of Theological Education in Africa*. Regnum Books International. <https://www.ocms.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Handbook-of-Theological-Education-in-Africa.pdf>
- Olatoyan, I. O. (2014). Charles Edwin Smith: A Visionary Missionary. <http://ojs.globalmissiology.org/index.php/english/article/view/1689/3745>
- Martin, P. (2010). *Shaping the Church: The Promise of Implicit Theology*. Ashgate Publishers.
- Marbaniang, D. (2023). A Historical Overview of Theological Education. *Journal of Mission, Leadership, Education & Theology*, p. 76-97. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330514753_Historical_Overview_of_Theological_Education
- Easley, R. (2014). Theological Education and Leadership Development. *Renewal Journal*, 1(2), 4-26. https://www.academia.edu/10269292/Theological_Education_and_Leadership_Development
- Christian Reformed Church in North America (2022). *Toward Effective Pastoral Mentoring—4th edition*. Christian Reformed Church in North America.

https://www.faithaliveresources.org/Content/Site135/FilesSamples/49681TowardEffe_00000034564.pdf

Practera (2021). What is the Experiential Learning Theory of David Kolb.

[https://practera.com/what-is-the-experiential-learning-theory-of-david-](https://practera.com/what-is-the-experiential-learning-theory-of-david-kolb/#:~:text=Kolb's%20theory%20explains%20that%20concrete,for%20students%2C%20educators%20and%20employers)

[kolb/#:~:text=Kolb's%20theory%20explains%20that%20concrete,for%20students%2C%20educators%20and%20employers](https://practera.com/what-is-the-experiential-learning-theory-of-david-kolb/#:~:text=Kolb's%20theory%20explains%20that%20concrete,for%20students%2C%20educators%20and%20employers)

Chiroma, N. H. & Cloete, A. (2015). Mentoring as a Supportive Pedagogy in Theological Training. *HTS Teologiese Studies/Theological Studies* 71(3), p. 1-8.

https://www.academia.edu/27555675/Mentoring_as_a_supportive_pedagogy_in_theological_training

Twomey, T. et al Ed. (1999). Pedagogy, Not Policing: Positive Approaches to Academic Integrity at the University. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 70(6), 642-666. [https://graduateschool.syr.edu/wp-](https://graduateschool.syr.edu/wp-content/uploads/Pedagogy-not-Policing-for-web.pdf)

[content/uploads/Pedagogy-not-Policing-for-web.pdf](https://graduateschool.syr.edu/wp-content/uploads/Pedagogy-not-Policing-for-web.pdf)

Matthew, G. A. (2020). Remolding the Pedagogy for Virtual Classroom.

Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research (CJAR.EU), 1(5), 1-7.

[https://www.academia.edu/download/87629004/1.5_20-](https://www.academia.edu/download/87629004/1.5_20-202020_20-201_20-2020Remolding_20the_20pedagogy_20for_20virtual_20classroom.pdf)

[202020_20-201_20-2020Remolding_20the_20pedagogy_20for_20virtual_20classroom.pdf](https://www.academia.edu/download/87629004/1.5_20-202020_20-201_20-2020Remolding_20the_20pedagogy_20for_20virtual_20classroom.pdf)

House, M. & Robertson, D. (2010). Field Based, Supervised Theological Education.

<https://research.avondale.edu.au/server/api/core/bitstreams/bab5aco0-1ed5-4311-b00a-15033cd5c50b/content>

Ayers, J. (2020). The Use of Reflective Pedagogies in Sustainability Leadership Education—A Case Study. *Journal of Sustainability*, 12(17: 6726), 2071-1050. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/17/6726>

Blodgett, B. & Floding, M. (2014). The Role of Theological Reflection within Field Education. *Journal of Reflective Practice: Formation and Supervision in Ministry, Cross-Culturality in Formation and Supervision*, 34, 268-283.

<https://journals.sfu.ca/rpfs/index.php/rpfs/article/view/341>

Bush Jr., J. E. (2017). Theological Field Education Across The Divides - Presidential Address to the 34th Biennial Consultation Association for Theological Field Education Saint Paul, Minnesota 21 January 2017.

Journal of Reflective Practice: Formation and Supervision in Ministry

214-228.

<https://journals.sfu.ca/rpfs/index.php/rpfs/article/download/479/463>

Trist, R. ed. (2023). *Ministry in Context – A Guide to Theological Field Education and Ministry Internships in Australia and New Zealand*. Australian College of Theology Monogram Series. Eugene: Wipf and Stocks Publishers.

Vattøy, Kim-Daniel (2020). Teachers' Beliefs about Feedback Practice as Related to Student Self-Regulation, Self-Efficacy, and Language Skills in Teaching English as a Foreign Language. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 64.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0191491X19301749>

Hillman Jr., G. M. ed. (2008). *Preparing for Ministry – A Practical Guide to Theological Field Education*. Kregel Publications.

Wang, D. C. et al. (2023). Spiritual Formation and Theological Education: Four Institutional Definitions and Perspectives on the Means by which Seminaries Participate in the Spiritual/Character Formation of Students. *Journal of Christian Education*.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370594546>

Blodget, B. J. (2008). Field Education and Critical Pedagogy: A Conversation. *Journal of Reflective Practice: Formation and Supervision in the Presence of Fear. Formation and Supervision in Ministry*, 28, 179-191.

<https://journals.sfu.ca/rpfs/index.php/rpfs/article/view/165/164>

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The Nexus Between Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Educational Creativity in the Post-COVID-19 Era in Nigeria

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Abstract

The relationship between Artificial Intelligence and educational creativity is the subject of much research globally in the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR). Scholars have researched on its impact on the educational system in the post-COVID-19 era in Nigeria. However, this paper aims to examine the nexus between AI and educational creativity. This is the lacuna addressed by this paper. To lessen the danger of the virus dispersal, social gatherings and relocation were proscribed. The epidemic also caused standard classes (face-to-face) to be interrupted, and education was temporarily suspended. Due to the epidemic, potential resolutions and alternatives are presently being researched to resolve the crisis in the educational system. This paper aims to see how Artificial Intelligence can help educational creativity in the post-COVID-19 era in Nigeria. The paper examines current research literature that explore the impact of Artificial Intelligence on educational creativity in the post-COVID-19 era. A systematic literature review was employed, and the Disruptive Innovation Theory forms the theoretical framework. The findings show that Artificial Intelligence plays a major role in educational creativity, with emerging technologies being used to pursue education in the COVID-19 and the post-COVID-19 era. Furthermore, Artificial Intelligence could not replace humans in the administration of education; rather, it will improve the accessibility to

quality education through the use of digital technologies irrespective of time and geographical location. Conclusively, Artificial Intelligence enhances educational diversification and hybrid in Nigeria, especially in this age of digital technology for online classes. The paper recommends that policymakers, business captains, and individuals must leverage the opportunity that arises from the usage of Artificial Intelligence to fully harness the potential of digital transformation and sustainable development in the educational sector of Nigeria.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Educational Creativity, Distance Learning, New Approach, Hybrid Classes Nigeria, Post-COVID-19 Era,

Introduction

The impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on educational creativity in this post-COVID-19 era can never be over-emphasized. Artificial intelligence (AI) has swiftly established itself as a revolutionary force in a wide variety of industries, including education. The evolution of AI has resulted in an array of developments and innovations that have impacted many aspects of human life. As an essential factor in societal development and individual improvement, educational creativity has had momentous advantages from AI innovations. The incorporation of AI in educational creativity is changing how students learn, teachers educate, and institutions work. By personalizing learning proficiencies, programming organizational responsibilities, and delivering real-time feedback, AI is transforming the educational landscape, connecting gaps, and inspiring a more all-encompassing and efficient education environment (Kamalov, et. al. 2023). Given the significance of incorporating AI in education, there is a need to deliberate on its implications.

The objective of this paper is to study the potential impact of AI on educational creativity based on a review of the existing literature. The prospective applications of AI in education comprise personalized learning, intelligent teaching systems, automation of assessment, and teacher-student collaboration (Wollny, et. al., 2021). Personalized scholarship is possible given the scalability of AI to the entire scholar population. AI algorithms like reinforcement learning can be used to

systematically learn about the peculiar needs of a scholar and adapt the learning procedure correspondingly. In association with personalized scholarship, intelligent education systems can be developed that can actively communicate with scholars, giving appreciated responses. Another impactful facet of AI is the computerization of the assessments. Computer vision and natural language processing systems can be combined to systematically grade homework, quizzes, and exams. Automated grading will provide great assistance to teachers, giving them more time to spend with scholars. AI can also be beneficial in expediting teacher-student partnerships by providing several feedback and analytics (Kamalov, et. al., 2023).

The application of AI in educational creativity reveals the potential for enormous benefits that are made conceivable by intellectual systems. The impact of AI can be perceived in enhanced learning outcomes, time and cost proficiency, worldwide access to quality learning, and other benefits. Personalized education and intellectual education systems can aid develop learning results for scholars, particularly in underserved populations. The worldwide reach and scalability of AI will allow scholars from both industrialized and emerging countries to benefit from better scholarship experiences. Automatic grading will have massive cost- and time-saving advantages in learning. Presently, around 40% of teachers' time is spent on grading and connected undertakings. Without the weight of grading, teachers will be able to spend more time with scholars and provide more learning support (Kamalov, et. al., 2023).

While the usage and benefits of AI in education can portray an appealing picture, it is vital to be conscious of the possible dangers of introducing autonomous systems in education. Since students are more vulnerable than adults to misinformation, the usage of AI in learning should be correctly pretested and judiciously supervised. Prospective problems comprise information confidentiality and safety, bias and discrimination, and the teacher-student connection. Certain applications of AI like personalized scholarship need students' data. For example, knowing that a scholar has a learning disability or a mental

health concern will allow AI to choose the suitable method and customize its content correspondingly. While scholars' data can be used for remarkable advantage, it can also be vulnerable to confidentiality and safety problems (Adeyeye, et al., 2021).

Anonymizing and encoding the scholarly information will lessen some of the challenges. Conversely, an all-inclusive approach is obligatory to tackle this concern. Another vital concern is partiality and discrimination. Since AI is trained on public information it can be open to the biases that exist on the internet. Additionally, AI algorithms can also accidentally learn bias on their own. Since there is a momentous amount of entropy in the AI algorithms, their actions could be unpredictable. Lessening the amount of bias is one of the main problems in applying AI in learning (UNESCO, 2023).

Novel technology has traditionally held the potential for abuse. For instance, the discovery of nuclear fission produced the devastating nuclear bomb. The advent of the internet produced the dark web, where illegal and illicit actions can be concealed from the government (Deepanjah & Adesh, 2022). On the other hand, civilization has been able to limit the potential for the misuse of technology through global collaboration and law enforcement. In general, the benefits of this novel technology surpass its hazards. Rather than discontinuing or thwarting the innovation of novel AI technology in learning, it will be more helpful, on balance, to incorporate it into the curriculum. Eventually, the only way forward is to embrace and adopt the novel technology, while implementing guardrails to prevent its abuse. The main contribution of the paper is to review the existing literature connected to the impact of Artificial intelligence (AI) on educational creativity in this post-COVID-19 era.

Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Educational Creativity

The term Artificial intelligence known as AI appeared for the first time in 1956 at a small conference at Dartmouth College, New Hampshire. Since then, lots of disciplines in many fields such as computer sciences or even philosophy are still arguing about what an AI is. An AI is a

computer program or a robot that can learn and improve to solve problems as usually done by humans or an intelligent subject. AI is “a branch of computer science dealing with the simulation of intelligent behavior in computer. AI is also the capability of a machine to imitate intelligent human behavior. AI is a computer system able to perform tasks that normally require human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages (Redmond, 2011).

In the book *Introducing Artificial Intelligence: A Graphic Guide* by Henry Brighton, he divided AI into 2 forms: they are, Strong AI and Weak AI. There is nothing much to talk about Strong AI, also called Artificial General Intelligence (AGI). AGI is a form of intelligent machine that can perform completely all kinds of tasks as a normal human. Scientists just had a feeling that AGI would appear, but no one can say for sure what, when, or how it will happen. On the other hand, they are linked to weak AI. It is a weaker form of AI in comparison with AGI which can solve some specific problems or perform specific tasks as a normal human.

John McCarthy initially coined the term AI in 1956 when he invited a bunch of researchers from a variety of disciplines as well as language simulation, vegetative cell nets, quality theory, and a lot of to a summer workshop known as the Dartmouth Summer Research on AI to debate what would ultimately become the sphere of AI (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019). At that point, the invited scholars to McCarthy’s conference in 1956 clarified and developed the ideas around “thinking machines” that up to the present moment had been quite divergent. McCarthy allegedly picked the name AI for its neutrality; to avoid highlighting one in every of the tracks being pursued at the time for the sphere of “thinking machines” that enclosed information processing, automata theory, and sophisticated information processing (Pettersson, 2018). The proposal for the conference aforementioned, “The study was to proceed on the idea of the conjecture that each side of learning or the other feature of intelligence will, in essence, be thus exactly represented that a machine will be created to simulate it.”

Nowadays, fashionable lexicon definitions specialize in AI being a sub-field of applied science and the way machines will imitate human intelligence (being human-like instead of changing into a human). *English Oxford Living Dictionary* offers this definition, “The theory and development of laptop systems ready to perform tasks ordinarily requiring human intelligence, like beholding, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages.”

Merriam-Webster defines it this way:

1. A branch of applied science coping with the simulation of intelligent behavior in computers.
2. The capability of a machine to imitate intelligent human behavior.

Definitions of AI begin to shift based mostly upon the goals that try to be achieved with associated AI systems. Generally, folks invest in AI development for one in every of these three objectives:

- Build systems that assume precisely like humans do (Strong AI)
- Simply get systems to figure while not determining how human reasoning works (Weak AI)
- Use human reasoning as a model however not essentially the top goal (Pettersson, 2018).

It turns out that the majority of the AI development happening nowadays by trade leaders falls below the third objective and uses human reasoning as a guide to supply higher services or produce better merchandise rather than attempting to attain an ideal reproduction of the human mind.

Amazon builds a great deal of its business on machine-learning systems (as a set of AI) and defines AI as “the field of engineering science dedicated to finding psychological feature issues usually related to human intelligence, like learning, downside finding, and pattern recognition (Pettersson, 2018).”

Education Dilemma in the Post-Pandemic Era

One main effect of the pandemic on learning is the greater adoption of digital education, hybrid, and virtual classes, as well as open (and distance) learning systems of education, became popular. During the

pandemic, education had to be carried out totally through the online method, consequently compelling everyone to adopt it as a mode of learning. This adoption is predominantly vital to all open universities around the globe (Adilakshmi, et al., 2021). Large organizations have been exploring knowledge management infrastructure as part of their exertion in transformation as educational institutions. Even smaller firms have websites that offer fundamental information in their field of industry as a marketing technique. The epidemic has aided in accelerating the advancement and development in this field. Nowadays job-related expertise development through online courses (short courses, massive open online courses, open educational resources (OERs) have become a big share of work life. Lifelong scholarship has become a philosophy in today's culture. The participation of respectable industry actors in the provision of online courses through platforms such as Coursera together with university online courses merely shows that the learning services are no longer in the purview of few, but people can select how they want to create their own knowledge bank (Silva, 2018). The question is if such wide opportunity is available for all people, therefore, the need to explore the digital divide and how it be closed. Information divide refers to the space that exists between those who have access to information and communications technology (ICT) and those who do not and those who have restricted access. Resources required range from ICT hardware and software, internet access, stable internet connection, and even a steady power supply. Gaps also have been discovered to exist among diverse generations and diverse genders. The information divide must be recognized as one of the world's most significant concerns because it increases inequity among people. The most important concern arising from the information divide is access to learning. Another critical concern is the enormous restriction on access to jobs. Much of nowadays' work necessitates digital expertise and better opportunities exist in the sphere of the information world (Trendov, et al., 2019).

Mental well-being triggered by social segregation, principally during the pandemic is another concern that is being explored comprehensively in

the post-pandemic era. Additionally, there are novel crimes caused by the digital world by producing a novel form of a susceptible group of individuals (those who are marginalized by the information divide). Information divide also transforms into other forms of divides such as classes of economies, as well as consequently social.

AI's Impact on Education and Teaching Process

Dealing with the impact of AI on the educational and teaching process, it is evident that AI will impact the educational and teaching process in many ways and primarily in two focal areas: enrollment and curriculum (Taneri, 2020). For example, Ma and Siau (2018) summed that AI will speed consistency and accuracy in curriculum and registration. Moreover, according to Ma and Siau (2018), human sciences and liberal arts majors will become more popular because these fields of learning are less susceptible to the area of AI than other fields, like accounting and finance (Ma & Siau, 2018).

Even though this study is vital for a load of data on the impact of AI on the educational and teaching process, it can be criticized for not confronting the concern sincerely, as the influence is much more intense. Certainly, concentrating on the educational and teaching process, no one would doubt that AI is substituting the lecturer or teacher in many ways, like blended education and e-learning.

The existence of an e-learning lecturer is restricted as the student interrelates with a virtual classroom, whether on Blackboard, Moodle, Turnitin, or any other platform (Jlu & Laurie A, 2018). Correspondingly, Professor Roland T Chin from Hong Kong Baptist University (2018) believes that AI is meant to revolutionize how we learn, teach, work, live, make decisions, and be ready for the AI age. Consequently, AI is not only about its superficial effect but also about radical changes in the teaching and learning process in depth (Chin, 2018).

What highlights this idea conditionally is the dispute from Princeton's Head of Computer Science, Jennifer Rexford. She surmises that AI is efficient in learning and teaching if others learn: "Learning how people learn will hopefully help us and others think more generally about

retraining down the road” (Rexford, 2018). Therefore, according to Rexford, the proficiency of AI is provisional, as understanding learning styles is the only basis for success. Alike, Jabar and Yousif (2011) argue that the education process in this world is becoming more interactive and engaging, according to recent scholars, because e-learning provides the learner with artistic and pedagogical features as well as integrates and deals with innumerable kinds of content which react efficiently to the scholars’ needs (Jabar and Yousif, 2011).

The absence of striking instances of how AI impacts the student’s everyday life can be a restriction of the method of Jabar and Yousif, highlighted below in the Education and Unit Study. For instance, AI provides deep education and teaching procedures to get higher performance from both the tutor and the tutee. For instance, adopting hypermedia for a writing class facilitates mistakes and cuts time consumption. For instance, before discovering AI, it took ages for a teacher to assess and grade papers and check for plagiarism. Thanks to AI, checking for academic integrity and language issues takes minutes or less. Indeed, using artificial intelligence, a lecturer submits the work to Turnitin, Grammarly, or other software. In minimal time, it can provide constructive feedback based on the results generated by the software used.

Even though Artificial Intelligence is flawless in covering language and educational integrity matters, semantic, pragmatic, and cognitive levels, in many instances, need the involvement of the human mind to perform the last touch (Mellul, 2018). Nonetheless, Artificial Intelligence offers several students connections about the topic’s prerequisite for the subject matter and eases and inspires both students and teachers by tackling different learning styles such as autonomous learning, visual learning, e-learning, audio-visual learning, and deep learning. Correspondingly, Artificial Intelligence enables the tutor to select and apply the learning method taxonomy that the learner needs and highlights the areas of improvement to be focused on (Jabar and Yousif, 2011).

In the meantime, Artificial Intelligence reinforces independent learning as the learner becomes autonomous and free to access input anytime and anywhere. Finally, according to Richer (1985), Artificial Intelligence positively impacts learning by offering intelligent computer-assisted instruction that facilitates educational intuition and provides expert systems to diagnose and assess learning results (Richer, 1985). It is undeniably clear that Artificial Intelligence adds a lot to the learning and teaching process, so what about assessments and grading?

Impact of AI on the Assessment and Classification Process

Artificial Intelligence does not impact only the education and teaching process but also the assessing and grading process. For example, Artificial Intelligence checks assignments and research projects through software such as Turnitin against billions of resources in no time. Therefore, similarities are easily generated to judge whether the learner plagiarised. Similarly, online rubrics and grading forms are added to assignments with criteria and scales, and final grades are automatically added to the submitted work without any hassle (Mahana, et al., 2012). Additionally, Artificial Intelligence provides interactive ways of providing constructive feedback to the student, easy access in a relaxed manner anytime and anywhere, with more privacy and autonomy.

Furthermore, the instructor can write or record feedback to facilitate and improve learning from errors. Also, in reference to a study by Stanford University, AI is applied to evaluate scholars' reactions and create a computer model that endorses rules inferred from the tutor's grading decisions. What is specific about AI is that it develops learning instead of making a final authoritative decision. Additionally, it reflects more transparency, trust, and quality control (Stanford University, 2019). In the same vein, Tovia Smith, in her article "More states opting to Robo-Grade' Student Essays by computer," argues that rob-graders (robots used for grading students' papers) are increasingly used to grade students' essays mainly in Utah, Ohio and soon Massachusetts to follow (Brad Rose Consulting, 2019).

Correspondingly, a research professor at Colorado University named Peter Foltz says they have Artificial Intelligence techniques that can judge up to 100 features and that grading essays are highly accurate (Brad Rose Consulting, 2019). In short, artificial intelligence is playing a more prominent role in the evaluation and classification of higher education in the United States of America.

Although the above researches are valuable from diverse standpoints in tackling the role of Artificial Intelligence in grading and assessing the learner and facilitating the role of the teacher, a critical thinker would not fail to pose the following questions: What about bias in marking reports? Who would guarantee that AI is fair and objective? What about the human side of the learning process and assessment? Will AI consider the psychology of learner grading or assessing a paper?

AI Impact on Future Careers of Graduates

Artificial Intelligence impacts the world of education, but it also seems restricted to this field and follows the student even after graduation. For instance, according to Wang and Siau (2017), Artificial Intelligence will influence the future job market of required skill sets. It will replace many other kinds of research that involve routine tasks and structures that are easy to automate instead of unstructured disciplines that require complex cognitive interference (Wang & Siau, 2017). Artificial Intelligence or computer assessment is not restricted to grading papers but can be the gateway to a future career. For instance, a human may not read CVs but be screened by an algorithm specialized in candidate shortlisting. For instance, in an article by the Economist entitled “How algorithms may decide your career: getting a job means getting past the computer”, it is reported that the largest firms are now using computer programs or algorithms to choose candidates with an applicant tracking system (ATS) which can reject up to 75% of candidates. The above policy pushed applicants to use keywords to maximise screening interests (Brad Rose Consulting, 2019).

Vodafone and Intel are not satisfied with shortlisting CVs but instead use a computer-driven visual interviews service called “HireVue” to further

select candidates. In this process, Artificial Intelligence analyses facial expressions and language patterns and decides to pass or fail the applicant (Brad Rose Consulting, 2019). According to research by Frey & Osborne (2013), the number of jobs at risk that will be computerized and comprise advances in robotics and machine learning is roughly 47% of US total employment (Frey & Osborne, 2013). Similarly, Dizikes (2020) refers to research conducted by Daron Acemoglu and Pascual Resrego from MIT University that each added robot replaces 5.6 workers, almost equal to six people (Dizikes, 2020).

Correspondingly, same study executed by Ma & Siau (2018) of Oxford University argues that within the next 20 years, around 47% of jobs in the United States of America and virtually 54% in Europe will be at risk due to Artificial Intelligence (Ma & Siau, 2018). Furthermore, the latter scholars at Oxford University forecast that Artificial Intelligence will write high-school essays by 2026, write best-selling books by 2049, translate languages by 2024, and perform surgeries by 2053. Chin (2018) from Hong Kong University argues that there are overlooked Artificial Intelligence instances or less obvious ones such as translation machines that enable you to speak to anyone with any language instantaneously. Chin (2018) added that JPMorgan Chase and Co. use a learning machine that deals with loan agreement processes and saves 360,000 hours of work by accountants and lawyers (Chin, 2018).

Even though all the values stated above about how Artificial Intelligence is creeping into the career world, Ma and Siau (2018) criticize these features disputing that when it comes to soft skills such as empathy, communication, collaboration, innovation, critical thinking, problem-solving, and leadership, Artificial Intelligence is not as robust as human cognitive ability (Ma & Siau, 2018). Both scholars reinforce their opinions by suggesting that higher institutions should provide soft and hard skills such as maths, IT, and engineering while training students. They think Artificial Intelligence may not be capable of affording these skills for future business careers (Ma & Siau, 2018).

Even though computer-driven screening is believed to avoid biases in the traditional employment process, Artificial Intelligence is not bias-free.

That algorithm can favour candidates with time and money to continually re-tool their resumes (Brad Rose Consulting, 2019).

To end the conflict with a concluding result, Chin (2018) disputes that citizens of the novel world order need new skills. These skills should include interpersonal skills such as adaptability, critical thinking, conflict resolution capabilities, and other cognitive skills.

Steve Jobs thinks, 'It is technology married with the liberal arts, married with the humanities that yields us the results that make our hearts sing' (Henn et al., 2005). How would higher education impact AI? Undoubtedly, the world is getting more innovative, and AI has rehabilitated our world by putting natural languages and data by enabling Siri, Netflix, Facebook, Google, Alexa, Amazon, and many other platforms as part of our daily lives (Oblinger, 2018). However, the question arises: How will higher education affect AI? This research paper will address these issues from the two focal points of ethics and cognition as answers to these concerns.

Theoretical Review

Disruptive Innovation Theory

The axiom "disruptive innovation," first used by Clayton Christensen in 1997, denotes how novel forms of technology or business models might displace obsolete ones. To succeed in the present extremely competitive business atmosphere and keep up with the rapid pace of technological improvement, disruptive innovation is more crucial than ever.

Because of digital transformation, companies may now offer cutting-edge goods and services, streamline internal processes, and forge deeper bonds with their clientele than ever before. This has resulted in the development of novel business models and the upheaval of established markets (Katz & Green, 2018). For example, Uber disrupted the taxi industry by using digital technology to create a new model of transportation service that was faster, more convenient, and cheaper than traditional taxis. Similarly, Airbnb disrupted the hotel industry by using digital technology to connect travelers with local hosts and provide a more personalized and affordable lodging experience.

Disruptive innovation theory explains how these new entrants were able to disrupt established industries. According to Christensen (1997), disruptive innovations typically start as low-end or niche offerings that are initially dismissed by established players as inferior or irrelevant. However, as these new offerings improve and gain market share, they begin to encroach on the established players' market, eventually displacing them. AI technology has enabled these new entrants to rapidly improve their offerings and gain market share, leading to the disruption of established players (Christensen et al, 2015).

Implications of Artificial Intelligence in Educational Creativity

The increasing adoption of Artificial Intelligence technology for various applications in the education sector and the growing need for multilingual translators integrated with Artificial Intelligence technology is expected to drive the growth of the AI in education market. AI is no longer just contained in science fiction films. It is going to be part of our everyday lives and in our classrooms. As we use tools like Siri and Amazon's Alexa, we are just beginning to see the possibilities of AI in education. A few more impacts are listed below:

1. Administrative Tasks Automation
2. Smart Content
3. Smart Tutors and Personalization
4. Virtual Lectures and Learning Environment
5. Teachers' Support
6. Students' Communication
7. Catering to the Needs of Variety of Students
8. Allow Teachers to Act as Learning Motivators
9. Provide Personalized Help
10. Dynamic Scheduling and Predictive Analysis (Subrahmanyam1 & K. Swathi, 2018).

Case Studies of AI in Educational Creativity

Artificial Intelligence's digital and dynamic nature offers opportunities for student engagement that cannot be found in often outdated textbooks or the fixed environment of the typical four-walled classrooms.

Some case studies have been provided in which AI is being pioneered and applied in education. Some of the applications are still in a relatively primitive stage in terms of envisioned long-term objectives. Out of those provided, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) seem to have made the most progress over the last 20 years, as one of the original concepts for applications of AI in education. All have the potential to help shape the next generation of more personalized learning and responsive teaching. (Subrahmanyam1 & K. Swathi, 2018).

I. Smart Content

Smart content creation, from digitized guides of textbooks to customizable learning digital interfaces, is being introduced at all levels, from elementary to post-secondary to corporate environments. Content Technologies Inc., an AI development company specializing in the automation of business processes and intelligent instruction design, has created a suite of smart content services for secondary education and beyond. Cram101 uses AI to help disseminate and break down textbook content into digestible smart study guides that include chapter summaries, true-false and multiple-choice practice tests, and flashcards. JustTheFacts101 has a similar, though more streamlined purpose like highlighting and creating text and chapter-specific summaries, which are then archived into a digital collection and made available on Amazon. Other companies are creating smart digital content platforms, complete with content delivery, practice exercises, and real-time feedback and assessment. Netex Learning, allows educators to design digital curriculum and content across devices, integrating rich media like video and audio, as well as self- or online-instructor assessment. It also provides a personalized learning cloud platform designed for the modern workplace, in which employers can design customizable

like characters who can think, act, react, and interact naturally, responding to and using both verbal and nonverbal communication.

The University of Southern California Institute for Creative Technologies is a pioneer in creating smart virtual environments and applications that draw on AI, 3-D gaming, and computer animation to develop authentic virtual characters and realistic social interactions. USC researchers have some ongoing projects in the space that hint at applications to come over the next two decades.

Captivating Virtual Instruction for Training (CVIT) is a distributed learning strategy that aims to integrate live classroom methods with best-fit virtual technologies—including virtual facilitators, augmented reality, intelligent tutors, and others—in remote learning and training programs. As AI advances in this education domain, it seems there is more evidence to support the idea that both intelligent systems and humans are needed to manage different aspects of students' academic and social competencies. AI will likely not replace but will serve as an invaluable extension of the human expert, helping teachers to more effectively meet the diverse needs of many students simultaneously.

From facial recognition in the classroom to computers marking essays, China is wholeheartedly deploying new technologies into its education system. A recent report has revealed a high school in Eastern China is testing a new facial recognition system designed to analyze the engagement of students in a classroom, in real time.

An Intelligent classroom behavior management system scans the room every 30 seconds logging both the behavior of the students and their facial expressions. The system can identify seven moods, including happy, sad, afraid, and angry, by simply analyzing a student's face. A camera, perched atop the blackboard at the front of the classroom, also tracks six types of behavior: reading, writing, hand raising, standing up, listening to the teacher, and leaning on the desk.

In an even more striking and widespread implementation of Artificial Intelligence into the education system, a recent report from the South China Morning Post (SCMP) claimed one in four Chinese schools were experimenting with computer software to grade essays. The machine-

learning software has allegedly been in development for nearly a decade using deep learning algorithms to constantly learn and improve its ability to understand and evaluate a student's work. It is currently estimated that 60,000 schools are testing the technology and it can reportedly offer the same grade as a human marker up to 92 percent of the time (Subrahmanyam¹ & K. Swathi, 2018).

Automated marking systems are not an entirely new idea. While computer-assisted marking software has been around for almost as long as computers, it has only been in the last decade or two that computers have begun to be used for marking more abstract student work, such as argumentative essay writing. In China, these systems are implemented with degrees of scale that are unprecedented anywhere else in the world. China is currently training its neural network grading system in a central server that compiles the work of millions of students. As well as promising a potential way to take out the variations attributed to human subjectivity in marking, this system undoubtedly offers the central government a remarkable ability to track the progress of all students in the country, in real time.

And this frighteningly comprehensive monitoring of its education system could inevitably be synced up with the country's oncoming social credit system due for full activation by 2020. This proposed system will assign each citizen a social credit score that will determine a person's ability to travel overseas, get a home loan, or even access the internet.

Issues and Challenges of AI in Educational Creativity

As we all know, there are pros and cons associated with every technology — and AI is no exception to this rule. The following are some of the issues and challenges:

1. The AI project development environment is quite different. Most of the time, development is about identifying data sources and then gathering content, cleansing it, and curating it. Such an approach requires different skills and mindsets, as well as different methodologies. In addition, AI-powered intellectual systems have to be trained in a particular domain.

2. The slow digitization rate is affecting the adoption of AI technology in emerging economies, as the deployment of AI-enabled solutions requires IT infrastructures to generate accurate results. This factor may restrain the growth of the AI in education market.
3. To train machine learning algorithms one needs massive and clean data sets, with minimum biases.
4. One needs also to keep in mind data privacy issues when it comes to harvesting personal data, particularly in light of the General Data Protection Regulation that is coming into effect in 2018.
5. By 2018, Gartner predicts that 20% of all business content will be produced by machines. While there is evidence that AI is capable of creating certain kinds of content that is virtually indistinguishable from human content in terms of clarity and accuracy, machine-produced content is substantially more boring and less pleasant to read according to one study.
6. It's easy – and fun – to envision a complex collection of AI-driven components collaborating to create fully automated, perfectly personalized customer experiences. But that system will be prone to frequent failures as one or another component finds itself facing conditions it wasn't trained to handle.
7. When combining the cost of installation, maintenance, and repair, it's clear that AI is expensive. Only well-funded schools will find themselves in a position to benefit from AI.

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence is the most intriguing of technological advancements of our time. From creating advanced data-collecting algorithms to providing detailed and customized student feedback, AI shines as the most competent AI that can quickly interpret a student's needs and design an appropriate assessment. It can show students mastery, repeat lessons as needed, and quickly design a personalized learning plan for each student. AI could provide teachers with a virtual

teaching assistant. But more than just teachers and students, it can be a way to support parents by involving them in the learning environment of students and providing them with the information they need to help their students be successful when they're not in the classroom. The future likely holds a lot of possibilities for AI. This paper highlighted the Potential impacts of AI on educational creativity, some worldwide case studies, issues, and challenges associated.

Recommendations

1. The paper recommends a structuring of Artificial Intelligence research and creating policies to support AI in the future.
2. Educational institutions should adopt some of the best practices of some of the world's most advanced nations and regions that have encouraged the use of AI in higher education, which enhances students' learning opportunities, and boosts student engagement.
3. There should be more focus on implementing educational software using AI techniques like Data mining techniques and machine learning approaches as in other nations.
4. Policymakers, business captains, and individuals must leverage the opportunity that arises from the usage of Artificial Intelligence to fully harness the potential of digital transformation and sustainable development of the educational sector in Nigeria.

References

- Adeyeye, T.O., Akeem A., Ganiyu & Amusat K. K. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic and education sector in Nigeria: An overview. *Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCJSS)* ISSN: 2449092X Vol 6 (1) June 2021
- Adilakshmi, G, Chaitany, A, Poojitha, K. and Ashok Naik, M. (2021). Application of artificial intelligence in agriculture, *Just Agriculture* 1(10):1-3
- Brad Rose Consulting. (2019). *Robots Grade Your Essays and Read Your Resumes*. Brad Rose Consulting. Programme Evaluation. MA.

<https://bradroseconsulting.com/robots-grade-your-essays-and-read-your-resumes/>

- Chin, R. T. (2018). Education in the Artificial Intelligence Era - QS WOWNEWS. <https://qswownews.com/education-in-the-artificial-intelligence-era/>
- Deepanjah, S. and Adesh, K. (2022). The role of digital technologies in educational transformation. In book: *Transformation of Higher Education in Nepal: Dimensions, Dynamics and Determinants* (pp.140-154). Pokhara University
- Dizikes, P. (2020). How many jobs do robots really replace? MIT News. Massachusetts Institute of Technology. <https://news.mit.edu/2020/how-many-jobs-robots-replace-0504>
- Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2013). The Future of Employment How susceptible are jobs to computerisation? Oxford Martin School. 37–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.08.019>
- Jabar H. Yousif. (2011). Artificial intelligence in e-learning-pedagogical and cognitive aspects. *Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering*, 1, 997–1002.
- Kamalov, Firuz, David Santandreu Calonge, and Ikhlaas Gurrub. (2023). "New Era of Artificial Intelligence in Education: Towards a Sustainable Multifaceted Revolution" *Sustainability* 15, no. 16: 12451. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151612451>
- Kaplan, A, Haenlein, M, (2019). "Siri, Siri, in my hand: Who's the fairest in the land? On the interpretation, illustrations, and implications of artificial intelligence". *Business Horizons*, 62: 15-25.
- Ma, Y. & Siau, K.L. (2018). Artificial Intelligence Impacts on Higher Education. Proceedings of the Thirteenth Midwest Association for Information Systems Conference, May 17-18(September), 1–6.
- Mahana, M., Johns, M., & Apte, A. (2012). Automated Essay Grading Using Machine Learning. Machine Learning Session Stanford University, 3–7.
- Oblinger, D.G. (2018). What will AI and robotics mean for higher education? - eCampus News. <https://www.ecampusnews.com/2018/08/02/what-will-ai-and-robotics-mean-for-higher-education/>
- Pettersson, F. On the Issues of Digital Competence in Educational Contexts—A Review of Literature. *Educ. Inf. Technol.* 2018, 23, 1005–1021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9649-3>

- Redmond, D.P. From Face-to-Face Teaching to Online Teaching: Pedagogical Transitions. In Proceedings of the 28th Annual Conference of the Australasian Society for Computers in Learning in Tertiary Education (ASCILITE 2011), Hobart, Australia, 4– 7 December 2011.
- Stanford University. (2019). Artificial intelligence assessment. Teaching Commons.
<https://teachingcommons.stanford.edu/resources/teaching/evaluating-students/assessing-student-learning/artificial-intelligence-assessment>
- Subrahmanyam, V.V. and K. Swathi; Artificial Intelligence and its Implications in Education. International Conference on Improved Access to Distance Higher Education Focus on Underserved Communities and Uncovered Regions, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India 11-12 Aug, 2018
- Trendov, N. M., Varas, S. & M. Zeng (2019). Digital technologies in agriculture and rural areas – Status report. Rome.
<http://www.fao.org/3/ca4985en/ca498>
- UNESCO (2022). Report on the Impact of Covid-19 on Higher Education and the Future of Uninterrupted Learning in Eastern Africa Djibouti, Ethiopia, Kenya, Madagascar, Uganda. Design, Layout and Printing: UNON Publishing Services Section. Nairobi, Kenya UNESCO (21st June, 2023). UNESCO's education response to COVID-19.
- Wang, W. & Siau, K. (2017). Impact of Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Machine Learning, and Automation on the Medical Field. August 4–6.
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Keng_Siau/publication/318913468_Impact_of_Artificial_Intelligence_Robotics_Machine_Learning_and_Automation_on_the_Medical_Field/links/5984ef56458515605844f070/Impact-of-Artificial-Intelligence-Robotics-Machine-Learning
- Window. New York Times, 45(10), 672.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/MSPEC.2008.4635038>
- Wollny, S.; Schneider, J.; Di Mitri, D.; Weidlich, J.; Rittberger, M.; Drachslar, H. Are we there yet?-A systematic literature review. *Front. Artif. Intell.* 2021, 4, 654924.

A Corrupt Member in the Cabinet of Jesus Christ: A Template for Effective Management of Corruption in Nigeria

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Abstract

The word corruption can mean abuse of power, relationship and finances. Corruption became popular in Nigeria since independence, particularly during the regime of President Muhammadu Buhari who won 2015 election because of his promise to fight corruption. Previous studies have discussed the life and career of Judas Iscariot, the disciples of Jesus Christ and Jesus himself, but little has been said concerning Jesus' expertise in managing corrupt members of his cabinet especially Judas Iscariot. This paper, therefore, intends to scrutinize the activities of Judas Iscariot during the ministry of Jesus and how his Team Lead (Jesus) was able to cope with him. Emphasis is placed on John 12:4-6; 13:2, 26; 14:22. The methodologies used for this work are exegetical and historical approaches, while library sources were extensively utilized as tools for sourcing for information. The corrupt members of Jesus' cabinet are investigated with particular attention to Judas Iscariot. The technique used by Jesus to manage the corrupt members of his cabinet has been explored. Finally, corruption has been with human race from the beginning and it will continue to exist. What really matter is the effective management of the corrupt individuals and the resources in such a way that wastage and loss of valuables will be reduced to the minimal.

Keywords: Cabinet Member, Corruption, Effective Management, Jesus Christ, Judas Iscariot, Nigeria

Introduction

Corruption can relate to political power, finances and social relationship. Political corruption has to do with the abuse of office for personal gain,

including bribery, embezzlement and cronyism. It involves using power and influence for personal benefits, rather than serving the public interest. Social corruption is a broader concept that encompasses moral decay, erosion of values and social norms. It can include issues like nepotism, favouritism and discrimination, which undermine social cohesion and trust. While financial corruption is illegal activities involving money, such as bribery, money laundering, fraud and embezzlement. It can occur in various sectors, including business, government and non-profit organizations and often involves concealing or misusing funds for personal gain. The corruption in this paper can be associated with the three categories mentioned above. The sacred text, which is the Holy Bible; otherwise known as Holy Scriptures, identify Judas Iscariot as the most corrupt member of the disciples of Jesus. Amazingly there is no evidence in the Bible that Jesus sacked Judas Iscariot as the treasurer for the disciples. It is not clear how long he held this position. Bible does not mention Judas being removed from his position as treasurer at all. Judas's role as treasurer is mentioned in the Gospel of John 12:6 and 13:29. The Bible does mention that Judas was the one who betrayed Jesus for 30 pieces of silver as stipulated in Matthew 26:14-16, Mark 14:10-11, Luke 22:3-6, and John 13:2, though this event happened toward the end of Jesus' ministry. Since it is not clearly stated that Judas was sacked from his position, it is assumed that he (Judas) was still serving as treasurer at that time.

According to the New Testament, among other crimes he committed; Judas Iscariot is the apostle who betrayed Jesus for 30 pieces of silver as recorded in Matthew 26:14-16, Mark 14:10-11, Luke 22:3-6, John 13:2-30. His action led to Jesus' arrest and subsequent crucifixion. Peter denied knowing Jesus three times during his trial as mentioned in Matthew 26:69-75, Mark 14:66-72, Luke 22:54-62, and John 18:15-27. Thomas refused to believe in Jesus' resurrection without physical proof as stated in John 20:24-25. James and John: the sons of Zebedee asked for positions of power in Jesus' kingdom as mentioned in Matthew 20:20-28 and Mark 10:35-45. All the disciples fell asleep while praying with Jesus in the Garden of Gethsemane as recorded in Matthew 26:36-

46, Mark 14:32-42 and Luke 22:39-46. And they all fled in fear during Jesus' arrest as in Matthew 26:47-56, Mark 14:43-52 and Luke 22:47-53. These errors show that the disciples are human and prone to corruption, indiscipline and they were also struggling with faith, understanding and loyalty.

Judas Iscariot is the principal culprit among the disciples and he is mentioned specifically in the following verses of the New Testament – Matthew 10:14, 26:14; Mark 3:19, 14:10; Luke 6:16; John 12:4, 13:2, 26, 14:22. The Bible records that Judas Iscariot used to help himself with the money kept in his charge. He is known as a betrayer among the disciples. Matthew 10:4; Mark 3:19, 14:10; Luke 6:16 describe him as a traitor, a conspirator, and a collaborator. John 12:4 also calls him a betrayer. John 13:2 says that: "And during supper, when the devil had already put it into the heart of Judas Iscariot, Simon's son, to betray him..." The discussion that Jesus had with his disciples in John 13:21-26 reveals the fact that Jesus knew that Judas was a corrupt person, a deceiver, a person of doubtful character. (Amy, 2017). When Jesus had thus spoken, he was troubled in spirit, and testified, "Truly, truly, I say to you, one of you will betray me." The disciples looked at one another, uncertain of whom he spoke. One of his disciples, whom Jesus loved, was lying close to the breast of Jesus; so Simon Peter beckoned to him and said, "Tell us who it is of whom he speaks." Jesus answered, "It is he to whom I shall give this morsel when I have dipped it." So, when he had dipped the morsel, he gave it to Judas, the son of Simon Iscariot. The bottom line is that Judas Iscariot was popularly known as a corrupt person nearly from the beginning of the ministry of Jesus, yet Jesus did not sack him neither did he put him on suspension or placed him on any form of disciplinary measure. Again, few other scholars are not comfortable with this negative description of Judas Iscariot and some have reconstructed his life history. Which of the story can we believe? How did Jesus cope with this kind of a team member and there was no record of fight or serious disagreement between the two parties? How is the Church and society managing corrupt members in our respective local assemblies and headquarters? We need to dig deeper into the life and ministry of Judas

Iscariot in order to know the roles he played and how he played them and the responses of Jesus and other disciples to his characters? What management skills can the contemporary society learn from Jesus Christ on effective management of corrupt members of the team as we know that corruption and human being are inseparable? It should be noted that only the Gospel according to John provides us with numerous hints of Judas. The other gospel writers only mention the call of Judas and how he betrayed Jesus.

What is Corruption? Corruption is dishonest, illegal, or immoral behaviour especially from someone with power. To be dishonest means to be deceiving or cheating people (*Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, 2012). Dishonesty is associated to theft and acquisition of properties in a fraudulent way. This definition affirms that an aspect of corruption is stealing and deceit by the individuals. The term illegal simply means not allowed by the law (*Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, 2012) Anything the law of a country, state, local government or association does not allow is simply illegal. Immoral means morally wrong. So immoral behaviour refers to any behaviour that is wrong morally. For instance, it is conventionally acceptable that making people to suffer deliberately is immoral. Not following acceptable standards of sexual behaviour is immoral (*Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, 2012). Lateness to work is immoral. Negligence to duty is immoral. Use of official assets or facilities for private advantage without express approval by the appropriate governing council is immoral, littering of surroundings, sexual harassment, greed, gluttony, assassination of character, deceit and fraudulent activities are all amount to corruption.

Who was Judas Iscariot?

John 12:6 tells us that Judas Iscariot was the keeper of money – the Treasurer. According to John 6:63, Jesus knew the type of person Judas is and He has been talking about him directly and indirectly concerning his evil plan. It has been observed that Judas was unspiritual, carnal and he was a man who did not believe in Him as a Messiah (Yeulett, 2013) It

is believed that Jesus and his disciples needed to collect offerings and gifts from friends and followers to help them feed and clothe. But he was a thief as recorded in John 12:1-8. He suggested that the expensive oil that was poured on the head of Jesus be sold at three hundred pence and be given to the poor as in John 12:4-5. Feeding: Jesus and the disciples relied on the hospitality of others, such as Martha and Mary (Luke 10:38-42), and the support of women who followed Him (Luke 8:1-3). They also received food and other provisions from the crowds who followed Jesus (Matthew 15:29-39, Mark 8:1-10). Clothing: There is no specific mention of how Jesus and the disciples obtained clothing, but it's likely they received donations or support from their followers. Paying bills: The disciples had a common purse, managed by Judas, which contained money donated by supporters (John 12:6, 13:29). This fund covered expenses like food, lodging, and taxes (Matthew 17:24-27).

The book of Acts of the Apostles mentions that the disciples received support from wealthy followers like Joseph of Arimathea and Nicodemus in Acts 2:44-45, 4:32-37. The "Gospel of Philip" mentions that Jesus and the disciples were supported by a network of women who provided for their needs. The "Didache" (an early Christian text) suggests that traveling missionaries like Jesus and the disciples relied on the hospitality of local Christians. It's important to note that the extra-biblical accounts provide additional insights but may not be historically reliable or consistent with the biblical narrative. Regarding Judas' theft, the biblical account suggests that Jesus and the disciples were not aware of the extent of Judas' embezzlement. Despite this, they continued to rely on the common purse and the support of their followers to meet their needs. He was only callous he did not care for the poor as in John 12:6. He was a traitor as recorded in the following bible passages: Matt. 10:4; 26:16, 25; Mark 3:19; 14:10-11; Luke 6:16; 22:4, 6; John 6:71; 12:4; 18:2, 5; Acts 1:16, 18, 25. Satan had controlled Judas Iscariot as in John 6:70-71. Satan is his spiritual father as in John 17:12. Satan put the desire in Judas Iscariot. Satan entered into Judas twice, first prior to the event at the upper room (John 13:2) and secondly in the upper room (John 13:27). Short Statistics of Judas Iscariot: First mentioned in

Matthew 10:4. Final mentioned in Acts 1:25. Meaning of his name – Praise. Frequency of his name – 22 times. Five biblical books that mentioned his name are Matthew, Mark, Luke, John and Acts. His occupation is Apostle. Place of birth – probably Judean city of Kerioth. Circumstances of his death – he hanged himself (Matthew 27:5; Acts 1:18). He was the apostle who betrayed Jesus (Wilmington, 2018). It has been noted that people of lower class do not have last name in the New Testament era, but Judas has and his last name is Iscariot. This shows that he belonged to high class (Ehrman, 2006). There are other Judases in the sacred texts such as Judas the brother of Jesus as mentioned in Mark 6:3, and John 14:22 also talks about another Judas different from Judas Iscariot; this Judas (also known as Jude) is the author of the shortest book in the New Testament. The description of Judas Iscariot can be found in the following verses of the sacred texts: Matthew 10:14, 26:14; Mark 3:19, 14:10; Luke 6:16; John 12:4, 13:2, 26, 14:22. The meaning of the name is not certain, but scholars have proposed the following meaning though none is yet to be universally adopted. A nineteenth century scholar suggested that the name Iscariot came from Hebrew word which connotes ‘to top up’ and that his throat was stopped up because he died by strangling (Ehrman, 2006) About ten decades after, some scholars said that the name Iscariot is from Semitic word ‘*isqa*’ re ‘*ut*’ which likely suggests someone who makes money out of friendship. And probably from the tribe of Issachar (he was Issachariot). Some felt that the term Iscariot sounds more of Latin word for ‘*dagger-sica*’ – and is likely to be the Jewish dagger assassin known as ‘*sicarii*’ and this suggests that Judas was a Jewish zealot who advocate violence against Roman Empire. Some said his name is from Hebrew word ‘*saqqar*’ which means ‘*liar*’ and it actually describes his person as described by the sacred tests. There are more possibilities about the meaning of the name Iscariot but none is yet to be accepted by the linguists who were intimately familiar with the ancient Semitic language (Ehrman, 2006). The most common explanation is that Iscariot is from Hebrew word ‘*ish kerioth*’ which might mean something like ‘*a man who comes from the village of Kerioth*’. If this is true, the name Kerioth is

mentioned in Joshua 15:25 – it belongs to the southern part of Israel and it was later known as Judea. The implication of this is that this would make Iscariot the only southerner among the followers of Jesus. In Jeremiah 48: 24 and 41 mention another Kerioth that was outside Israel but it is very unlikely that Jesus close associate would come from any of these two places. Some top scholars concluded that we do not know the meaning of Iscariot (Gathercole, 2007).

The only book which contradicted the records of the Gospels concerning Judas is *Gnostic Gospel of Judas Iscariot*, the book which was considered heretical by Irenaeus. It was written around 180AD and was brought to the attention of the international community in 2006. It was written by Cainites who venerated the biblical character of Cain who killed Abel his brother. This same author also describes God as evil. Therefore, his view cannot be taken seriously by many researchers. (Sorensen, 2021). Throughout the Christian tradition Judas has been portrayed as the rotten apple in the apostolic barrel. Some claimed that he was inherently evil and that he was Christ-killer. Some commentators did not portray Judas Iscariot as a demonically inspired or money-grubbing betrayer of the cause but as the one disciple who both understood Jesus and did his will (Ehrman, 2006). He is the one who leads the way. He is the thirteenth, because Matthias replaced him after he died as a result of the sorrow he had for his master. Only he had the glimpse of the truth and therefore Jesus revealed the most sacred information to him. As a sign of kindness to Jesus, Judas rendered the most sacred service unto Jesus by handling him over to the authorities who needed a closest person to Jesus to hand him over. Judas Iscariot probably thought that matters were getting out of hand and he wanted Jesus securely taken out of the way before any violence broke out. But he was most likely frustrated because of the delay of Jesus' promise about their upliftment in the kingdom of Jesus Christ (Bultmann, 1953). He reflected on all he had heard along with other disciples. It is believed by some researchers that he had crisis of faith, activated by Jesus' mysterious allusions to his own coming death. May be out of bitterness, he turned to his own master when his expectations were sunk. He helped

Jesus to reach heaven and he is a star in the sky (Sorensen, 2021). Judas Iscariot is the greatest of all the disciples because he helped Jesus to fulfil the climax of his mission on earth and this act of generosity of him provided salvation to the whole human race. No wonder, Jesus said to him, “You will exceed them all, for you will sacrifice the man who clothed me”

In summary Judas Iscariot can be described as enumerated below:

- i. A leader or member of the Zealots (a party of Jews who advocated armed rebellion from Rome), who supported Jesus until the latter refused to become king.
- ii. A friend of Jesus who essentially helped him to do his duty and commit suicide after.
- iii. A negotiator between Jesus and the Jewish authorities.
- iv. A dupe – he did not fully understand what he was doing.
- v. A character invented by the Gospel writers because they supposedly needed a villain. The Greek name “Judas” (“Judah” in Hebrew, the source of the word “Jew”) in this view was purposely employed as an anti-Semitic device (Sorensen, 2021).

Other Corrupt Members in the Cabinet of Jesus

As a matter of fact, the disciples expected something different from Jesus Christ. They were all expecting him to function as a political deliverer from the oppression of the Roman power. (Barrett, C. K. 1996. *The New Testament Background*. London: SPCK) As recorded in Mark 9:34 and 10:35–37; they also had high expectations for themselves and they were already lobbying and discussing who will be the first Vice President and the second Vice President. Could it be said that the disciples are corrupt? Were they not responding to the promises of their master (Jesus) that the poor, powerless and meek would be exalted? Who else could be as poor and powerless as the disciples of Jesus? The disciples never expected Jesus to be arrested, molested, tortured and killed. The truth is that the disciples did not understand fully the mission of Jesus Christ and therefore their attitude could not correlate perfectly with the expectations of their master (Ehrman, 2006) Simon Peter also denied

Jesus and this act is also a form of corruption. It is equivalent to the offence of Judas Iscariot as recorded in Matthew 26: 58, 69, 73, 75; Mark 14:54, 66, 67, 70, 72, Luke 22:54, 55, 58, 60, 61. It must be noted that all the disciples were indicted for corruption in Matthew 26:6-13 and Mark 14:5-10, where a woman suggested to be Mary the sister of Martha poured a very expensive oil on the head of Jesus Christ. The author of the first gospel says in verse 8: “But when the disciples saw it, they were indignant, saying, “Why this waste?” RSV. They were irritated, they were annoyed. They were disappointed in Jesus Christ. They did not know that Jesus could allow someone to pour such an expensive oil on his head. Considering the simplicity of Jesus Christ from his birth till then, the disciples should not be blamed for reasoning that way. The disciples did not know the purpose of the oil that was poured on the head of Jesus Christ.

What Did Judas Betray and Why Did He Betray It?

If we maintain that Jesus was principally a Jewish rabbi who taught his followers that they should love one another, why would Romans execute him for that? Did Pontius Pilate say, “Oh no, we can’t have you loving one another, and we definitely don’t want you to love us, your enemies. Or if Jesus’ overarching concern was with the status of women in first-century Palestine, would Pilate have been angered at the idea and deemed him worthy of death? Or if Jesus principally taught his disciples that they should be like Cynic philosophers and spurn material things in favor of the spiritual, would Pilate have decided Jesus needed to be tormented, maimed, and executed? Any account of Jesus’ life must explain his death. If Jesus had been a political revolutionary, that would explain his death. The Romans in that case would have tried him on political charges and executed him. The problem is that Jesus appears to have been a pacifist. He never raised an army and never advocated the violent overthrow of the empire. Of course, the Romans might have thought Jesus was an insurrectionist, even if he wasn’t. But there’s a better explanation for why they sought to put him to death. He didn’t take up the sword against the Romans because in his view he knew that

he didn't need to. He knew that the empire was soon to be overthrown—not by the armies he would lead against Rome, but by God himself, in an imminent act of judgment. Jesus was one of those apocalypticists who predicted a future violence, brought not by humans but from heaven. When he went into the Temple the last week of his life and overturned the tables of the money changers and the people selling sacrificial animals, it was a symbolic statement that God's judgment was soon to arrive and destroy that place. The holy place? The sanctuary of God? Yes, God's judgment would hit even there. The rulers of the people had grown powerful and corrupt, they collaborated with the Romans, and they would be destroyed when God's judgment came. It is no wonder the Jewish leaders did not take kindly to Jesus, fearing he would cause unrest among the people. He was preaching against them, so they decided to have him taken out of the way. That was not particularly unusual. Actually, it was a common fate of apocalyptic prophets of coming judgment. It is what happened to John the Baptist before Jesus. And it is what happened to other apocalyptic prophets in Palestine after his death. The Roman authorities were quick and ruthless when it came to anyone preaching against them, whether they were influencing others to take up weapons or maintaining that God himself was going to intercede. Anyone that is very frank and passionate in their opposition to those in power were dealt with in kind. But, of course, there had to be grounds for prosecution (even if they were wrong or misguided). Which leads me back to my question: if it is beyond reasonable doubt that Jesus was condemned for claiming to be King of the Jews, yet there is no record of him calling himself this publicly in our early sources, how do we explain the charge? (Ehrman, 2006). Jesus considered himself to be a king, they would have the information they needed. They couldn't get this information from what they heard Jesus preach, of course. It was not his public proclamation but his private instruction to the disciples, his co-rulers in the future Kingdom. But Judas told them what they needed to hear.

The Jewish leaders arranged to have Jesus arrested. They used the betrayer to lead them to him. Then they put Jesus on trial, asking him:

“Are you the Messiah?” He had to answer truthfully, and so he revealed what he considered to be the truth: yes, he was the one who would rule the future Kingdom. The authorities then handed him over to the Roman governor for trial. That is precisely why Pilate put Jesus on trial for calling himself King of the Jews even though this was not his public message. Jesus thought he would be the Messiah of the coming Kingdom, that is, the future king. So, when he was asked by Pilate, he either spoke the truth, that he was the king, or at least didn’t deny they charge. How could he? This was the heart of his message. The Romans saw this as political insurgency. Pilate ordered his crucifixion. Jesus was flogged and executed on the spot. And so, we have the historical explanation for why Jesus was killed for calling himself King of the Jews when in public he never did so. Judas betrayed the information. This understanding of what Judas really betrayed makes much better sense than the standard explanation. In the Gospels, the only thing Judas does is show the authorities where they can arrest Jesus privately. But that is scarcely much of a betrayal.

If the authorities wanted to know where Jesus was, they could have had him followed. There was no need to hire an insider. The alternative explanation given here makes sense of all the data:

- Jesus taught his followers, privately, that they would rule in the Kingdom.
- He also taught them that he would be their ruler, as the king in the Kingdom (the messiah).
- He was executed for calling himself King of the Jews, even though he never called himself that publicly.
- He was later revered by Christians as the messiah, even though he did nothing the messiah was supposed to do. The reason they did so: he was known to be the messiah before his death, because that’s what he himself taught (Ehrman, 2006).

Did Judas Know that His Betrayal Would Lead to Jesus' Death?

In the Gospel, Judas allowed himself to be used for the arrest of Jesus which subsequently led to the murder of Jesus. That is the point of the betrayal: to allow Jesus to escape his mortal body to return to the realm of the Spirit. But this account was written a century after the fact by a Gnostic who saw liberation from this material world to be the greatest good imaginable, and who told his story about Jesus and Judas in light of his own belief. In two of our canonical Gospels, Mark and John, Judas completely disappears from the scene after the betrayal, so there is no evidence of what he felt afterward. But it is striking that in our earliest report, Mark's, Judas instructs those arresting Jesus to take him away "securely" (Mark 14:44; sometimes translated too loosely as "under guard"). This is an odd statement, and some interpreters have thought that it indicates that Judas was afraid Jesus might try to escape. But another option is that he didn't want anything amiss to happen to Jesus, that he wanted him to be kept safe (the term could also be translated "safely" instead of "securely"). If so, then the outcome of the betrayal may have come as a surprise to Judas. Maybe he simply wanted Jesus taken out of the way because he too was afraid riots might start, and he didn't want Jesus—or the disciples—to be hurt in the mayhem. Maybe he didn't expect that handing Jesus over to the authorities would lead to a death sentence, but simply assumed that they would keep Jesus for questioning, find out that he had no political objectives, and let him go as another prophet with high hopes for the future. This might make sense of the tradition found in Matthew that Judas felt remorse once he saw that "Jesus was condemned," and that he then tried to return the money he had made off the deal. Why would Jesus' condemnation lead to remorse? Only if that had not been the goal of the betrayal in the first place. Possibly Matthew also understood Judas as being intent not on Jesus' death but only on his being safely removed from the public eye until the festival had ended. When things did not turn out as he had planned, Judas was torn with guilt and grief, and hanged himself.

Why, Then, Did Judas Do It?

The Gospels of course give various answers to this question. In the Gospel of Judas, he betrays Jesus because that's what Jesus wants him to do. In our earlier accounts there are a range of different reasons given: John portrays Judas as inherently evil, "a devil," and so naturally he did what he was inclined to do; Luke suggests that "the Devil made him do it"; Matthew indicates that he did it for the cash. But what was the real motivation behind Judas's act? At the end of the day, I'm afraid we can't know for certain. It might be that the scenario I've suggested above is the right one, that Judas simply wanted Jesus removed from public view until after the festival had ended and they could return to Galilee to continue their public preaching. But there's another option that might be even more intriguing, possibly hinted at in Mark, our earliest surviving account.

Management Skills of Jesus Christ

The mishap of development and enlargement of church today is informed by the high premium placed on leadership positions in the church and the mode of handling church property and possessions. (Oduwaga, 2022). The management skills applied by Jesus Christ to supervise the corrupt disciples include: leadership by example, raising funds miraculously to meet the immediate needs, putting less fund in the safe, running cashless financial activities, paying less attention to the position of the treasurer, encouraging direct services from the supporters of Jesus' ministry, giving opportunity to the corrupt person to leave and death penalty for the chief offender (Nwizu, 1997).

Leadership by example – Jesus himself did not handle money directly during his earthly ministry. He used his disciples. He played down on earthly materials and focus more on things that are of life after death. Jesus stayed away from everything that could corrupt him such as women (he did not marry), money (he did not handle money directly) position (he was not ambitious about earthly position but sought for the kingdom of God). Since he was a clean person and it was very difficult for anyone to accuse him of any evil, it was very easy for him to manage

the corrupt members of his cabinet, particularly, Judas Iscariot (Alister, 1987).

Raising funds miraculously to meet immediate needs - In Matthew 17:24-27, Christ was at Capernaum – (his headquarters and where he most resided) where if Jesus disbursed any money to each of the disciples for the journey as most Churches do today (Treat, 1971). Church gives pocket money, food items/provisions and medical facilities/personnel to the participants that are going to the mission field for a week or two weeks. But Jesus told his own disciples not to worry about those things for whatever they needed would be divinely provided at the right time. In another words, the office of Judas Iscariot was ignored and rendered less important. In John 2:1-11, where Jesus turned water to wine, if it were to be in today's dispensation; the church leader would be expected to release some fund to purchase more wine. If that was what Jesus did perhaps, he would have invited Judas Iscariot to bring out some money from the common pus to purchase more wine for the wedding. But Jesus disregarded money and the treasurer by turning water into wine. Management of a corrupt member of his cabinet became very easy when there was no need no frequent ask for the money in the custody of Judas Iscariot.

Encouraging direct services from the supporters of Jesus' ministry - Attitude and reaction of Judas Iscariot to the generosity of a good woman in Matthew 26:6-13 and Mark 14:5-10 and the erroneous step that was taken by Judas Iscariot in the subsequent verses show clearly that Judas Iscariot wanted more money in the common pus, but wished to also determine the purpose it must be used for. A woman that was suggested to be Mary, the sister of Marta and Lazarus says that it is the same as Mary Magdalene (Henry, 2006). Pouring oil on someone will be a strange form of complement in our contemporary society, but then it was a glorious honour for a highly placed person. Judas Iscariot was not having the same mind with his master. His mind was corrupt. Here Jesus encouraged the woman and others to donate generously towards his ministry. Judas Iscariot betrayed Jesus shortly after this incidence. Was it because the honour that that woman gave to Jesus was too much in the

eye of Judas? Definitely, Judas was offended by the honour received by Jesus and it was the last straw that broke the camel's back. He went straight to betray Jesus and handed him over to his enemies. A corrupt member in the cabinet of Jesus Christ was corrupt from the beginning to the end. Jesus gave the corrupt members the opportunities to repent as indicated in John 13:27. Even after he betrayed Jesus, nothing stopped him from repenting and Jesus would have accepted him, but he chose to kill himself. Leadership is, if possible, a way of inspiring and encouraging subordinates to achieve allotted responsibilities (Ajibade, 2022).

Giving opportunity to the corrupt person to leave – in John 6:67 and other places quoted above, Jesus actually gave Judas many privileges to leave but he refused to go. For instance, it can be very frustrating if you are in a position and your position is rendered almost ineffective and useless. Jesus used various supernatural method to provide cash, food, means of transportation and wine during a wedding and disregarded the Treasurer: Judas Iscariot by refusing to give or ask for money from the pus he was keeping (Yeulett, 2013). Death penalty – Jesus knew that the corruption of a corrupt person will eventually swallow him. Judas killed himself after he collected money from the accusers of Jesus and betrayed his LORD (Awojobi, 2021).

Conclusion

It is a fact that human being generally is not perfect. We all have our strength and weaknesses. The weaknesses could be regarded as corrupt aspect of human life. Judas Iscariot was so corrupt to the extent that he did not repent from his wickedness, instead he committed suicide. Some are of the opinion that he repented, but the Greek word used is not *μετανοεω* which means "I repent". The Greek word used is *μεταμελομαι* which connote regret or remorse. It should be noted that such regret does not necessarily involve modification of character and therefore, repentance cannot take place. (Robert, 1998). Jesus did not allow the corrupt member of his cabinet to have his way as he wanted by using diplomatic methods to check his excesses and to ensure that the tasks of the ministry continue without delay. The responses of Jesus to the

outstanding corrupt members of his cabinet are worth mentioning. The sin of Peter is referred to as denial while that of Judas Iscariot is referred to as betrayer. In Luke 22:22, he predicted a curse over whosoever betrayed him (“Jimmy” Again III, 2014) But in the case of Peter in Luke 22:32, Jesus said to Peter “... But I have prayed for you that your faith may not fail...” According to Matthew 10:2-4, Mark 3:16-19, and Luke 6:14-16, the name Judas Iscariot has been affiliated to betrayal and treachery. In fact, the name of this disciple of Jesus almost became a synonym for the word betrayal (Yeulett, 2013). The sin of Judas Iscariot was deliberate and intentional unlike Peter who determined and vowed not to deny Jesus but could not keep to his promise due to human weakness (Yeulett, 2013).

References

- Alfred, Tresidder Sheppard (2016). *The Autobiography of Judas Iscariot*. London: George Allen & UnWin, LTD.
- Ajibade, E. O. (2022). *Jesus’ Model of Leadership Development: Simon Peter as an Exemplar*. In *Leadership, Mission, and Church Growth in Africa*. Dada A. O. ed. Ibadan: Zenith Bookhouse.
- Amy, B. (2017). *Fascinating Facts about the Disciples*. Update: Mysteries. www.mysteries
- Alister, M. C. Grath (1987). *Understanding Jesus*. Eastbourne: Kingway.
- Awojobi, O. P. (2021). *Fundamental issues in the church administration*. Ilorin: Kingdom Power Communication
- Barrett, C. K. (1996). *The New Testament Background*. London: SPCK
- Bultmann, R. (1953). “*New Testament and Mythology*” *Kerygma and the Myth* (ed. H. W. Bartsch; tr. R.H. Fuller; London: SPCK).
- Dada, A. O. (2012). “*Repositioning Contextual Biblical Hermeneutics in Africa Towards Holistic Empowerment*” *Black Theology: An International Journal* 8:2.
- Ehrman, Bart. D. (2006). *The Lost Gospel of Judas Iscariot*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Green, J. B. (2010). *Hearing the New Testament*. Strategies for Interpretation. Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company
- Gathercole, Simon (2007). *The Gospel of Judas*. Vol. 118. London: Sage Publications. 209-215.

- Henry, Matthew (2006). *Matthew Henry's Commentary on the Whole Bible*. Vol.5.o.2. Bible Soft Inc
- Harold, Wilmington (2018). "A Biographical Study of Judas Iscariot" *New Testament Biographies*. 26.
- Iruoma I. N. (2004). *Church Management in Today's World*. Owerri: Krison.
- "Jimmy", C. D. Again III (2014). *The Imitation of Christ in the Gospel of Luke: Growing in Christ like Love for God and Neighbour*. New Jersey: P & R Publishing. 164.
- Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*. Edinburgh Gate: Pearson Education Limited.
- Nwizu, G. (1997). *Eminent Administrative Thinkers*.
- Odonuga, J. O. (2022). *John Wesley Effective Leadership Styles and Its Impacts on Contemporary Methodist Church Leaders*. In *Leadership, Mission and Church Growth in Africa*. Dada O. A. ed. Zeneth Bookhouse Ltd. Ibadan: Nigeria.
- Robert, Lee Shank (1998). *Life in the Son*. Minnesota: Bethany House Publishers. 324.
- Yeulett, Paul (2013). *Jesus and His Enemies*. New Jersey: P & R Publishing. 152. scholarlycommunication@liberty.edu.
- Sorensen, Richard. B. (2011). *Fact or Fiction – Judas Iscariot –* <https://richardsorensen.com/>
- Treat C. (1971). *Church Management: Leading People in the Church Growth*. Washington. Casey.

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YAHWEH's Reprobation of the Shepherds of Israel (Ezekiel 34:1-10) in the Context of the 21st Century Church Leadership in Nigeria

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Abstract

The shepherd-leader motif has occupied a pride of place in scholarship, it is found in various texts of the Old Testament and the New Testament. One of such texts that has increasingly come to the fore is Ezekiel 34, concerning the nature and function of pastoral leadership. Though it may be argued that in the studies of pastoral leadership, some scholars have discussed the implication of the motif of 'shepherd-leadership' in Ezekiel 34 for modern ecclesiastical structure. Nevertheless, the nexus between the ineptitude and corrupt dispositions of Christian leadership practices in Nigeria in the 21st century and YAHWEH's reprobation of the profiteering and corrupt shepherds of Israel has not gained considerable attention. This leaves a lacuna in literature filled by this paper, which focuses on contextualisation of the shepherd motif of Ezekiel 34:1-10 and its lessons for pastoral ministries and Church leadership in Nigeria using rhetorical textual criticism/analytical approach. This is based on Clines (2014)'s rhetorical criticism as the theoretical framework. Rhetorical criticism focuses on "the way the language of the selected texts is deployed to convey meaning"

(Clines, 2014: 31). Findings reveals that, like the shepherds of Israel condemned by YAHWEH many Nigerian Church leaders in the 21st century have become economically bankrupt, sexually corrupt, and lacking integrity in many fronts. This is a great departure from God's expectation of His shepherds. However, the life, leadership and contributions of many faithful church leaders who had joined the Church triumphant and some who are still part of the church militant are praise worthy. It is recommended therefore, that probity, civility and integrity should be promoted among church leaders in Nigeria.

Keywords: Christian Leadership in Nigeria, Church, 21st century, Exegesis of Ezekiel 34: 1-10, Shepherds of Israel, YAHWEH

Introduction

The shepherd motif is found throughout the Bible. In the Old Testament God strong rebuked and warned bad shepherds. He also prophesied the coming of a good shepherd. In the New Testament, Jesus identifies himself as the Good Shepherd and we find in the epistles the notion of good shepherding extended to those who would lead in the church. This paper unravels the pains associated with the lapses among some Church leaders in Nigeria in the 21st century. These include economic profiteering, hypnotism, sexual immorality, inordinate ambition for leadership positions, false prophesies and idolatry. This will serve as a reminder to present-day Church leaders of the demands of leadership calling; it will also present a blueprint for Christian leaders on carrying out the divine assignment of guiding and guarding God's people with utmost care and sense of responsibility to God. The theoretical framework is premised on Clines (2014) theory which is "in the devices of writing, in metaphor and parallelism, in narrative and poetic structures, and stylistic figures" (Clines, 2014: 32). In principle, this approach focuses on the actual situation of the composition and promulgation of ancient texts and their intended effect upon their audience" (Clines, 2014: 32). Muilenburg (2007) writes that "the ultimate goal of rhetorical analysis is to discover the authorial intention and how that is transmitted through a text to an audience". Furthermore, this approach is also known as "close reading." Therefore, it engaged a

rhetorical criticism or close reading of the “shepherd motif” in Ezekiel 34:1-10 to ascertain the contextual intention of the prophecy to make valuable inferences for the contemporary Christian leadership in Nigeria.

The “shepherd” motif runs deep and wide throughout the Old Testament (Rodgers, 2010: 2), and the New Testament (Gan, 2007: 12). This shepherd imagery is often associated with the leadership of varying kinds, from patriarchs to kings, prophets to Israel’s leaders (Gan, 2007: 12). In the Old Testament, two prominent figures Moses and David are seen as ideal shepherds of Israel. Moses led the people of Israel during the exodus and reception of the Torah, he spent four decades shepherding flocks. David was Israel’s greatest king. He was out in the fields shepherding when the prophet Samuel anointed him king over Israel. These two prominent leaders in Israel’s history oversaw important events such as the exodus and the establishment of the kingdom (Laniak, 2012: 42-93). It may be said that their background as shepherds aided their sense of responsibility and accountability in leadership. As such, there is a close relationship between leader and shepherd. In fact, in the second book of Samuel, Yahweh introduces the two tasks as the same, “You will shepherd my people Israel and will become their ruler” (2 Sam. 5:2). Therefore, the term ‘shepherd’ is synonymous with leadership in Ancient Israel’s cultural milieu. Subsequently, the rise and fall of Israel’s society were tied to the leadership abilities of the shepherds of Israel. The survival and continual fidelity of the nation to YAHWEH, with whom they had a covenant, is seen to depend on the religious policies of the shepherds of Israel. Furthermore, Taylor (1983: 7) writes that the concept of pastoral ministry is related to the idea of shepherding. The shepherd is a well-known figure among many rural peoples, and in ancient Israel, everyone understood what the work of a shepherd was.

Most Nigerians in the 21st century living both in the rural and the urban cities do not understand the world of shepherds; however, the poor perception of most people is the aggressive killings, wanton destruction

of farm lands and kidnapping credited to the herdsmen in Nigeria (Atowoju, 2007: 21).

The idea of the caring shepherd was so familiar and meaningful to the people of Israel that many preachers and writers use it as a picture language about God and the human shepherd. Leupold (1971: 87) thinks that “The shepherd image has a long association with spiritual leadership within the Judeo-Christian tradition, and there are many instances of the term being thus employed. It is also clear that problems and difficulties with the shepherd of the people of God are no new occurrence. Some of the most scathing indictments voiced in the Word of God are directed at those who have exercised the role of shepherd poorly, resulting in much harm to the flock.”

Influence of Church Leadership in Nigeria

The leadership of God’s people has always been a matter of utmost interest to God due to the pivotal role it plays in the overall good and well-being of the assembly or community of God, particularly, in fulfilling the divine purpose by individual members in their specific micro-environment and the larger society. God recognises that the depravity of the flesh does not allow humankind to do what is right when left alone unguarded, and unguided; therefore, he invented the principle of leadership and authority. He appoints individuals as leaders to be guides and guardians to his people. God expects those selected and assigned to lead his people to adhere strictly to his patterns and not otherwise. Therefore, he holds these individuals personally responsible for exercising the authority that he gives them. As a result of the divine involvement, significant power and control are vested in the leadership of the community’s religious practice (Atowoju, 2007: 53)

With the advent of Christianity in Nigeria in the late 19th century and on gaining firm grounds, the church has contributed enormously to the development of the country, socially, economically, politically and religiously. Junaid-Eko (2003) notes that formal schools were established in various parts of the country as accompaniment to founding of churches where classes were held, and payment of teachers’

salaries and allowances became the responsibility of the church. In these schools, the pupils were taught to read the scripture, the catechism and commandments in Yoruba and to utter some words in English (177-178). The early church leadership in Nigeria used an education framework to impact lives and infuse western civilization. As early as 1859, CMS Grammar School was established on Lagos Island. (Junaid-Eko, 2003: 178). According to Junaid-Eko (2003):

Islam predated Christianity in Lagos for about a century, but access to Western education by Muslims was not possible. The Church Missionary Society (CMS) brought the young minds to attend their schools, but the Muslim parents did not wholly approve of the type of education brought by the evangelists. Dr O. Johnson took time off in 1855 to speak to some influential Muslims on the advantages of Western education and advised them to send their children to schools. Some Muslim parents did not totally ignore this appeal. They sent their children to Christian Missionary Schools. Christianity was then firmly established in Christian schools. In 1893, there were 412 Muslim children in the thirty-three government-assisted Christian mission schools in Lagos colony.

In several other parts of the country agriculture, small scale industries and provisions of white-collar jobs were introduced to the citizens by the church. In 1860, Bishop Samuel Ajayi Crowther established the first primary school in Northern Nigeria named Holy Trinity Primary School, Lokoja (Danfulani and Atowoju, 2012: 79). The school is situated in the premises of Anglican Church, Lokoja. Furthermore, in 1915, Etinan Institute, Etinan, Akwa Ibom, was established by Qua Iboe Mission with Mr. R.J. Taylor as the first principal. The school is co-educational employing as many as 73 youth coppers annually, thus, becoming one of the highest employers of corps members (Etinan-<http://akwaibomschools.com>). Besides evangelism, the Christian missionaries opened dispensaries, clinics, maternity homes, and medical centres to fight diseases and cater for the health of the people.

Many people became Christians in order to have access to these medical services (Osoba and Yusuf, 2003: 32).

Osoba and Yusuf (2003) also note that the Christian involvement in the creation of social order in Nigeria was very apparent. They emphasise that the 19th century was characterised in the Yoruba kingdom by social feud, pandemonium, and misdemeanour. Each tribe rose against the other, the kingdom knew no more political stability, and lives became unsafe because of the incessant raid and spasmodic kidnappings. At the start of the missionary enterprises in Nigeria, missionaries described Lagos as one of the darkest places on earth, full of the habitation of cruelty and the headquarters of the horrible human sacrifices and qualified it as “veritable den of satanic wickedness and diabolical cruelty, heathenism, barbarity and detestable enormities” perhaps because of the horror of slave trade and human sacrifices at Breadfruit Street then (172). The efforts of church leaders ameliorated these societal ills. Asaju (1995) credited Christianity as a faith radically different from others, because of its peaceful means of conversion and relationship with others which is based on love (187).

According to Adekoya, the early contributions of the Church Missionary Society (C.M.S.) in building the primitive Yoruba society in education, healthcare, social, and political development cannot be over emphasised (55). Over the years, the church has indeed influenced the educational structure of Nigeria. Adekoya posits that the advent of Anglicanism and other branches of Christianity in Nigeria, particularly Lagos, turned the slavery and kidnapping customs of the pre-colonial state into that of civilised development centres. (56) He argued that the activities of the Lagos Anglican dioceses are visible in the areas of church political awareness, increased membership and parishes, job creation, economy, social services, development of infrastructural facilities and enviable leadership. However, his comments on desirable leadership focused mainly on the church’s political involvement (Adekoya 58). In contemporary times, some of these feats have continued as some denominations in Nigeria have established health care facilities, for instance, the Cathedral Church of Christ Marina Lagos and Our Saviour’s

Anglican Church, Tafawa Balewa Square have well-equipped and functioning Church Clinics that attend to aged members and children *for gratis*.

The Misdemeanor of Some Nigerian Church Leaders in the 21st Century in the Context of Ezekiel 34: 1-10

Most Nigerians are gracefully religious, simple minded, naive and unquestionably committed to faith and the directives of their Church leaders. Christian leaders over the years have contributed enormously to the development of the country, social security, support system and welfare of their followers. However, the recent misdemeanours among some church leaders have brought a lot of disrepute to the body of Christ, these include outright corruption, involvement in ritual killings, kidnapping, money laundry, false prophesy, heretical teachings, etc. In 2009, one of the church leaders in Amuwo Odofin, Lagos State asked his followers to drink the water used in washing his legs, in July 2010, a Pastor at Ewekoro, Ogun State was arrested and his Church demolished for killing and burying a woman later alleged to be his concubine under his alter in the Church, in 2011, a pastor in Oyo State asked all his members to eat grass like goats at a crusade and they did, in 2015 one asked his female members praying for fruits of the womb to put their hands on his genitals and they did. In December 2019, a pastor was arranged by Police Inspector General –Mohammad Abubakar Adamu, at Igbosere, Lagos State for allegedly sending a six-man gang of suspected assassins to kill a female pastor over popularity (Punch, Newspaper, 4 December, 2019). In May 2020, a Pastor in Omuo-Oke, Ekiti State asked members of his church to pay N310,000 each to get flight to heaven (Sahara Reporters: Ekiti State Police invite Nigerian Pastor Who Asked Members to Pay N310,000 to get flight to Heaven, accessed on 2nd June, 2023). In June 2022, a General Overseer in Owerri, Imo State, asked his members to bribe his angels generously for them to receive miracles. In June 2023 the General Overseer of the Altar of Solution Assembly based in Oyingbo, Rivers State was sentenced to death by Justice S.O. Benson for multiple murders. The story is endless,

shameful and irritating, many people, particularly, the youths have left the church and openly rejected the faith because of the nefarious activities of some Church leaders.

Nevertheless, a considerable number of Nigerian church leaders (who are remnants for God in a dying World) are still spiritually alert, living sacrificially, committing their lives and personal resources to the development of the country and the church, helping and giving godly examples, care and counselling to the faithful and others outside the church. Their contributions are evident in the provision of welfare package to the less privilege members of the society, giving scholarships for education to destitute and talented children from primary schools to tertiary institutions (Colleges and Universities), health care facilities, small scale industries, giving social support to individuals and families, provision of essential infrastructures and many more to members of their congregation and non- Christians alike. The Redeem Christian Church for instance offers free medical services to both Christians and non-Christians in Abuja, Lagos, Bauchi State, Borno State and other places in Nigeria and overseas (Onyedika-Ugoeze, 2023, March 23: 5). Over the years, the Baptist Church, the Four Square Gospel Church and the Anglican Church in Nigeria have been involved in establishing schools, universities, hospices, building community roads, sinking boreholes for communities, giving scholarships and other social welfare assistances to their members and others in their host communities. Many other Churches too have carried out empowerment programs, projects and supported spiritually, socially and financially other activities to empower individuals and communities.

However, the changes in social, religious, political and economic paradigm in the 21st century have grossly affected the life and operations of many Church leaders too. The overall effect of their ineptitude, greed, love for personal gains and aggrandisement, corruption and godless living has horrific impact on the Nigerian society. As it were for the Jews under the evil shepherds in Israel (Ezek. 34:1-10), many Nigerians have equally had terrible experiences with some clerics (both young and old) who by their callings are God's shepherd for Nigerians.

Participants in Edmund Akanya's research on "The Extent of Adoption of the Servant Leadership Model in the Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion: A Case Study of Three Diocese" carried out on his doctoral degree of Ministry Dissertation, in Asbury Theological Seminary noted that most of those in positions of leadership in the three chosen dioceses do not possess the requisite ability and skill to provide quality and exemplary leadership to their followers. It was the view of participants that materialism, unfaithfulness, and lack of accountability are at variance with servant leadership. Unfortunately, these traits characterize the visible activities of some of the leaders. The respondents claimed that some of these leaders are falling prey "to the get-rich-quick syndrome popular with the prosperity gospels, thereby adapting some sharp and unwholesome practices in dealing with church finances." These unwholesome practices of some Christian leaders are not different from what prevails within the larger society where our politicians are being daily accused of corruption, greed and avarice (88). These leaders and the led remain very shallow and ill-equipped to face spiritual challenges that are daily confronting them in the ministry rather exhibiting pomposity, ego and pride, lack of humility, fame-seeking, position conscious, selfishness, and competitiveness which are character traits inhibiting the practice of servant leadership model (Akanya 89). Oladimeji (2019) observes that the authority of most church leaders and pastors have become so intimidating to many in the pews. When these pastors are challenged, one of the things they say is that they are the spiritual head of the church quoting bible passages like, "Touch not my anointed, and do my prophets no harm." He notes that today the record shows that some Nigerian pastors have used their pastoral offices to influence people into immoral affairs and sexual perversion. He writes:

The misappropriation of Scriptures for the benefit of the person or the persons quoting them is one of the hallmarks of the recent Nigerian religious equation. The lack of contentment among pastors has impacted many of their parishioners to the extent that greed has been encouraged as a sign of looking forward to financial breakthroughs... Greed has become the basis for some of the

reasons for the leaders in the church to resort to control and manipulation of God's people in Nigeria. Preachers today in Nigeria have promoted greed in different dimensions and forms. The titles of church special programs indicate they are based on greed, revenge, and fear. The constant competition among church leaders about the type of cars they drive and those who use first class on every flight and those who are able to buy private jets. They also have members who have been made to think that the material blessings they have are the yardstick for measuring the favour of God and their spiritual lives. Many pastors have continued to fan this flame of vanity among their members (Oladimeji, 2019: 88)

In Nigeria, leadership positions and leadership responsibilities mostly do not correspond, a situation which justifies William Faulkner's claim that "that which is destroying the Church is not the outward groping of those within it or the inward groping of those without, but the professionals who control it and who have removed the bells from its steeples". In short, there are many leadership challenges facing the Church in Nigeria today which need prompt attention. On one hand are the many lapses at the top echelon which are daily brought to the notice of all and sundry via print and news media. This consists of increased and nagging emphasis on materialism which has impinged negatively on the value system of the society and ethical crises characterized by sexual scandals and abuses, relational indiscipline, financial irregularities, etc. On the other hand, is an increasingly disproportionate relationship between the claim of spirituality and actual demonstration of godliness among professing believers, a situation which pointedly reflects inadequacies in the spiritual nurture and guidance offered by the leadership. There is also the problem of spiritual abuse in which members are spiritually abused using "mind-control, thought reform, coercion, manipulation, deception, legalism, authoritarianism, guilt trips, judgementalism, a holier-than-thou attitude, and a "we are right and everyone else is wrong" attitude, through the promotion of extra-biblical rules and standards in a legalistic fashion and equate them as

doctrine or at least as absolutes of the Bible, coming directly from God, with salvation and/or spirituality in jeopardy if they are not followed.”

God’s Judgement of the Shepherds of Israel: Textual and Literary Analysis of Ezekiel 34: 1-10

According to Block (1998: 273), “Ezekiel 34 is a self-contained literary unit bounded by the word-event formula in v. 1 and a modified version of the recognition formula in vv. 30–31, followed by a thematic conclusion and sealed with the divine signatory formula.” In other words, the whole chapter under consideration may be perceived as a single literary unit. Indeed, the unit contains important formulae that serve a pivotal role in highlighting it as divine speech and focusing the audience on the speaker (Block, 1998: 273). For instance, *כֹּה אָמַר יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל* “Thus says (or declares) the Sovereign Lord,” which is an example of citation formula, appears five times (vv. 2, 10, 11, 17, 20); the signatory formula, *נְאֻם יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל*, “the declaration of the Lord Yahweh,” four times (vv. 8, 15, 30, 31); *שִׁמְעוּ אֶת-דְּבַר יְהוָה* “Hear the word of Yahweh,” is the summons to listen appears twice (in vv. 7, 9); the recognition formula, *וְיָדְעוּ כִּי אֲנִי יְהוָה*, “And they will know that I am Yahweh,” twice (vv. 27, 30); the divine self-introduction formula, *אֲנִי יְהוָה*, “I am Yahweh,” once (v. 24) (Block, 1998: 273). There are shifts in the formulaic characteristics in analysing the textual structure as in the tone and content of Ezekiel 34 (Block, 1998: 274). As such, it can be said that after the preamble (v. 1), the oracle proper divides into three parts approximately equal in length: (a) the announcement of deliverance (vv. 2–10); (b) the nature of the deliverance (vv. 11–22); (c) the goal of the deliverance (vv. 23–31). (Block, 1998: 274).

Block (1998) recognises the first part to be more of independent woe oracle directed against the rulers of Israel. This segment divides naturally into two parts, which in style and tone represent a formal accusation (vv. 2–6) and an announcement of judgment (vv. 7–10), respectively, elements typical of woe oracles. However, its location forces the reader to interpret this segment within its present literary framework. The second panel focuses entirely on Yahweh and his salvific

activity on behalf of his flock (Block, 1998: 274). Block (1998: 274) argues that the text of Ezekiel displays strong semantic and formal links with Jer. 23:1–6, stating that:

The linkages in theme and structure, style, and diction are too numerous and too specific to be accidental, and their distribution throughout Ezek. 34 may support the unitary interpretation of the latter. Ezekiel seems to have had Jeremiah's oracle before him and presented his "Shepherd Address" as an exposition of his contemporary's prophecy. But his adherence to Jeremiah is not slavish.

It can be concluded that the primary concern of Ezekiel 34 is not centred on the dispositions of wicked shepherds, but the relationship of the Good Shepherd and his flock. It serves a paradigmatic function, announcing the re-establishment of Yahweh's kingship over his people and highlighting his role in Israel's restoration (Block, 1998: 274).

Accusation and Reprobation of the Shepherd of Israel (Ezek. 34: 1-2)

A careful perusal of pre-exilic historiography of Israel reveals that the dispositions of shepherds of Israel determined the nation's destiny. In this regard, the exilic debacles were occasioned by bad leadership that continually disregarded the Torah and evoked YAHWEH's anger towards his people. In the prophetic literature, the oracles of Ezekiel focused, among many other things, on the defects of pre-exilic leaders ("shepherds") of Israel, which ultimately led to the humiliating exile for the people. Exegetical studies of the Prophetic literature reveals Ezekiel's attitude toward the leadership of Israel. It shows a nexus between the attitudes of the various leadership groups and the welfare of the Jewish nation - those singled out for reproach in Ezekiel's critique of the past are marginalised in YAHWEH's plan for the future, while those who escaped blames are assigned higher positions of honour and responsibilities" (Duguid 1-2). Such was the harsh proclamation of judgement and a clear indication of YAHWEH's reprobation of the shepherds: "I will require their deeds upon their heads" (Ezek. 9:10).

In Ezekiel 34: 1-10, we find a heavily rhetorical language unveiling the reprobation of YAHWEH towards the shepherds of Israel. The shepherd-kings of the Davidic dynasty were indicted for being irresponsible shepherds, who by their ineptitude caused Israel to go to exile in Babylon (vv.3-6; Jer. 23:1; 50: 6). YAHWEH's response to the crisis of the flock in exile is twofold. YAHWEH's major attention is given to the rescue of the flock, which royal neglect has jeopardised. YHWH will act as a proper and responsible shepherd to recover the flock" (Brueggemann, 1997: 260). Secondly, YAHWEH's disposition in the prophetic oracles of Ezekiel underscores the all-important place of shepherd-leaders and the need for genuine and humane empathy in leadership (Ezek. 34: 7-10 cf. 11-15). The relevance of this is that it aptly fits the current socio-religious climate of the Church in Nigeria.

דְּבַר יְהוָה, דְּבַר יְהוָה, דְּבַר יְהוָה - The construct phrase דְּבַר יְהוָה - the word of the Lord - in this verse is of particular theological significance to the message passed in Ezekiel 34: 1-10. In Old Testament understanding, דְּבַר יְהוָה refers to a message from or about God. The use of דְּבַר יְהוָה offers clear evidence of an established theological conviction that "Israel's God is a God who speaks". The phrase דְּבַר יְהוָה authenticates the prophetic speeches that follow. This formula דְּבַר יְהוָה אֵלַי לְאמֹר punctuates the fact that God was ready, as part of his restoration package, to tackle the trouble which arises from the lack of good leadership in Israel (Jack 119).

The Selfishness and Negligence of the Shepherds of Israel (Ezek. 34:3-4)

אָתְּהַחֲלֵב תֹאכְלֻהוּ וְאָתְּהַחֲמַר תִּלְכְּשׁוּ הַבְּרִיאָה תִזְבְּחוּ הַצֹּאן לֹא תִרְעֹוּ
אָתְּהַחֲלֵב is the first verb in this verse 3. תֹאכְלֻהוּ is the imperfect second person masculine plural of the verb אָכַל meaning "eat, consume or devour" which appears in both non-ritual and ritual contexts, where either humans, beasts, or inanimate objects are its subject. In verse 3, Ezekiel charges the rulers with three crimes of commission. First, they consume the fat of the flock. Conventionally, eating the fat of the sheep is not an exploitative act, but here it is made to look like a robbery. Second, the shepherds fleece the flock. This is natural in a pastoral economy, but

Ezekiel's figure assumes the forceful removal of wool, making it look like the sheep are left naked before the elements. Third, they butcher the fatlings (*habbērî'â*). The verb *zābah* often denotes the slaughter of a sacrificial animal, especially for the *zēbah*, "sacrificial" meal. But here the verb functions simply as a synonym for *tābah*, without any religious overtones. Shepherds do raise sheep for their mutton, but in this metaphorical context, such slaughter represents the most blatant violation of the Shepherd's role, presumably judicial murder (cf. 7:23; 9:9; etc.). The triad of accusations concludes with a reiteration of the general charge in v. 2. The rulers have taken excellent care of themselves, but they have not cared for the flock (Block, 1998: 278).

According to Walther, Verse 4 states the crimes of omission of the shepherds of Israel which reflect a stratum of Israelite leaders representing the antithesis of responsible shepherds. First, they have shown no concern for the physical health of the flock. They have not strengthened (*hizzēq*) the weak (*nahēlôt*), healed (*rippē'*) the sick (*hōlâ*), or bound up (*hābaš*) the injured (*nišberet*). Second, they have shown no concern for the sheep that have left the flock. They have neither gone after the strays nor sought the lost. Instead of caring (*rā'â*) for the flock, the shepherds have ruled over them with harshness (*hāzēqâ*) and brutality (*perek*) (Block, 1998: 279). The office of a shepherd is represented in this verse as a very onerous and responsible vocation, requiring tireless vigilance and readiness for sacrifice. Yet the shepherds of Israel have not only failed to show self-sacrifice in protecting and providing for those in need of their care, but have violently trodden down the stronger sheep, which would otherwise be the pride of the flock, i.e. they have atrociously overworked them and taken advantage of them for their own profit (Walther 390).

The Consequent Collapse of the State of Israel Resulting from Evil Leadership (Ezek. 34:5-6)

Block (1998) avers that, verses 5 and 6 describe the disastrous effects of the irresponsible conduct of the leaders. He opines that, "to have leaders like this is worse than being shepherdless." Scattered, the sheep roam

about the mountains and high hills, defenceless prey for all the wild animals (תִּיתָ הַשְּׂדֵה). The parallelism of the final two lines summarises the bitter fate of the nation: there is no one to seek the scattered sheep. The insertion of my flock (צֹאֲנִי) – an expression of ownership and endearment in verse 6 shows Yahweh’s and the prophet’s primary concern. The abused sheep are Yahweh’s flock, not the leaders’. Theirs was a delegated authority argues Block (1998), and they would answer to him for the manner in which they have exercised leadership. This clearly indicates that finally, after what seems to have been an endless series of judgmental pronouncements against his nation, a change in the divine disposition is evident. Jerusalem has fallen and her population is dispersed, but Yahweh, the divine Shepherd, has not forgotten his people (Block, 1998: 282).

The Pains Associated with the Collapse of the State of Israel Due to Evil Leadership (Ezekiel 34:5-6)

The verb נִתְפָּצְצָה is an imperfect 3rd person feminine plural derived from פָּצַח the root word for “to dash in pieces, to disperse, cast (abroad), scatter (abroad), and spread abroad.” The flock was dispersed and scattered abroad. The inseparable preposition adverb of negation מִבְּלִי a formation of מִן meaning “because of, by (reason of), and בְּלִי meaning “failure, nothing, without, because not, as long as, for lack of,” marks the object which is the verb **qal** participle masculine singular רֹעֶה from the root רָעָה “to tend or graze a flock, to rule, to associate with (as a friend), keep company with. The definite article noun masculine הַשְּׂדֵה means “the country, field, ground, land, wild” (Hinson, 1990: 102). A working translation of the verse is given thus: ‘and they were scattered abroad for lack of shepherds they became food to all wild beast, and they were scattered’. Verse 6 concludes the flow of thought which is rendered: ‘my flock wander on all the mountains and on high hills on the face of the earth my flock scatter and none seek for them and none search for them.’

The Punishment of God for the False Shepherds of Israel (Ezekiel 34:7-10)

The formula *לָכֵן רָעִים שָׁמְעוּ אֶת־דְּבַר יְהוָה* used in this text is a declaration of divine judgement on the leaders of the house of Israel. It starts with the adverb *לָכֵן* meaning “therefore” which in the prophetic books frequently introduces a divine declaration or command. The particle *לָכֵן* usually forms the transition in prophetic judgment speeches from the discussion to the declaration. ‘Therefore shepherds hear the word of Yahweh’, verse 8 opens with the oath formula *חַי־אֲנִי נְאֻם אֲדֹנָי יְהוָה*. The construct word *חַי־אֲנִי* derived from *חַי* is an adjective meaning “alive or living” and first person singular personal pronoun *אֲנִי* meaning “I, my, myself” used to express a true present or liveliness. “I am alive” declares the Sovereign Lord, surely because my flock became a prey and became food for every beast of the field because no shepherd cared for my flock, the shepherds fed themselves and my flock they did not feed’ (Kohn 2003). Verse 8 reiterates the crisis of the people and presents Yahweh’s complaint about the desperate condition of his flock; they have become prey (*בָּזֵי*) and food (*’oklâ*) for all the wild animals. Responsibilities for the flock placed on the shoulders of the shepherds have been neglected. Having been appointed by Yahweh to care for his flock, they have exploited the office for personal gain (Jeremiah 88).

Verse 9 - *לָכֵן הָרָעִים שָׁמְעוּ דְבַר־יְהוָה*: - This is a repetition of verse 7 which is translated ‘Therefore, the shepherds hear word of Yahweh.’ The two verses are a twofold appeal to hear the divine declaration (vv. 7, 9) which leads the reader to expect an announcement of judgment upon the irresponsible rulers (Jack 122).

Verse 10 begins with another prophetic formula - *כֹּה־עַמֹּר אֲדֹנָי יְהוָה* - *כֹּה* is an adverb meaning “thus, now, here”, acting as a marker of a transition in a discourse or sentence, as a prompter of attention focusing on content that will follow. The emphatic particle *הִנְנִי* translated “behold” is an interjection and draws special attention to what the Lord, who is the subject, is about to declare (Hengstenberg, 1923: 216). It specifies that Yahweh will require his sheep from the hand of the wicked leaders. In this case Yahweh will hold the criminal shepherds accountable for the fate of the flock. He will sack them from feeding the sheep as declared in *וְהִשְׁבַּתִּים מִרְעוֹת צֹאן* - by sacking them they will no longer feed themselves

off the flock as indicated in the expression *וְלֹא-יִרְעוּ עִוֹד* particularly *וְלֹא-יִרְעוּ* marked by the negative particle *לֹא*. God will also deliver his flock as announced thus: *וְהִצַּלְתִּי צֹאֲנֵי מִפִּיהֶם וְלֹא-תִהְיֶינָה לָהֶם לְאֶכְלָה* – they will “be rescued or saved” (Hinson, 1990: 312)

A working translation of verse 10 will then read thus: “Thus says the Sovereign Lord behold I am against the shepherds and I will require my flock from their hand and I will stop them from tendering the flock and not feed again the shepherds themselves for I will rescue my flock from their mouths and no longer will they be food to them’. Since the shepherds, who had been appointed by Yahweh to care for his sheep, have not only neglected their duty but turned into ravenous wolves themselves, Yahweh is compelled to intervene and rescue (*hiṣṣîl*) his sheep from their jaws. For the rulers this is an announcement of judgment, but for the flock it is a message of hope (Block, 1998: 289).

Christian Bodies and the Churches in Nigeria in the Context of Ezekiel 34:1-10

Christianity in Nigeria no doubt has suffered many irreparable damages due to the activities of her leaders mostly in the 21st century. Chris Irekamba and Nkechi Onyedika-Ugoeze (2019, July, 7) ask:

Both social and traditional media are agog with disturbing stories of men of God engaging in illicit sexual affairs and occult practices. And there seems to be no end to it, as the menace keeps rearing its ugly head in different forms. This is aside other alarming activities as ritual killings, hypnotizing their members, false miracles, intimidating their members with false prophecies, robbery and 419, among other unprintable things discovered to be going on in some churches (2023, March 23: 97).

Why are these happening in the House of God? What are the bodies constituted to enhance collaboration, regulations and supervision of churches doing to curb these excesses? Is there anything the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN), the Catholic Secretariat of Nigeria (CSN), Organization of African Indigenous Churches (OIC), Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN), Christian Council of Nigeria (CCN), and the

Evangelical Church Wining All/ Fellowship of Churches of Christ in Nigeria can do to save the Church from these scandals?

These views show that there is a lacuna to be filled between leadership positions and leadership roles in Nigeria. Oladimeji (2019: 163) submits that “in order to bring about the necessary change from corruption to fidelity there is a major work to be done in leadership.”

As the assembly of God’s people, the Church recognises the need for effective and godly leadership; hence individuals are selected or elected to offer guidance and guardianship to the believers. This comes in form of ordained and lay ministries of the Church. Interestingly, leaders are increasingly affirming authority over the Church, even when they do not always agree about its appearance or how it should be exercised. Similarly, Christian communities, especially local Churches, are constantly faced with opportunities and challenges resulting from societal shifts and changes. In contemporary times, the dominant default method for responding to these changes has been to defer to and rely upon the expertise and professional leadership of the Church. This happens because modern Churches have generally accepted this position under the influence of cultural perspective on leadership, which views the pastor as the expert or professional leader of the Church. However, more recently, questions about this cultural position on Church leaders have come from different perspectives (Kinnison, 2010: 2). Cornel West opines that “the major challenge is the need to generate new leadership...we need leaders...who can situate themselves within a larger historical narrative of this country and world, who can grasp the complex dynamics of our peoplehood and imagine a future grounded in the best of our past yet attuned to the frightening obstacles that now perplex us” (21-25).

In “Feeding and Leading of Shepherds”, Crissman (2005) demonstrates a good grasp of background information of the context as helpful in pastoral hermeneutics. Taking his example from Ezekiel 34:1-31, he sees Ezekiel 34 as a complete exegetical unit with two main divisions, vv 1 -16 and vv 17 – 31. His illustration concentrates on the historical and political context of the last days of the Judean monarchy

when it was besieged and deported to Babylon over their covenant infidelity. He sees the text situated “within an indicative section of leadership irresponsibility, where the prophet employs the shepherd metaphor and sheep to address the audience. He further said that these shepherds (kings and rulers) failed in their responsibilities in leading, guiding, and protecting Israel. Instead, they devoted much energy to exploiting the sheep; they were selfish, harsh, and brutal. These kings were supposed to lead all of Israel with a “sense of compassion, love, care, responsibility and accountability” (23-25).

To Iain, the condemnation of the shepherds is for self-interest, oppression of the people and a lack of concern for the commonwealth of Israel (Duguid 266). Constable (2004) observes that God pronounced judgment on them for three reasons. First, they fed themselves rather than the people; they were selfish. They were more interested in providing for themselves than for the people whom God had placed in their care (cf. John 10:11-13; 21:15-17). They exploited their followers (267).

Specifically, these unfaithful shepherds ate the best parts of the sacrifices rather than offering them to God (cf. 1 Sam. 2:12-17). They used sheep’s wool to make clothing for themselves rather than providing these animals as sacrifices to God (Constable, 2004: 267). Second, they slaughtered them rather than feeding God’s sheep; they were oppressive. They had not restored those that needed restoring nor sought those that had wandered away and needed finding. They had dominated God’s flock rather than providing loving, self-sacrificial leadership. The primary responsibility of a leader is to care for the needs of those he leads, even if this requires sacrificing his desires (Constable, 2004: 267). Third, the rulers allowed the people to scatter over the earth instead of keeping them safely together; they were negligent. The Israelites scattered because they lacked leadership and became prey for the enemies of God’s flock. They wandered everywhere, but there was no one to seek them out (cf. Matt. 9:36; John 10:12-13) (Constable, 2004: 268).

Commenting on the role performed by a shepherd, Vancil (1992) observes, “The principal task of the shepherd is to see that the animal found enough food and water (cf. Psalm 23), and he was important that he guards the sheep since they were easy prey for wild animals (1 Samuel 17:34-35; Amos 3:12). (1187). Cachia (1997:27) agrees with Vancil (1992) when he states, “The shepherd was expected to look after the flock under his responsibility and provide for it. He was to render service and protection to his flock, which includes the concern for providing food and water, refuge and security - all these entailed leadership roles of the shepherd.” Leadership, therefore, encapsulates the essential functional role of the shepherd. However, Cachia (1997: 27) notes further that the shepherd not only caters for the flock; he also depends on the flock for living, deriving nourishment and sustenance for himself and his family. Hence, there exists an interdependence relationship between the shepherd and the sheep. This relationship, therefore, “created a vital and existential interdependence between the shepherd and the sheep, and interdependence which develop into a relationship of love and dedication of the shepherd and the sheep” (Cachia, 1997: 28). Thus, it is pertinent to note that this loving relationship demanded the shepherd to constantly lead the sheep to wherever he could find the excellent pasture daily and make sure they were safe back to the sheepfold. The sheep’s safety is paramount; and calls for uncompromising commitment, vigilance, and inordinate passion on the part of the shepherd to endanger his life for the sheep’s sake, be it during the night or daytime. This understanding of the daily routine of taking good care of his sheep was later taken over in the social and religious life of the people of Israel. In the final submission, Cachia (1997) notes that Old Testament presents God as the only absolute, genuine, and supreme shepherd of his people, Israel. The key Hebrew word used in all of the passages where God is depicted as a shepherd is (*ro’eh*). See Ps. 28:9; Isa. 40:10; Jer. 31:9b-10; Ezek.34:13-16; Hos. 4:16; Mic.7:14, and Zech.11:7, 9. The verb (*ra’ah*) takes God as its subject where God is succinctly compared as a shepherd (Cachia, 1997: 42). Laniak (2012: 11) points out that God’s relationship with Israel - a relationship analogous to the relationship between a

shepherd and his sheep - is a covenant relationship. God as the shepherd of Israel thus implies that God is the “ultimate provider, protector, and guide of his sheep.

Hence, the description of God as the shepherd of his people - Israel, in the Old Testament, is a divine obligation on God’s part to always serve as Israel’s guidance, provider, and leader who knows the needs of his people and adequately made provisions. The description also connotes the covenantal relationship fostered by Israel’s continual allegiance to God at all times. On this note, Cachia (1997: 45) submits that God performs six distinct, interrelated foundational roles in God Israel’s shepherding metaphor, and these are: leading, feeding, guarding-presence, gathering-searching, delivering-judging, tenderness-healing, and knowing-alliance.

The Roles of Christian Organisations in Promoting Godly Christian Leadership in Nigeria

The task of developing selfless Christian leadership in any context is a herculean task. However, it is not a gainsaying to assert that the Christian organisations have so much to do in this regard. First, Christian organisations have the job of promoting and exhibiting spiritual values and norms that are templates for church leaders. There have been attempts to seek, emulate, and imbibe the social, personal and domestic qualities of selfless leaders into the teeming youth populations within the organisations. This is chiefly done through seminars, conferences, and important religious meetings over the years.

Also, Christian organisations have taken it upon themselves to offer spiritual guidance and support to their leaders through prayers, spiritual retreats and intercessions. It is agreed that “the place of prayers cannot be underestimated as guidance comes from God. Faith and trust in God encourage leaders and push their resolves to be selfless and visionary in their endeavours” (Mala and Akanbi, 2012: 430).

On several occasions, those superintending in different Christian denominations have used various passages of the Bible to admonish local leaders and administrators under them on the need to be selfless

and ensure the spiritual and physical prosperity of their followers. In fact, we have cases of Christian organisations partnering with different governmental and non-governmental agencies to float conferences targeted at raising the next generation of leaders who are selfless and visionary both for the Church and the state in Lagos.

Conclusion

In the light of the prevailing situation in Nigeria in the 21st century, Church leaders with shepherd heart are greatly needed to shepherd Christ's flock, "to exhort in sound doctrine and to refute those who contradict the divine principles of godly leadership" (Titus 1:9), for "many rebellious men, empty talkers, and deceivers ... who must be silenced" (Titus 1:10-11) had crept into the Church, "savage wolves ... not sparing the flock" (Acts 20:29 cf. Jude 4-13; 2Pet 2:1). It can be argued that we are "in the last days" (2 Tim. 3:1), and men are now "lovers of self, lovers of money ... lovers of pleasure rather than lovers of God" (2 Tim 3:2-4). Against this background, this paper conducted a rhetorical analysis of the shepherd motif in Ezekiel 34:1-10 in relation to church leadership in Nigeria. Christian leaders must be more outspoken against wrong leadership, corruption, and abuse of powers among secular and spiritual leaders. In recent times, Leaders of the orthodox, mainline and New Generational Churches have openly and jointly condemned the selfishness of the contemporary leaders just as Yahweh did in Ezekiel 34. In fact, it may be said that this attitude of raising a prophetic cry against social injustice and inequality is entrenched among leaders of Christian organisations on Lagos Island. Various Christian organisations have also attempted to lend their voices against wrong leadership, corruption, and abuse of power both in the ecclesia and the state. This is often done in the spirit of love with the intent of developing the much-needed selfless character in the existing and emerging leaders in the nation and the church. In spite of this, it is believed that Christian organisations have to do more even as Nigeria approaches another election year, 2023.

There is need for the Church to promote moral recovery and transformative values among her rank and file. The intention of God

within the scope of the Scriptures is for the Church to be the salt and light of the world. Salt in terms of fighting against corruption and various abuses; light in terms of being a guide and template to the outside world. Therefore, it is crucial that the Church through her various spiritual programmes focuses on moral recovery through intentional values which is Biblical based (Okunoye, n.d.: 411). Okunoye (n.d.) further argues that the church must raise godly shepherd leaders by organising consistent and in-depth bible studies for would-be leaders and current leaders on subjects of justice, fair play, righteousness and moral disciple, hard work and extravagance, decision-making by consensus, accountability and openness, communal spirit, honesty and sincerity, love through sacrificial living and giving- all the portrait selfless leadership (411).

Recommendations

1. The different Christian denominations should encourage their Provinces, Conferences, Dioceses, local churches or parishes to organise seminars and workshops for their ministers and church leaders on leadership from the biblical perspective. Resource persons should be engaged, and they should be those who have a vast knowledge of leadership development and administrative skills. The workshops or seminars should focus on the challenges Christians face in leadership, whether secular or spiritual in the 21st century. The church must therefore do her path in providing an educational platform for the socio-religious transformation of leaders and would-be leaders in Nigeria.
2. The various Christian blocks (CAN, CSN, OIC, CCN PFN, ECWA/FCCN) should be more proactive in mediating and regulating the affairs of the different denominations in affiliation with them.
3. Adequate spiritual, pastoral formation and theological education should be given to those accepted into the ordained ministry.
4. The various Christian denominations in Nigeria should continually intercede for their leaders and also ensure that all

members of their pastoral force give considerable attention to their spiritual and secular developments. They should further ensure that the clerics attend periodic training workshops, seminars, retreat and the annual clergy school.

5. Church organizations, denominations or ministries should establish training centres and seminaries where church leaders are exposed to the essence of their duties as shepherds of God's flock.

References

- Adekoya, Richard A. Ayodele. *"The Diocese of Lagos West of the Anglican Communion, Church of Nigeria as Agent of Social and Political Change in the Society."* Doctoral Thesis Prifysgol Bangor University, Wales. www.core.ac.uk/download/pdf/228911893.pdf
- Akanya, Edmund, "The Extent of Adoption of the Servant Leadership Model in the Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion: A Case Study of Three Diocese. Doctor of Ministry Dissertation. Asbury Theological Seminary.
- Asaju, D. F. (1995). "Christianity in Africa: A Case Study" in A.O.K. Noah (ed). *Fundamentals of General Studies* (pp. 347-55). Lagos: Rex Charles Publication.
- Atowoju, Ayodele A. (2007) "Jesus' Denunciation of Corruption in Luke 22: 24-25 with particular reference to the Governance and Economy of Nigeria", in S.O. Abogunrin et.al., (eds.), *Biblical Studies and Corruption in Africa, Biblical Studies Series*, Number 6, NABIS, pp. 392-411.
- Block, Daniel I. (1997). "The Book of Ezekiel Chapters 1–24." in *New International Commentary on the Old Testament*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans.
- Block, Daniel I. (1998). "The Book of Ezekiel Chapters 25–48" in *New International Commentary on the Old Testament*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans.
- Brueggemann, Walter (1997). *Theology of the Old Testament*, Minneapolis: Fortress.

- Cachia, N. (1997). *The Image of the Good Shepherd as a Source for the Spirituality of the Ministerial Priesthood*, Paizza della Pilotta: Gregorian University.
- Clines, David J. A. (2014). Contemporary Methods in Hebrew Bible Criticism. In *Hebrew Bible/Old Testament: The History of its Interpretation*, Vol. III. <https://doi.org/10.13109/9783666540226.148>
- Constable, T. L. (2004). *Notes on Ezekiel, 2004 Edition*, www.sonlight.com.
- Crissman, B. M. (2005) *Feeding and Leading of Shepherds*, Newcastle, Plowpoint Press.
- Dairo, Afolunsho O. (2014). “Church Leadership in Nigeria in the light of Leadership Qualifications in Timothy 3:1-7”. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol. 4, No 6.
- Danfulani, D. D. and Atowoju, A. A. (2012). *Youth Restiveness in Nigeria: A Theological Reflection*, Lagos: B. Print Publishing.
- Duguid, I. M. (1999) “Ezekiel”. *The NIV Application Commentary*. eBook by Zondervan
- Duguid, I. M. (1960) “Ezekiel Commentaries” in Terry Muck (Gen. Ed), *The NIV Application Commentary - Old Testament*, Zondervan
- Duguid, I. M. (1994). “Ezekiel and the Leaders of Israel”. in *Vetus Testamentum Supplement Series 56*. Leiden: Brill.
- Duguid, I. M. (1994). *Ezekiel and the Leaders of Israel*, Vol. 56, Oxford: BRILL.
- Gan, J. (2007) *The Metaphor of Shepherd in the Hebrew Bible: A Historical-Literary Reading*, New York: University Press of America.
- Hengstenberg, E. W. (1923) *The Prophecies of the Prophet Ezekiel Elucidated*, London, Tandt Clark.
- Hinson, D. F. (1990) *History of Israel: Old Testament Introduction 1*, Revised Edition, The University Press: Cambridge.
- Igbari, Olusola (2021). “Jesus’ Model of Leadership and the Integrity of Church Leaders’ in Nigeria.” *Nigeria Journal and Christian Studies* – Vol. 4, No 1.
- Irekamba, Chris and Onyedika-Ugoeze, Nkechi, (2019, July, 7). “Scandal in House of God: What Church Leadership must Do”, *The Guardian Newspaper*
- Jeremias, Joachim (1985). “Poimen” in Geoffrey W, Bromiley, (ed.). *Theological Dictionary of the New Testament Abridged in One Volume*, Grand Rapids: Eerdmans.

- Junaid-Eko, N. O. (2003). "The Growth of Islam and Civil Crisis in Old Lagos". R. Ajetumobi (ed) *The Evolution and Development of Lagos State*. Lagos: Centre for Lagos Studies.
- Kinnison, Quentin P. (2010). "Shepherd or One of the Sheep: Revisiting the Biblical Metaphor of the Pastorate". *Journal of Religious Leadership*, Vol. 9, No 1 Spring 2010
- Kohn, R. L. (2003). Ezekiel at the Turn of the Century <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476993x0300200102>,
- Kohn, R. L. (2009). *A New Heart and New Soul: Ezekiel, the Exile and the Torah. (The Library of Hebrew Bible/Old Testament Studies*. London: Sheffield Academic Press.
- Laniak, Timothy S. (2012). *Finding the Lost Images of God: Uncover the Ancient Culture, Discover Hidden Meanings*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan.
- Leupold, H. C. (1971). *Exposition of Zechariah*. Grand Rapids: Baker Book House.
- Mala, Simon B. and Akanbi, Jude O. (2012). "The Roles of Religious Leaders/Clerics in the Actualisation of Good Governance in Multi-Faith Nigeria in Ayantayo, J. K. et.al. (eds) *Religion and Governance in Nigeria*, Religious Studies Series, Vol. 4.
- Muilenburg, Andrew (2007) "Profitable and Unprofitable Shepherds: Economic and Theological Perspectives in Ezekiel 34, in *JSOT*, 31.4 496,500
- Oderinde, Olatundun Abosede (2014). "Ethical Misconduct among Nigerian Church Leaders in the context of 1 Timothy 3:1-7" in *Research of Humanities and Social Sciences* Vol.4, No 17.
- Okunoye, Job (n.d). "The Role of Church Leaders in Building Sustainable Nigeria Future", in *Journal of Religion and Culture*, Vol. 17 Issue 1 Department of Religious and Cultural Studies University of Port Harcourt.
- Oladimeji, Babatunde (2019). *Progressing from Corruption to Fidelity: An Exploration of Church-Initiated Agency in Nigerian Society*. Doctor of Philosophy Dissertation. Asbury Theological Seminary 2019.
- Onyedika-Ugoeze Nkechi (2023, March 23). "The Redeem Christian Church for instance Offers free Medical Services. *The Guardian Nigeria*.

- Oshun, C. O. (2017) "Leadership and Christocentric Principles in the Fight Against Corruption in Nigeria" – Nigeria Journal of Christian Studies 1, No. 1 (5)
- Osoba, A. J. and Nojimu-Yusuf, A. R. (2003). "The Growth and Development of Christianity in Lagos State" in R. Ajetunmobi (ed) The Evolution and Development of Lagos State, Centre for Lagos State Studies
- Rodgers, B. (2010). *A Christological Reading of the Shepherd Motif for Pastoral Theology with Special Reference to Ezekiel 34*, <http://www.biblicalthology.com/Research/RodgersBo1.pdf>
- Taylor, Harold (1983). "Tend my Sheep" in Applied Theology TEF Study Guide Vol. 2, SPCK.
- Vancil, Jack W. (1992). "Sheep, Shepherd" *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*. Freeman, New York: Double day.

Diversity and Cultural Consciousness: A Case Study of Challenges of Interculturality in Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Samonda, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Intercultural competence and diversity management strategy are necessary for effective leadership in any human organization that is characterized with cultural diversity. In a multicultural organization like church, leaders, particularly pastors, bear the responsibility to manage diversity of human experiences, promote intercultural understanding among the congregations, and mobilise them toward achieving common goals. This responsibility, however, requires a certain degree of cultural consciousness. This paper focuses on the challenges of managing Interculturality in the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) Samonda, Ibadan. It is concern with the cultural consciousness and challenges among the diversity of the congregants. The paper is based on focused group interviews conducted among pastors in the parish, primarily to measure their level of cultural consciousness and awareness of cultural diversity among their parishioners. The findings of the paper – multiculturalism due to globalization, diverse cultural background, adherents to culture and beliefs, trying to unify through gifts-sharing accounts for the challenges of interculturality in a culturally diverse organization, particularly, the challenges that pastors encounter with multicultural worshippers. The paper therefore concludes that the lack of cultural consciousness and

willingness to adopt culturally–appropriate methods may result into cultural dissonances and disunity among the congregation and, ultimately, hamper the mission goals of the church. The study recommends that the promotion of interculturality among the congregations, pastor’s education on intercultural strategy requires an unwavering attention.

Keywords: Multiculturalism, Diversity, Cultural Consciousness, Interculturality, Gift Sharing, Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG)

Introduction

The Church and Intercultural Challenges: A Historical Perspective

Since its expansion from its cradle in the Palestine region into Europe, Asia and the rest of the world, the Church had always faced challenges of cultural diversity (Ian). The first Church in Jerusalem was comprised of myriad cultures and languages, comprising Parthia, Medes (present day Iran), Elam, Mesopotamia, Judea, Cappadocia, Pontus, Asia, Phrygia, Pamphylia, Egypt, Libya, Cyrene, Rome, Jerusalem, Cretes and Arabia as recorded in Acts of the Apostles chapter 2. Even the Jewish community that made up the Church comprised of Aramaic-speaking Jews (those brought up in Palestine) and Greek-speaking Jews (known as Hellenists), that is, Jews that were raised outside Palestine. Throughout Palestine, there was tension between the two groups and the tension was carried over into the Church. As a result, the nascent Church encountered cultural dissonance, particularly in the treatment of widows. The Hellenists complained that their widows were neglected and discriminated against during palliative distributions as recorded in Acts of the Apostles chapter 6.

The dissension continued after the dispersal of the Apostles, following oppositions from Jewish leaders in Jerusalem. Culturally-based dissonance within the Church grew in intensity, particularly as non-Jewish Christians (Gentiles), whom Jews considered unclean, were brought into the Church fold (Acts of Apostles 10). For example, old Jewish law made a distinction between ‘clean’ and ‘unclean’ food. The details of Moses’ instruction to the Israelites on food is recorded in

Leviticus chapter 11 verses 1-23. Jewish Christians observed this strict law of eating only those food or animals that were considered clean. But the Gentile Christians were more liberal and they ate every food without discrimination. As a result of cultural prejudices among the congregations, the Church became polarized along Jew –Gentile lines, on the basis of types of food to be eaten or avoided among the congregation (Froehlich, 1985). Nevertheless, the ‘crisis ‘was resolved through the interventions of the Apostles, Deacons and Elders, the leaders of the Church (especially Peter, James and, later, Paul). These details are contained in the Acts of the Apostles chapters 11, 13 and 15 (Berry, 2022, March 21).

The fact that difference of opinions - based on cultural diversity among the congregation – on a trivial issue as food could negatively alter unity and acceptability within the Church, is an indication that interculturality is a serious phenomenon that requires attention. Indeed, the phenomenon of diversity and how to accomplish interculturality has been a subject of concern within the universal Church, particularly with the way it has impinged on its missional goals. For example, cultural diversity resulted into painstaking translation of the New Testament from Latin to Greek, as well as from Greek to numerous languages of the world (Ehrman, 1993). Attempts to seek the preservation of cultural diversity was also the main goal behind the translation of the Bible into several languages of the world. In Nigeria, the Bible Society of Nigeria has translated the Bible into more than 50 local languages, and is prepared to continue with the translation to local languages. This measure has to closed the linguistic gap and, indeed, cultural chasm among Christians within the country. The adoption of certain common creeds of faith within some denominations, which must be confessed aloud, as an oath of commitment to a common belief and practice, has further engendered the universality of Christian creed and doctrines, such as the Trinity.

The Christendom adopt diverse pragmatic approaches to manage cultural encounters within their congregations in different part of the

world. For example, the Sacred congregation for the Propagation of Faith under the Roman Catholic Mission sent out series of instruction in 1659. The intention was to stimulate the congregation to pursue appropriate cultural means to proselytize and keep its focus: 'Do not regard it as your task, and do not bring any pressure to bear on the peoples, to change their manners, customs and uses, unless they are evidently contrary to religion and sound morals' (Peter & Bradley, 1990: 64).

The instruction above imposed huge responsibilities on leadership of the Church at every level to cultivate positive cultural consciousness in daily encounters with their multicultural congregations. The focus of the Papal writ was to ensure respect for all cultures, especially among communities in which missionary enterprises take place. The emphasis was on the unity and universality of the Catholic Church. By the time the decisions of the Second Vatican Council, namely, Vatican II, was adopted three centuries later, specifically, 1962-1965, the overwhelming objective was to ensure inculturation in the mission, with emphasis on ensuring that rituals, worship and theology grow out of the living cultures of the people. It was not surprising that Bishop Firmin Schmidt, a German American, and formerly Catholic Bishop of the Southern Highlands in Papua New Guinea, said: 'God is the authors of culture, we have to respect' (Peter & Bradley, 1990: 64-67)). At the heart of this is the search for points of cultural contact, or the possibility for a synthesis of cultures, that is, interculturality.

The need to manage cultural diversity and promote intercultural relations is not peculiar to the orthodox churches. Among the Pentecostal denominations in Nigeria, the same challenge has prompted them to seek culturally appropriate means to achieve positive interculturality among their congregations. An example is the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), one of the fastest growing Pentecostal denominations in Nigeria, with a global reach and parishes/congregations in over 190 countries of the world (Asonzeh, 2008). The lack of cultural consciousness in pastoral leadership may

year 2000, during the Ministers (Leadership) Conference, the General Overseer (G.O) of the Church, Pastor Enoch Adeboye, took a strict stance against all forms of cultural prejudices within the denomination. The G.O (as he is fondly called by his members) issued a stern warning against cultural separatism, and called those who fanned the embers of cultural – dissonances to order. This tendency also stimulated leadership of the Church to seek culturally – appropriate means to promote interculturality among the congregations, from the Parish level, the Area level (made up of 5 parishes), to the Zonal level, comprising of, at least, two Areas. For example, among other strategies, the General Overseer composed a special congregational anthem for the Mission in 2020, in which emphasis is placed on virtues such as unity, love, and shared destiny. All members of the Mission, regardless of cultural disparities, are described as ‘covenant children united in love’ in the song. This special song must be rendered in unison by all members of a congregation whenever a meeting/service is rounded off. This song is rendered standing up, while all congregations join hands across the aisles as a symbol of unity. The adoption of an anthem to be sang in harmony among a congregation is not peculiar to RCCG. Many Pentecostal denominations have, in the past, adopted similar congregational anthems to foster a sense of togetherness (Archer, 2011).

Culturally-learned differences reinforce prejudices and dissonances among people with dissimilar cultures (Kruger, 2019). This is particularly more prevalent within social contexts, such as the workplace and religious settings that bring people from diverse cultural orientations together to achieve common goals. The importance of intercultural strategy in religious context, especially the Church, cannot be over-emphasised as the Church been a melting point of cultures since its inception around 33AD, despite having a unified biblical canon. However, the Church has never been immune from the challenges that cultural diversity poses (Harvey, 2020).

In this paper, the authors appraise the challenges of interculturality in Shekinah Zone (that is a group of more than ten parishes) of the

The theory explores behavioural approach to examining the gap between knowing and doing, that is, between what people knows to be inter-culturally competent and what they do in intercultural situations. In order to bridge the gap between what people know and do, the theory postulates several dimensions that are essential to determine and measure individual intercultural communicative competence. These are highlighted below:

The first is the Display of Respect describes an individual's ability to "express respect and positive regard" for other individuals. Another dimension is Interaction Posture, which refers to an individual's ability to "respond to others in a descriptive, non-evaluative, and nonjudgmental way. Ruben's Behavioural Theory also hints on Orientation to Knowledge. This describes an individual's ability to "recognize the extent to which knowledge is individual in nature. In other words, orientation to knowledge describes an individual's ability to recognize and acknowledge that people explain the world around them in different ways with differing views of what is right and true. The Behavioural Theory also mentions Empathy, which is an individual's ability to see oneself as others. The fifth is Self-oriented Role Behavior. This expresses an individual's flexible ability to function in initiating and harmonizing roles. In this context, initiating refers to requesting information and clarification and evaluating ideas for problem solving. Harmonizing, on the other hand, refers to regulating the group unity through mediation. The sixth is the Interaction Management. This is an individual's ability to take turns in a discussion, initiate and terminate interaction based on a reasonably accurate assessment of the needs and desires of others. Ruben's Behavioural Theory also mentions Tolerance for Ambiguity. It describes an individual's ability to "react to new and ambiguous situations with little visible discomfort. Since RCCG comprises people with different people at different social class and level of life, which, in turn, contribute to their attitude and behaviour in intercultural situations, the seven dimensions proposed by the postulator of the theory are necessary to determine what the people know and do, especially during intercultural interaction or engagement.

Cultural Diversity and Challenges of Interculturality in RCCG Samonda, Ibadan: Report of Focus Group Discussion (FGD)

To examine individual level of intercultural communication competence of the leadership of the parishes of the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone, Oyo Province 16, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was conducted by the researchers among pastors in charge of zone. The FGD was held on Sunday 1st October 2023 at the Zonal Headquarters in Samanda, Ibadan. A total of nine (9) pastors, representing nine (9) parishes in the zone, participated in the FGD. The parishes are: Shekinah Glory Parish, Breakthrough Parish, Redemption Parish, Salvation Assembly Parish, Messiah Ambassador Parish, His Glory Pavilion Parish, Royal Sanctuary Parish, Latter Glory Parish, and Mercy Land Parish. The FGD was based on cultural diversity, interculturality within the parishes, and the strategies adopted by the pastors to manage their interplay within the congregations. Overall, the FGD was designed to strike a balance between the intercultural communication competence of the participants and their disposition to applying the competence to solving problems arising from cultural diversity among their congregations.

The talking points focused on six main subjects, namely:

- ❖ The level of awareness of cultural diversity among leaders in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone.
- ❖ The challenges (if any) of cultural diversity to leadership experience among leaders in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone.
- ❖ The relationship between gift sharing, Christian Social Responsibility and cultural diversity in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone.
- ❖ The effects on gift sharing on church growth, such as attendance on the days set aside to share gifts and the commitment of members to, for example, evangelism in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone.

- ❖ The challenges of intercultural communication in gift sharing and Christian Social Responsibility among leaders in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone.
- ❖ Measures to improve intercultural communication skills and strategy to grow the church in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone.

Procedure

The researchers provided a brief introduction of the aim of the research, and sought the consent of all prospective participants. All the participants had equal opportunities to respond and discuss the questions raised by the researchers. The FGD lasted for one hour and the entire session was digitally recorded using an Android phone. The recorded discussion was later transcribed by the researchers. The texts of the responses of participants are interpreted and analysed using textual and content analysis methods.

Textual analysis is used in qualitative researches to describe and interpret visual messages (such as paintings, photographs, websites, architectures etc.), electronic materials (such as audiotapes, videotapes, films, etc.) and written documents (such as transcript of speeches, conversations, newspapers, letters etc.). Content analysis is a qualitative method researchers use to identify, describe, and analyse the occurrences of messages and message characteristics embedded in a text (Gray, Botan, Kreps, 2000). The content of the responses of the participants in the FGD, which have been transcribed into texts, were subjected to critical content analysis to answer the questions that are posed in the study. Important anecdotes that provoked or buttressed perspectives that the participants convey in their responses are used as quotes and vignettes in the analysis of results.

Findings

The results of the FGD are presented below:

Question 1: What is the level of awareness of cultural diversity among leaders in the RCCG Shekinah Zone?

Findings:

Most of the pastors indicated that their parishes comprised of multicultural membership as follows:

- ❖ Shekinah Glory Parish membership comprises of Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa, Edo, and Ikwere
- ❖ Peace Assembly: Multicultural membership comprises of Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, Edo, and Egede
- ❖ Royal Sanctuary Parish membership comprises of Yoruba, Hausa, and Egede
- ❖ Redemption Parish: Multicultural membership comprises of Yoruba, Igbo Edo, and Egede
- ❖ Salvation Parish: Multicultural membership comprises of Yoruba and Igbo
- ❖ Breakthrough Parish: Multicultural membership comprises of Yoruba, Edo, and Igbo
- ❖ Messiah Ambassador: Multicultural membership comprises of Yoruba, Igbo, and Togolese
- ❖ Latter Glory Assembly: Multicultural membership comprises of Yoruba, Igbo, and Hausa
- ❖ His Glory Pavilion: Multicultural membership comprises of Yoruba and Igbo.

What the responses suggest is that all the participants demonstrated strong awareness of cultural diversity in their parishes.

Question 2: Has cultural diversity been a challenge to your leadership experience in the Church?

Findings:

Some participants claimed they have no challenges of cultural diversity, as the case with Salvation Parish and Redemption Parish. However, there are indications that cultural diversity constitutes many challenges to leadership experience in some local churches. This is particularly the case where a section of the church is made of non-literate people in English language, which is usually the language of conducting services, especially of sermon rendition. This challenge is not peculiar to any

cultural group, but is prevalent among non-Yoruba speaking members, who are not familiar with the language of the environment.

In Royal Sanctuary Parish, for instance, there were challenges arising from cultural diversity.

For instance, the Egede and Hausa-speaking components of membership of the parish are mostly non-literate in the English language, which is the official language of conducting services, and are yet not-fully integrated into the language of the environment, which is Yoruba, thereby posing a challenge of communication. We, however, have overcome the challenge by interpreting our sermons through a third-party interpreter, especially to the Hausa-speaking members. The Egede group is assimilating the Yoruba language through interaction with the Yoruba-speaking members.

The same challenges were reported by Mercy Land Parish:

We have a similar challenge. Two women that just joined the parish do not understand the English Language. Even before they joined the church, we had people on ground who used the mixture of Yoruba and English language to communicate sermons and other information to those who did not understanding either Yoruba or the English language very well.

In both instances, intercultural communication is enhanced through third party interpretation of sermons. The use of “pidgin” English (mixture of dialect and English language) been adopted to drive home the points is an intercultural communication strategy. Besides, interpersonal relationship is fostered through this.

Question 3: What is the relationship between gift sharing, Christian Social Responsibility and cultural diversity?

Findings:

Almost all the participants claimed that they share gifts to members on certain Sundays in the month that are set aside for the purpose of

embarking on Social Responsibility programmes (Roger, 1991). For instance, some participants (3 parishes) claimed that they share gifts on every first Sunday of the month, which coincides with the monthly thanksgiving service of the Redeemed Christian Church of God. Some participants (3) claimed that they share gifts on every third Sunday of the month. While two (2) participants claimed that they share gifts twice monthly, that is, on every first and third Sundays, only 1 participant indicated that they share gifts to commemorate the birthdays of members. Two (2) participants claimed that they share gifts to members in their parishes on every Sunday. Overall, all the participants indicated that they share gifts to members, at least, once in a month. The responses are summarised below church-by-church:

- ❖ Redemption Parish: We share gifts to members every Sunday.
- ❖ Royal Sanctuary Parish: ‘We share gifts twice in a month, first Sunday (thanksgiving service) and on every third Sunday of the month for convenience’.
- ❖ Mercy Land Parish: ‘We share gifts every third Sunday’.
- ❖ His Glory Pavilion Parish: ‘We do it to commemorate the birthday of every member. It might twice or once monthly’.
- ❖ Salvation Parish: ‘We do it on third Sunday alone’.
- ❖ Messiah Ambassador Parish: ‘It is only on thanksgiving service that we share gift’.
- ❖ Breakthrough Parish: ‘We have it every thanksgiving Sunday’.
- ❖ Peace Assembly: ‘We share gifts almost every Sunday’.

Question 4: Does gift sharing have any effects on church growth, such as attendance on the days set aside to share gifts and the commitment of members to, for example, evangelism?

Findings:

All the participants reported that gift sharing has positive effects on church attendance. According to Mercy Land Parish, ‘everybody wants to come on that day, primarily to partake in the goodies’. Shekinah Glory Parish claimed that ‘gift sharing does affect attendance. The attendance is usually higher on the days we share gifts than on the days we do not

share gifts.’ Also, Salvation Parish indicated that ‘on the days we share gifts there is always increase in attendance’. Redemption parish observed that gift sharing ‘motivates members to come for the next service’, while Peace Assembly reported that ‘we have great attendance when we share gifts’. Almost all the participants also indicated that gift sharing as a strategy had positive impacts on the commitment of members to evangelism.

According to the participant from Royal Sanctuary Parish:

When we share gifts, we tell people to bring their neighbours. So, a lot of people find it easy to bring their neighbours if the neighbours have been told that prior Sundays they were given certain gifts. So, consistently, we get people’s commitment, as there were also gifts for people who bring more than a person. We reward people with gifts, and because of that some people want to go all out to ensure that they bring somebody to service.

Similarly, in the words of the participant from Salvation Parish:

The reward gift is like a bait to bring in more people because they will have something to take home. These are mostly students who look forward to have something to take home.

Also, the participants from Latter Glory Assembly claimed similar benefits. He says:

The sharing of gifts has been very helpful. It helps us to keep the members and not losing them.

However, the participant representing Breakthrough Parish observed that they go beyond gift sharing and embark on other interventions to get people committed. He observes:

Through our intervention and follow up, we have seen certain number of them (non-members) committed, and now they are our members.

Question 5: Do we have challenges of intercultural communication in gift sharing, and Christian Social Responsibility among leaders in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone?

Findings

Although all the participants have strong awareness of the cultural diversity in their churches, opinion varies on the challenges of intercultural communication in gift sharing and social responsibility programs. Some participants claimed that cultural differences do not constitute any challenge on these matters, while certain other participants admitted that cultural diversity has at some point affected gift sharing in their parishes.

In the words of the participant from Salvation Parish:

We are family. We do not act on the basis of tribe or ethnicity. I have Egede, Igbo, and Yoruba. Even among the Yoruba we have Ijebu, Ekiti. At that level, as a leader, I do not deal with them on the basis of cultural differences. So there is no problem of intercultural relationship. We do not look at the church as a divided entity. We look at it as one family in Christ.

The same sentiment is shared by participant from Shekinah Glory Parish. According to him:

We do not have such problems, because we do not look at cultural or ethnic considerations in the sharing of gifts.

On the contrary, certain participants, for example, participants from Mercy Land Parish and Royal Sanctuary Parish, admitted that they sometimes have challenges of acceptability of gifts among their members. Each of them reported particular incidences.

In the words of participant from Royal Sanctuary:

There was a time, I think a family weekend, when we asked people to bring gifts for one another. A farmer brought a large quantity of Okro as gift to be shared among the 7 families that make up the Church. But a particular family politely turned down the gifts because, according to them, they do not eat Okro in their family, and I think the taboo

was tied to cultural restraints. That day the family could not partake in the gift sharing.

Similar incidence was reported by participant from Mercy Land Parish:

It happened a long time ago in our parish when we shared gift of yam among members. One of the beneficiaries returned the tubers gifted their family the next day, because they claimed that the person that shared the gifts was not supposed to be the one to do so, based on personal or class conflict or offence on the part of the beneficiary.

Question 6: How do we improve on our cross-cultural communication skills and strategy to grow the church in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Shekinah Zone?

Findings:

The challenges of cross-cultural limitation compelled participating parishes to devise means to build bridges across-cultural constituents in the church. Specific instances of how the challenges of cross-cultural limitations were resolved were reported by the participants. These include third party interpretations of sermons, mixed language praise and worship sessions. In addition, the observation of cultural days in which every cultural group in the country (in the Church) is allowed to render special ministrations in songs, dance, drama and poems (*ewi*) to ensure that nobody is left behind in the church. According to participant from Royal Sanctuary Parish:

In my parish two Hausa men joined the parish sometimes ago. But they could barely speak English, nor did they understand Yoruba. We devised a means of communicating to them through a third-party interpreter, also a Hausa-speaking person, but who speaks spattering English.

Similarly, the participant from Messiah Ambassador Parish observed that:

A certain person who had wanted to join the church but could not because of language barriers but decided to rejoin because we do interpret our sermons now.

Also, the participant from Peace Assembly Parish observed that:

When we start service, we mix the language right from praise and worship session.

The participant from Shekinah Glory Parish suggested closer interaction across cultures, or what he called 'language of love', especially with minority cultural groups in the church to improve cross-cultural interactions. In his words:

We can use visitation as a language of love. Although they may not understand the language of the environment often spoken in the Church, if we move closer to them, interact with and win them over, it can encourage them to be interested in what we are doing in the Church.

Discussions

From the analysis of the data presented above, there is strong cultural diversity in the parishes, and pastors in the zones are aware that cultural diversity affect intercultural communication and interactions among the congregations. Thus, to harmonise cultural differences among their congregations, the Pastors adopted some measures, such as third-party interpretation of sermons, adoption of mixed languages in song renditions during services, particularly to accommodate the interests of minority groups among the members.

In other words, the pastors manifest the understanding that their congregations comprise people with different people at different social class and level of life, which contribute to their attitude and behaviour in most cases. Indeed, the seven behavioural measures of intercultural competence proposed in Rubens' theory, namely, display of respect; interaction posture; orientation to knowledge; empathy; self-oriented role behaviour; interaction management; and tolerance for ambiguity, manifest themselves within the church at different degrees.

Overall, there is a positive correlation between intercultural communication among the congregations and their behavioural manifestations. For example, in the management of linguistic differences among the congregations, they display respect, empathy and manifest a positive interaction posture. Thus, culturally-appropriate behaviours, such as use of a common language, such as the English Language, or culture-specific languages, and a third-party interpretation were adopted in during worship and sermon sessions, to mitigate the effects of linguistic diversity and protect the interest of minority languages speakers within the congregations.

In almost all the parishes, sharing of gifts is adopted to bridge the gaps between different people at different social class and level of life within the congregations. The sharing of gift as social responsibility activity has been successfully used to improve the commitment of members. But the practice has, to an extent, revealed that some members of congregation have low tolerance for ambiguity. In the context of Ruben's Theory of Intercultural Competence, 'tolerance for ambiguity' describes an individual's ability to "react to new and ambiguous situations with little visible discomfort'. However, the level of tolerance that certain segments of the congregations manifest in dealing with certain ambiguities that come gift sharing does not align with expectations. There is a tendency for some individuals to reject certain gifts that they consider culturally inappropriate, even when they fully know that the purpose of sharing gifts was humanitarian. For example, there was a case of family in one of the parishes who rejected okro on account that it was a taboo in their culture to eat the vegetable.

There was also a challenge with interaction management in regards to sharing of gifts. There was a case in a Parish, where a beneficiary of a gift returned it, because she had expected the item to be shared in a more discreet manner. The person in question felt that the gift should not have been delivered to her through an individual she considered of a lower social class. Overall, these cases indicate that strategies for intercultural competence within the Parishes were imperfect, and leaves room for

improvement in their intercultural communication skills and strategy.

Conclusion

Intercultural competence and diversity management strategy is necessary for effective leadership in any human organization that is characterized with cultural diversity. The Church, like any other multicultural human organization, is not totally immune from challenges of interculturality. Church leaders, particularly pastors, bear the responsibility to manage diversity of human experiences among the congregations, and mobilise them toward achieving common goals. This responsibility, however, requires a certain degree of cultural consciousness in pastoral leadership, as well as a willingness to act appropriately. The lack of cultural consciousness and willingness to adopt culturally–appropriate methods to accomplish may result into cultural dissonances and disunity among the congregation and, ultimately, hamper the mission goals of the church.

Overall, the findings suggest that pastors are aware of their responsibility to manage cultural diversity, harmonise members' cultural experiences and promote interculturality among the worshippers. It further suggests that Pastors within the zone have a considerably high degree of cultural consciousness, and were willing to promote positive intercultural behaviours among the worshippers. However, the leadership of the church still faces certain culturally-based dissonance and disunity among the congregation, which, in some ways, impinge negatively on overall mission objectives of the church. Thus, in order to promote interculturality among the congregations and mobilise them toward achieving common visions and missions of the church, the leadership of the church needs to adopt certain measures that are recommended in this paper.

Recommendations

1. Based on the foregoing findings and apart from further training in intercultural competence, the leaders and church members are

- expected to manifest Christ-like character, such as respect for people regardless of their cultural affiliation.
2. The need to show empathy for others and tolerate every member in the congregation no matter social class, sexual orientation and level of service in the church.
 3. It is also recommended that Pastors know their members cultural preferences and disposition and treat each cultural preference accordingly.
 4. The linguistic preferences are a good example. Based on the linguistic composition of their parishes, Pastors should make provision for the language differences in their churches through an appropriate use of, first and foremost, the immediate language of the church environment, which is likely to be the language of the majority.
 5. Pastors should make provision for secondary languages, namely, languages that are not necessarily the immediate language of the environment, but which are represented within the congregations. Another strategy recommended is the observation of cultural days. On such days, every cultural group is represented and allowed to participate fairly through extra-liturgical interventions, such as special ministrations in songs, dance, drama and poems (in local languages) with other culture-specific performances.
 6. Overall, the success of these measures depends on intercultural competence and diversity management strategy of pastoral leadership.

References

- Adekola, M.A. (1989). 'The Redeemed Christian Church of God: A Study of an Indigenous Pentecostal Church in Nigeria' (Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, 1989)
- Asonzeh, Ukah (2008). *A New Paradigm in Pentecostal Power: A Study of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Nigeria*, Trenton: Africa World Press
- Berry, R. (2022, March 21). 'How the Early Church Dealt with Racial and Cultural Division', *Christianity Today: Leadership Journal Archives*.

- Ehrman, Bart. D. (1993). *The Orthodox Corruption of Scriptures: The Early Effects of Christological Controversies in the New Testament*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Froehlich, Karlfried (1985). *Biblical Interpretation in Early Church*. Philadelphia: Fortress.
- Golubeva, I. (2020). Conceptualising intercultural (communicative) competence and intercultural citizenship. Book Chapter by Michael Byram and Irina Golubeva in *The Routledge Handbook of Language and Intercultural Communication*, Edited by Jane Jackson.
- Harvey, K. (2020). 'Multicultural Kingdom: Ethnic Diversity, Mission and the Church', United Kingdom: SCM Press, *Theology Engaging Church and Society*.
- Ian, P. *Ethnic and Social Diversity in the Early Church*. <https://www.psephizo.com/biblical-studies/ethnic-and-social-diversity-in-the-early-church/>
- Julian Peter & Richard Bradley (1990). *Missionaries*, London: BBC Books
- Kenneth J Archer (2011). *The Gospel Revisited: Toward a Pentecostal Theology of Worship and Witness*. Eugene, Oregon: Pickwick Publications
- Knibbe, K. (2009). 'We did not come here as tenants but as landlords': Nigerian Pentecostals and the Power of Maps. *African Diaspora* 2(2):133–158.
- Kruger, W. *A Systemic Perspective on Culture* https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/systemic-perspective-culture-waynekruger?trk=public_profile_article_view
- Lawrence Gray, Carl Botan, Garry Kreps (2000). 'Textual Analysis'. In *Investigating Communication: An Introduction to Research Methods* (pp. 225-256). Eagle Wood Cliffs: Princeton Hall.
- Marshall, R. (2019). *Political Spiritualities: The Pentecostal revolution in Nigeria*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Marshall, R., Peel, J. D. Y., Smith, D. J., Robbins, J., & Bayart, J. F. (2011). An Authors Meets Her Critics: Around "political spiritualities: The Pentecostal Revolution in Nigeria" by Ruth Marshall. *Religion and Society*, 2(1), pp: 138-157. <https://doi.org/10.3167/arrs.2011.020109>
- Roger, A Buchholz (1991). Corporate Social Responsibility and the Good Society: From Economics to Ecology,' *Business Horizon*, July/August, 1991.

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The Covenant, A Handbook of the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Christ
the Redeemer Press, New Edition, 2021

The Holy Bible, King James Version

Varathan, P. R. (2004). *Multiculturalism and The Church In Acts* , A thesis
submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree M.A.,
in the School of Religion and Culture, at the University of KwaZulu
Natal.

Impact of Church Leadership and Governance on the Church Missions

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Abstract

Jesus defined leadership as service (Matt. 10:1ff). To aspire to leadership in God's kingdom requires us to be willing to pay a price higher than others are willing to pay. The toll of true leadership is heavy and the more effective the leadership the higher it goes. The purpose of this paper the emphasis is on the impact of Church leadership and governance on church mission. In any Church, the governance/leadership system fulfills a set of core functions: assuring security, delivering basic spiritual services efficiently and effectively and generating financial needs. Church missions vary in terms of how well or how poorly their leadership system fulfils these functions. A descriptive method was adopted to carry out this research. It was found that the impact of Church leadership and governance on church missions needs to be on the positive side and should be improved. The paper put some measures of recommendation; such as meeting the needs of the church missions, maturing the numbers, taking charge during difficult times, multiplying workers and encouragement of the followers. The essence of leadership is to create an opportunity to influence the lives of others to be conformable to the norms acceptable to the missions work.

Keywords: Church Leadership, Church Missions, Church Organization, Governance, Yeshua

Introduction

The Christian Church was born in the Roman Empire (Harry 1976). Roman Empire was the Jewish background of the Church. The center of the empire was the city of Rome and in Rome, all the power of the government was in the hands of the emperor. The foundation of the Church can be deeply traced into the history and religion of Israel. Jesus

confirmed it in John 4:22 that the salvation came from Jews. Jesus also said in Matt.:17 that he chose not to destroy the law but bring it into fulfillment. The earliest Church was wholly Jewish, Jesus was a Jew and the whole New Testament was probably written by Jews.

According to Harry Boer, it was in Palestine the historic land of Israel that the church of the New Testament first appeared in history. It is difficult to set a date for its beginning. If we say the church began at Pentecost, we leave out of consideration the life and ministry of Jesus. If we say that the church began with him, we must remember the fact that the ministry of Jesus grew out of the life of Judaism. It is therefore best to say that the Church arose out of the life and work of the Lord and became a universal witness to him at Pentecost.

Boer clarified whatever confusion about the foundation of the Church. In ecclesiology, Christian Church can be defined as the true body of Christ or the original Institution established by Jesus. A Christian Church is not a building but a body of believers united in Christ. Church can also be defined as a type of Christian Organization which emphasizes the Bible as its behavioral standard and focuses on the inerrancy of the Bible.

The Church, both on Earth and in Heaven, is composed only of true Christians, those who are fully conformed to Christ (Eph.4:12-13, 5:26-27, Heb. 12:22-24, 1 John 3:2-3, Rev.19:7-8). The relation between Christ and the Church is set forth in these New Testament figures:

- i. The Shepherd and the Sheep (John 10)
- ii. The Vine and the Branches (John 15)
- iii. The Cornerstone and Stones of the Building (1 Cor.3:9, Eph.2:19-22, 1 Pet.2:5)
- iv. High Priest and the Kingdom of priests (Heb. 5:1-10, 1 Pet. 2:5-9, Rev. 1:6)
- v. The Head and many members Body (1 Cor. 12:12-13, Eph. 4:4)
- vi. The Last Adam and the New Creation (1 Cor. 15:22, 2 Cor.5:17)
- vii. The Bridegroom and the Bride (John 3:29, 2 Cor. 11:2, Eph. 5:25-33, Rev. 19:7-8).

The church's mission is to preach the gospel of the kingdom of God and making disciples throughout the world, teaching them exactly what Jesus taught (Matt. 28:19-20) while church leadership is a task to serve other members following Christ interests so that they can see and accomplish God's purpose for them in the world.

Identifying Leaders

There are two ways of identifying leaders in a group/church. The first is by "self-reporting", where you ask members whom they regard as the most influential in directing the affairs of the Church while the second is by "observation". This you do by asking for the person who seems to exert influence over their fellow members more than others. However, something that is common to the two methods is the influence, which the individual has on his fellows.

Consequently, those occupying leadership positions can either be classified as official or actual leaders depending on how they influence their followers. An example of this classificatory paradigm is that of Saul and David. For a period of over forty days, Saul could not muster his army to respond to the challenge from Goliath, the Champion of the Philistines, that anyone from the army of Israel should come and face him in a combat. It was when David, who previously had been "secretly" anointed King by Samuel came, he challenged and defeated Goliath. David's action thereby confirms the assertion that actual leaders emerge when official leaders refuse to discharge their responsibilities (1Samuel 7:1-54).

Governance presupposes a power structure with its own hierarchical categories, incorporating the economic, social, cultural, and political tensions within the society and thus displaying the inherent dynamism which absorbs the ebbs and flow of pressures towards ensuring peaceful solutions to existential problems confronting the citizens within the society. The means of arriving at such peaceful solutions to existential problems and the implementation of such solutions into purposeful actions make up what is called "the Governance process" (Olatunji, et al 2016).

As it is in the Federal, State and the Local Government, so also governance serves the same purpose among the Church Leadership. Church Leaders have the hierarchical power structure to incorporate how the people in mission will not suffer the tensions brought by the economic, social, cultural, and political within the society or mission field.

Field Marshal Montgomery said that his war experience taught him that the staff must be the servant of the troops and a good staff officer must serve his commander while remaining anonymous himself. In his book, *Training of the Twelve*, Alexander Bruce wrote: “In other Kingdoms they rule, whose it is to be ministered unto. In the Divine commonwealth, they rule who account it a privilege inister”. The Son of God became the servant of God in the mission of God. That image provides the pattern for mission societies, Churches and individual believers to fulfill their God given mission. The true leader is concerned primarily with the welfare of others, not with his own comfort or prestige. He shows sympathy for the problems of others, but his sympathy fortifies and stimulates, it does not soften and make weak. A spiritual Leader will always direct the confidence of others to the Lord. He sees in each emergency a new opportunity for helpfulness. When God chose a leader to succeed Moses, it was Joshua, the man who had proved himself a faithful servant (Exodus 33:11)

Leadership and Ministry

The term “Leadership” can be understood in more than one way. Some see it as a synonym for “ministry”, so that anyone engaged in Christian service is referred to as a leader. Others consider the term to be more restrictive in its meaning and to relate a functional description of someone in ministry whose role is to equip and release others into ministry. There is a definite world of difference between ministry and leadership though it may be possible for some to combine the two depending on the level of their engagement with either of them.

The Greek word “*Diakonia*” translated ministry in the New Testament means one who attends or waits on another, a servant or one who serves

in menial jobs. Ministry is doing things that rightly meet the need of the people while leadership is making people doing the right things so that not only the present need is met but their future is secured. The church leadership of today has failed by turning their responsibility upside down. Church Leadership is expected to serve the Church mission but Church mission is serving Church Leadership. “And as ye go, preach, saying, The kingdom of heaven is at hand. Heal the sick, cleanse the lepers, raise the dead, cast out devils: freely you have received, freely you give” (Matt. 10:7-8). Jesus and His disciples focused on the mission works instead of getting things in return unlike this generation.

“Self-sacrifice must be paid daily. A Cross stands in the path of spiritual leadership, and the leader must take it up. Jesus Christ laid down his life for us and we ought to lay down our lives for our brothers (1 John 3:16). To the degree the Cross of Christ is across our shoulders and over our backs, so the resurrection life of Christ is manifest through us. No cross, no leadership” (Olatunji, et al 2016). In this Century, we can count the numbers of the Church Leaders who sincerely laid their lives for Christ. Self-Sacrifice is becoming a taboo to the Church leadership in the ministry. Fulfilling the purpose of self-sacrifice leadership in the ministry bring about tremendous blessings to such leader.

In 1 Cor.12:1-6, Paul the Apostle discusses on spiritual gifts which help every believer to locate his rightful place and peculiarity in the plan and programme of God. He categorized the gifts and associated particular ones to each member of the Trinity (1Cor.12:4-6). A true picture emerges of how the gifts complement each other in ensuring that every Christian and body of Christ fulfills their calling.

Qualities of Church Leadership

“And he said unto them, look unto me, and do likewise: and behold, when I come to the outside of the camp, it shall be that, as I do, so shall you do” (Judges 7:17). Gideon led an army of just three hundred (300) men to face the host of Midianites that were in hundreds of thousands. As the leader and commander of the Army of Israel under God, he had to set himself as an example for the rest to follow. The qualities are:

- (1) *Outstanding*: Looking at Gideon example, a leader is someone who is act of outstanding influences other members or policies of the group than all the others. It will suffice to say the presence of each member of the group affects all the others to an extent. However, when the right of leadership is conferred on any, it stands a better chance of influencing the decision making process of the group more than others. A leader is the person who is in the front or goes first. He is the person who guides or directs a group of movements. Conclusively, the Leader is the one who is in the front and can boldly say unto the rest of the group “look on me and do likewise”.
- (2) *Executive Order*: James Burns said “Wesley had a genius for organization that he founded because he was such a gifted executive, his movement was unshaken when death deprived it of his presence and guidance. His judgement of others, his skill in deploying them to the mission’s best advantage and to win their loyal submission, amounted to genius and spread the moment from disasters that others experienced”. Wesley was divinely called and equipped. Leadership shapes the goals, ideology and structure of the group. Leadership is an activity that directs and facilitates the mission to a great extent. A leader is the one directing, controlling or governing the affairs of the group. Leading includes doing such things as planning, decision-making, personnel section and vision-setting.
- (3) *Ability*: A leader cannot translate vision into mission without executive ability. “The Lord is a God of judgement.” The word ‘judgement’ means order, so God is orderly. God requires of his stewards that all things be done decently and in order. The duty of church leadership is to reflect the orderliness of God in all that he does. Church mission is not a matter of organizing people into the kingdom, but neither is it justified in careful planning. Church mission depends on the power of God and The Holy Spirit, leading converts to salvation, despite the fact of depending on God and the

Holy Spirit, leaders must also plan and act on his plans for the sake of gospel research.

- (4) *Listening ear:* A leader must develop a listening ear at all times. Leaders should listen more than talking. A listening leader always more influence over his followers. It is difficult for any leader to know the root of the problems brought to him without mastering the art of listening but genuine listening seeks to understand another without pre-judgement (Oswald 1967). Leaders who want to show sensitivity should listen often and long and talk short and solemn. A lot of church leaders in the 21st century are too busy to listen.
- (5) *Education:* The ability to know how to read and write is highly important in church leadership. The position of leadership involves a considerable amount of correspondence. Apostle Paul has a moral integrity, intellectual honesty and we have the understanding of his spiritual life from his letters than from any other source. Anytime he found himself in trouble or challenges, he took his pen and paper in tears and sorrow not in suicide. If Paul had no education, it would have been difficult for him to write. A lot of those who are governing the church mission are called but not trained. They lack education. Saul of Tarsus is better known to us in Christendom as Paul. He was born to Jewish parents in a thoroughly observant home in Tarsus. His father was a Jewish community leader and a Roman citizen (Atowoju, 2010). Paul of Tarsus is one of the most influential figures in the world, who followed Jesus Christ's legacy and influence. Tarsus was known as a center of culture, philanthropy, trade, sport and education. Education was one of the major tools that brought about the influence of Pauls' leadership in his mission work. Letters formed an important part in Pauls' programme of follow up in the mission. When a leader is educated, writing spiritual letters and tracts for the mission would be easier. Clear language would be important in our letters but more importantly is the right spirit. Letters are an unsatisfactory medium of communication.

- (6) *Discipline*: Discipline is yet another responsibility of Church leadership, a duty often unwelcome. Any Christian society requires godly and loving discipline to maintain divine standards in doctrine, morals and conduct. Paul describes the spirit required in leaders who exercise discipline. “Brothers, if someone is caught in a sin, you who are spiritual should restore him gently but, watch yourself, or you also may be tempted’ (Galatians 6:1). The fundamental ingredient in all discipline is love. “Warn him as a brother” (2 Thessalonians 3:15). “I urge you, therefore, to reaffirm your love for him” (2Cor 2:8). The person who has faced up to his or her own problems and weaknesses is best able to help another in a way both loving and firm. The spirit of meekness will achieve far more than the spirit of criticism. Discipline in love is a forgone issue among the Church leadership because of personal gain.
- (7) *Providing guidance*: This is another area of Church leadership responsibility. The leader must go before his flock. Jesus gave us the pattern. “When he has brought out all his own, he goes on ahead of them, and his sheep followed him because they know his voice” (John 10:4). I follow the example of Christ (1 Cor. 7:1). Paul knew he was following, where he was going and he could challenge others to follow him there. It is not easy to guide people, even mature Christians, who have strong opinions of their own. The leader cannot assert his will recklessly.

There are various leadership styles but since our focus is mainly on the impact of the Church leadership governance on Church missions, I will briefly mention them;

- a. *Lordship leadership*: Theocracy 1Sam 8:7; Monarchical rule 1Sam 8:10-17 and at the extreme end is dictatorship. Lordship leadership should not be practiced in the Church mission because such a model gives us the leadership situation of which much was said in the time of the rule of judges in ancient Israel (Judges 17:6, 18:1, 21:25).

- b. *Partnership leadership*: This in the ideal sense finds an expression in the principles of Communism. The early Christian practiced something similar to this system by sharing and having everything in common (Acts 4:32). The democracy system of governance is akin to this type of leadership style. This understanding is derived from the Prophecies of Daniel and that of Apostle John in the book of Revelations.
- c. *Servant Leadership*: This style of leadership was taught and demonstrated by the Lord Jesus Christ. Jesus set an example in leading through serving. He washed his disciples' feet (John 13), something they found inappropriate and Peter was uncomfortable with this. This action does not reduce Jesus's authority, but increased it by this servant attitude. Jesus came to this world not to rule but to serve (Matt. 20:20-28; 1Kings 12:7; John 13: 1-16).

Recommendations

The Church Leadership has great impact on Church mission. Every member governing the Church influences the activities of the Church mission. Those in leadership outstandingly affect the Church mission. Being a Leader confers on mission the power or right to perform certain acts without impediment. The general purpose of leadership is to promote order in Church mission and its highest use is in serving others as Christ stated. "In this world the Kings and great men order their slaves around, and the slaves have no choice but to like it! But, among you, the one who serves you best will be your leader. Out in the world the master sits at the table and is served by his servants but not here! For I am your servant" (Luke 22:26-27).

Christians when given the opportunity to lead in any capacity should use the authority given to them well to the glory of God and benefit of those around them. Such appointment must be seen as emanating from God

that require some degree of state involvement and provides economic opportunity through rules-driven and transparent policy making regulation, fiscal arrangements, partnerships and Civil Service system” (Olatunji, et al 2016). The above quote also implies to the governance of Church mission. Church leadership must be able to morally govern the Church mission to provide effective and efficient service delivery.

- iv. *Make Charge during difficult times:* As the priests carried the ark in the Old Testament, Church Leaders are expected to help and support the Church mission through hard times to possess the possessions. Church leadership must be seen as a Fatherly figure that serves as a perfect focus for the positive emotional feelings individuals. This Fatherly figure role to some extent accounts for the power of certain leaders in special circumstances. Paul to the Corinthians says, “For though you might have ten thousand instructions in Christ, yet you do not have many fathers; for in Christ Jesus, I have gotten you through the gospel. Therefore, I urge you, imitate me” (1Cor 4:15-16).
- v. *Multiplying Workers:* Leaders have the primary responsibilities of teaching and edifying the members so that the faithful ones can also be trusted with the work of ministry (2Timothy 2:2, Exodus 18:13-26, Acts 11:22-26). The duty was important that the Apostles made it a priority (1Peter 5:1-4, Acts 6:2-4). The Leader should also have the ability to reward members in order to motivate them for a better performance (Numbers 27:18-23, Phil 2:19-20).
- vi. *Encouraged his followers:* Leaders complete the work by encouraging the heart of those who share the vision. David did this by caring for them as persons and not as pawns. David himself being encouraged by the Lord brought the same encouragement to others. Though, as a King, David never lost contact with his people and knew how to encourage them in difficult situations, He recognized the contribution of others. After victory over the Amalekites, He appreciated the role of both those who fought and could not fight (1 Samuel 30: 21-25). He grieved the loss of a warrior, though a rival

(1Samuel 30:33-37). David sent a delegation to attend the funeral of a neighboring King, they treated them as spies and humiliated them by shaving part of their head. When David heard this, he commanded them to stay there until their hair was fully grown and showed no mercy to those who humiliated his followers (11 Samuel 10:4-5).

References

- Alexander, B.B. (1831-99) was a professor of apologetics and New Testament at the Free Church College, Glasgow, From 1868 to 1899. *He wrote Training of the Twelve in 1871*
- Atowaju, Ayodele *Saul of Tarsus*, Bprint Publication, Lagos 2010.
- Burns James (1909), *Revival, Their laws and Leaders*, London: Hodder and stouvghton.
- Boer, Harry R. (1976). *A Church History of the Early Church*, Daystar press, Nig.
- Olatunji, A., et al (2016). *Ethics, Governance and social Order in Africa. Essays in Honour of Godwin S. Sogolo*. Department of Philosophy, University of Ibadan, Published by Zenith BookHouse Ltd. Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Oswald J.S. (1967). *Spiritual Leadership*, Oasis International Limited, USA.

Adopting the Renaissance of Digital Technologies in Religious Studies in Nigerian Federal Universities

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Abstract

Adopting the renaissance of digital technologies is inevitable in all fields of studies, religious studies inclusive. Digital technology has brought a new era of efficiency and learning strategies in human history. It has also become a significant key in deriving global economic, scientific, educational and religious growth in Africa, especially in Nigeria. Consequently, in the face of increasingly fierce global competition, it is essential to take advantage of full benefits and potential offered by the renaissance of digital technologies to remain relevant and competitive. Previous studies on digital technologies have focused mainly on digital strategy, digital transformations, and Artificial Intelligence, with little attention paid to adopting the renaissance of digital technologies. Therefore, this paper examined adopting the renaissance of digital technologies, to understand its relevance to religious studies in federal universities in Nigeria (FUN). This study employed a documentation method for data gathering. Data were sourced mainly from published works on digital technologies. Data were content analysed within the ambit of the connectivist theory of Downes and Siemens. The study showed that by adopting digital technology as a catalyst of change, religious studies procure discovery, exploration, and growth, transcending traditional boundaries to unlock the unlimited possibilities of religious studies in the digital age. The study concludes that adopting the renaissance of digital technologies is relevant to preparing students and educators for the demands of the current digital age. It also recommends relevant training workshops on the use of digital

technologies to acquire digital literacy skills for efficiency in religious studies in Nigeria.

Keywords: Digital Renaissance, Digital Adoption, Digital Technology, Religious Studies, Nigerian Federal Universities

Introduction

Digital religion studies appeared in the mid-1990s at the time that scholars in both media and religious studies commenced to become aware of the fact that the new technology of computer internetworking invented a unique pace for people to re-present religion in a technological setting (Campbell, 2024). As a result of the rapid advancement of technology and the increasing in adoption of digital solutions across various sectors, Africa is on the cusp of a digital revolution (P23 Africa, 2024). To this effect, adopting the renaissance of digital technologies is inevitable not only in all fields of studies such as engineering, physical sciences, and other relevant educational domains but also in religious studies in Africa, especially in Nigeria. This is because it has brought a new era of efficiency and learning strategies into human history. According to Johnson, Adams, Estrada and Freeman (2019), digital technology has brought about a new period of possibilities, and transformations. Digital technology has also become a significant key in deriving global economic, scientific, educational and religious growth in the world at large, especially in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities.

Religious Studies in Nigeria consist of the study of three major religions: African Traditional Religion, Christian Religion and Islamic Religion. African indigenous religion includes all African beliefs and practices that are regarded as religious before the advent of foreign religions (Christian Religion and Islamic Religion) in Africa. "It is the belief system that has been handed down from one generation to another in Africa. It is the religion that is indigenous to Africans" (Ibezim, 2024, 168). Christian Religious Studies as a field of study focuses mainly on systematic examination of the Christian faith as contained in the Old Testament and

New Testament components of the Bible (Baiyeri, 2019). Islamic Religion is one of the three Abrahamic and monotheistic religions– the others are Judaism and Christianity. It is a religion based on the Quran and the teachings of Muhammad, the founder of the religion. The word *Islam* in Arabic means “submission” or “surrender.” It implies surrender or submission to the will of Allah. The will of Allah, to which Muslims (Islamic believers) must submit, is made known through the sacred scriptures, called the Quran, which Prophet Muhammad claimed to have received from Allah (in Arabic, *Allah* means “God.”) (Rahman, Mahdi, & Schimmel, 2024).

For effective education in religious studies in Nigeria, it is pertinent to understand digital religion in teaching and learning in the current digital era. As Campbell (2023, pp. 218-219) rightly notes, “Digital religion as a term was [...] used to describe the understanding that contemporary religion is being practiced in both online and offline contexts, and these religious contexts intersect with one another in interesting and important ways worthy of further scrutiny.” Thus, the fact that digital technologies have brought a new era of efficiency and learning strategies in human history, the above three major religions in Nigeria require adopting the renaissance of digital technologies to remain relevant and competitive in the current digital age. Previous studies on digital technologies have focused mainly on digital renaissance in tertiary language teaching and learning strategies (Musa, 2024). They also concentrate on digital transformations in Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Hariyanti & Kristanti, 2024). Kue, Williams, Perimal-Lewis, and McCauley (2024) deal with the use of Artificial Intelligence/ Machine Learning to detect and minimize medical errors. While some scholars look into the impact of adopting the digital strategy on the competitive advantage in the banking sector (Al Afaishat, Maadhede & Yamin, 2024), others emphasise artificial intelligence applications in Evangelical and Pentecostal/Charismatic Churches (La Cruz & Mora, 2024). However, little attention has been paid to adopting the renaissance of digital technologies. This study is, therefore, designed to examine adopting the renaissance of digital technologies, to understand

its relevance to religious studies in Nigerian federal universities. This study focuses mainly on federal universities that offer religious studies as a course of study. They are chosen because they are being controlled and financed by the federal government. Therefore, FUN ought to serve as a template for state and private universities.

Some of the pertinent questions arising from this study include: What do the terms digital renaissance and digital adoption mean? What are the challenges in adopting digital technology in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities? What is the relevance of adopting the renaissance of the digital in religious studies or the advantages of adopting digital technology in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities? This study aims to provide answers to these questions. The study employs a documentation method for data gathering. Data are sourced mainly from published works on digital technologies in Nigeria. Data will be content analysed within the ambit of the Connectivist Theory of Downes and Siemens.

Theoretical Framework

The Connectivist Theory of Downes (2010) and Siemens (2004), which is adopted as the theoretical framework for this study, posits that as a result of the introduction of the internet, social media, blogs, and online discussion forums, the approach to educational theory has further radically changed. Learning can no longer be considered an individual trait as there are now networks, resources, and opportunities obtainable that were formerly unimaginable. As noted by Kok (2009), the principle behind connectivism is that learning is reliant on multiple sources of view. The capability to study in this context is influenced by the variety of the network and also the potency of the bonds between the information sources and may also make use of 'non-human appliances' (e.g. virtual and augmented reality). The procedure of identifying these sources is itself component of the learning process and can enable the learner to get a greater understanding of the subject. As a result, the usage of technology with the flexibility and interactivity that it provides has been explained as bringing about an enhanced constructivist

learning environment. Sahin (2012) also avers that by transforming the experience to a learner-led approach, connectivism is a good instance of heutagogy. One of the main strengths of connectivism centers on the fact that it enables flexible learning time. If a learner feels like learning, they can do so at their own convenient time without being dependent on formal and organised programmes that may clash with location difficulties, work, or family commitments. This capability to reiterate learning at the learner's convenience until mastery is achieved is an important attribute particularly as a lack of available time for slow learners has already been identified as a weakness of the traditional constructivist approach. The second strength of connectivism is the fact that it has the prospective to expose the learner to a vast range of information.

However, connectivist theory has three weaknesses. The first one is that it prospective to expose the learner to a vast range of information is also considered a weakness if that information is inexact or the amount of information is overwhelming. The second weakness of this approach centers on the fact that it may place those with a lack of digital literacy skills at a disadvantage. Thirdly, there are also concerns regarding the prospective harmful effects of an addiction to technology and the social isolation that this may foster. Despite these limitations or weaknesses, the present study adopts this theoretical framework to maximize its strengths in adopting the renaissance of digital technologies in religious study in Nigeria. This is to understand the relevance of adopting the renaissance of digital to religious studies in Nigeria. This is necessary because "contemporary religion is being practiced in both online and offline contexts and these religious contexts intersect with one another in interesting and important ways worthy of further scrutiny" (Campbell, 2023, 218-219).

Clarification of Terms

It is pertinent to clarify "digital renaissance and digital adoption," the keywords that form the basis of this study, and to explain how it is employed in this study. The word "renaissance" calls to mind images of

rebirth, renewal, and revival—a period of deep cultural, intellectual, and artistic flourishing in human history. Thus, the term “digital renaissance” sums up the deep cultural, intellectual, and technological transformations that have reshaped educational practices in the 21st century (Warschauer, 2019). UNESCO (as cited in Musa, 2024) avers that in the same way, the Renaissance era marked a resurgence of innovation and creativity in human history, the digital renaissance indicates a parallel revival within the ambit of education, stimulated by the incorporation of digital technologies into teaching and learning practices. The main aim of the digital renaissance is to focus on the imperative to reimagine educational practices in response to the evolving digital landscape (Musa, 2024). Likewise, in the religious context, as it is used in this study, the digital renaissance implies a resurgence of innovation and creativity, driven by the integration of digital technologies into teaching and learning in religious studies and practices in Nigeria. This paradigm shift is not just only about digitizing traditional techniques but also involves a fundamental reimagining of pedagogical approaches, curriculum design, and educational paradigms to harness the full potential of digital tools in fostering religious skill and intercultural competence (Musa, 2024) in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities.

Furthermore, “digital adoption is the process of learning how to use new technology that enables you to take advantage of its full benefits and potential” (Whatfix, 2024, p. 1). It can also be defined as the state where somebody can employ tools such as programs, websites, apps, or software to their full capacity to do various kinds of digital process (Herman, n. d.). Thus, digital adoption usually entails implementing a definite technology solution (Bdc, n. d.). In a religious setting, digital adoption is taken place when a religious organisation facilitates the widespread use of the new technology by her members during implementation with contextually guided onboarding and training, as well as on-demand performance support. As a result, in the face of increasingly fierce global competition, it is essential to take advantage of full benefits and potential offered by adopting the renaissance of digital to remain relevant and competitive

(Hariyanti & Kristanti, 2024) in all fields of studies, especially in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities.

Challenges in Adopting the Renaissance of Digital Technology in Religious Studies in Nigerian Federal Universities

Adopting the renaissance of digital is a vital step for religious studies to remain relevant to contemporary Nigeria in this current digital age. However, in the process, religious studies in Nigerian federal universities often face various challenges that can obstruct their capability to adopt digital technology effectively. In the empirical study of Atsumbe, Rmond and Duhu (as cited in Baiyeri, 2019) in one of the Nigerian federal universities, the first main challenge of adopting digital technologies in religious studies is inadequate infrastructures for effective teaching and learning, especially for e-learning. It is also discovered that internet services could not be easily accessed outside the university campus. Secondly, the study shows that even though the lecturers do possess electronic devices and laptops that could facilitate e-learning; they could not effectively employ those devices to teach. Thirdly, the study depicts that most student who owned electronic devices and laptops were found to be ineffective in using their devices for e-learning purposes. Besides, the study reveals that major challenges associated with adopting the renaissance of digital technologies in religious studies include poverty, poor funding, and poor electric power supply within and without the university. Finally, it is noted that attitudinal problems of resistance to change on the part of lecturers was discovered to hamper the use of e-learning infrastructures for teaching and learning purposes in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities.

The study of Anene, Iman, and Odumuh (2014) in Nigerian universities shows that there are many challenges to adopting the renaissance of digital technologies in religious studies. These include infrastructure deficiencies or underdeveloped digital infrastructure, financial and technical challenges, lack of e-learning library domain, lack of online seminars and no discussion with lecturers, no online examination, and

there are limited bandwidths. Moreover, Baiyeri (2019), in his study, notes that even though religious students do not regard it as sinful to use social media for educational purposes and religious inclinations, personal spirituality, parental influence, negative peer pressure, and religious education of the students of religious studies were not found to be hindrances to adopting the renaissance of digital technologies in teaching and learning in religious studies, financial challenge and technical challenge such as inadequate of electricity and broadband internet service remain problematic to adopting digital technologies in religious studies in Nigeria. He further considers general issues of weak infrastructure, lack of relevant skills, high cost, limited access to affordable internet connectivity, lack of relevant software, a deficit in well-equipped e-learning centres, inadequate electricity or power supply, low level of computer literacy among support staff, inadequate training of students and staff on e-learning technologies as perennial challenges to adopting e-learning for educational purposes in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities.

In the same vein, Musa (2024) considers digital inequality, technological infrastructure limitations, pedagogical integration challenges, and privacy and security concerns as the key challenges and barriers to adopting the renaissance of digital technologies in tertiary language teaching and learning strategies (Musa, 2024). These mentioned challenges and barriers are not only hindering adopting digital technologies in tertiary language teaching and learning strategies, but also hindering adopting digital technologies in religious studies teaching and learning strategies.

In facing these challenges and barriers, religious studies teachers and students need to develop a holistic and sustainable strategy for adopting the renaissance of digital technologies in religious studies. This comprises allocating adequate resources, investing in digital infrastructure, improving technological infrastructures for effective teaching and learning—especially for e-learning, strengthening their online presence, organizing adequate training programmes on digital technologies for both staff and students to develop their digital literacy

skills, provision of unlimited internet facilities, improving data security, and embracing cultural change that supports technological innovation. By overcoming these challenges, religious studies can remain relevant, increase their competitiveness, harness the full potential of digital transformation and maximize the relevance of adopting the renaissance of digital technologies.

The Relevance of Adopting the Renaissance of Digital Technology to Religious Studies in Nigerian Federal Universities

Adopting the renaissance of digital technology opens up important opportunities for religious studies to develop and compete in an increasingly digitally connected society. One of the main opportunities is expanding religious studies' scope. By using online platforms such as websites, social media and digital marketplaces, religious studies educators, students and researchers can acquire the necessary knowledge in their field of study throughout the world without being limited by geographical boundaries. This opens the door to wider effective religious studies (Rogers, 2016). Sinclair (2013) rightly notes that due to the availability of digital technologies in the current digital age, modes of communication and the 'information landscape' has changed significantly within religious studies as a discipline. Chrystides (as cited in Sinclair, 2013, p. 45) also avers that "religion is the second most popular topic to feature in the World Wide Web." This shows that through the use of the Internet such as websites, Facebook pages, blogs or Tweets, it is feasible to have wider and faster access to religious information. These include information about different religious groups, organisations and institutions and their leaders. Moreover, digital technology has considerably broadened opportunities for networking and sharing information with other students and scholars of religion across the world (Sinclair, 2013).

Digital technology is relevant to religious studies because it has many positive impacts on religious practices and beliefs. "Digital technology has significantly impacted religion by reshaping religious practices,

beliefs, and communities” (Insight from top 5 papers, 2024, para. 1). As Campbell (2005, p. 311) notes, “Digital technology has created new opportunities for social interaction and religious experiences and for the development of new cultural practices, patterns of belonging and participation.” He further explains that new expressions of religion comprise “cyberchurches, cybertemples, online rituals (such as e-prayer and virtual pilgrimages), and online religious communities” (Campbell, 2005, p. 311), interactive worship, for example via avatars, webcasting of religious services (Campbell, 2013, p. 1), as well as several websites, Facebook pages, iPhone apps, Twitter accounts, blogs and online forums devoted to religious issues or the provision of religious services. Although some scholars, such as Chryssides, have emphasized some of the limits of religious activities on cyberspace due to the lack of physical sacred space and the absence of the physical presence of officiants or sacred objects (Chryssides, 2007, p. 400), others scholars like Brenda Brasher (as cited in Cowan, 2011, p. 462) have gone to the extent of predicting that “using a computer for online religious activity could become the dominant form of religion and religious experience in the next century.” Whether this prediction will be the case or not, it is significant to keep in mind that how religion is presented, discussed and practiced online also impacts on the ways it is perceived and practiced offline (and vice versa).

Besides, although digital technologies deteriorate interpersonal communication and good human relations necessary in sustaining African Indigenous Religion and traditional education by exposing the youths to social vices and encouraging religious syncretism, it is worthy of note that adopting the renaissance of digital technologies have given room for availability of literature on African Traditional Religion and education (Ibezim & Chukwuma-Offor, 2024, p. 166). It is essential to understand that digital technologies provide useful information on African culture, religion and traditional education to researchers on the internet. Indeed, digital technologies have made African indigenous religion and education to shift from the traditional stage of having no written records to the digital religion and education. As a result,

information concerning the African traditional religion and education can be easily retrieved from the internet these days. Therefore, digital technologies are functional in making data or information on African tradition education and religion accessible to students and young adults in this current digital age (Ibezim & Chukwuma-Offor, 2024, pp. 173-174).

In addition, adopting the renaissance of digital technology has also assisted religious studies' scholars to improve their efficiency and learning strategies. By implementing e-learning, e-library, PowerPoint presentation and virtual presentation, religious studies' students and researchers can reduce the time and costs required to achieve their educational goals. According to Hauck (2024), cost savings are inevitable due to the fact that more efficient processes and digital tools can reduce operational costs over time. Likewise, increased efficiency gives room for automating routine tasks, saves time and reducing errors in every sector. Similarly, Cowan (2011, p. 146) affirms that in religious studies, digital technology "brings us into contact with a considerably wider range of informants and deeper pool of data than we might otherwise expect," and at relatively low cost, vast speed and without the need to travel. This gives room to have access to current and relevant academic materials and to focus more on their academic pursuit without having the barrier of geographical boundaries (Hariyanti & Kristanti 2024).

Adopting the renaissance of digital facilitates better decision-making in religious studies. This is possible through digital adopting because easy access to data helps scholars and religious adherents make informed decisions quickly (Hauck, 2024). Researchers of digital religion studies affirm that "early technologies such as the World Wide Web, email, newsgroups, and discussion forums were becoming spaces facilitating religious conversations and experimentation with new manifestations of religious rituals" (Campbell, 2024, p. 222). In the same vein, Stephen O'Leary explained how technology of the internet as at the time he wrote his article was helping to set up "a new form of sacred space, as both traditional religious groups and new forms of religion engaged online,

and cyberspace gave rise to both Christian discussion groups and the creation of technopagan rituals” (O’Leary, 1996, 786). Brenda Brasher (as cited in Campbell, 2024, p. 222) also notes that the cyborg as a religious concept helpful to religious studies scholars, enabling them converse about the nature of humanity in an increasingly technologized society. These notions suggest that the internet and the emerging technologies invented new possibilities for religious discourse and intensified public consciousness of various facets of religion that could potentially have cultural and institutional impact.

Another relevance of adopting renaissance of digital technology in religious studies is that it increases competitiveness. By following the latest technology trends such as artificial intelligence, data analysis and the Internet of Things, religious studies’ students and scholars can create competitive advantages in their studies, services or educational programmes. This allows them to compete with their colleagues and stay relevant in a rapidly changing society (Denning, 2018).

Moreover, adopting the renaissance of digital is essential for success in religious studies. Digital renaissance stresses the significance of digital literacy and fluency in the workforce in the 21st century (Hockly, 2021). As the global economy turns out to be increasingly reliant upon digital technologies, proficiency in digital skills is necessary for success in almost all fields, including religious-related professions. Thus, incorporating digital literacy and digital citizenship skills into religious studies curricula is imperative to prepare students for the demands of the digital age and equip them with the adequate skills and competencies required to flourish in a globalized, interconnected world (Musa, 2024). Other relevance of adopting renaissance of digital technologies in religious studies include increasing religious adherent engagement through more personalized and interactive digital experiences, as well as developing new ideas and services based on data analysis and members’ feedback. By utilizing digital technology creatively and innovatively, religious studies can take big steps in developing their religious communities and expand their impact in an increasingly connected global society. Therefore, adopting digital technology is not only a

necessity but also an inevitable opportunity for religious studies educators, students and researchers who want to develop and survive in this digital era (Rogers, 2016).

Conclusion

The study considers financial and technical challenges as the two types of challenges in adopting digital technologies in religious studies in Nigerian federal universities. While the financial challenge includes poverty, poor funding, and high cost of digital facilities, technical challenges include infrastructure deficiencies or underdeveloped infrastructure which hinders effective teaching and learning, limited access to affordable internet connectivity, lack of relevant digital skills, attitudinal problems of resistance to change on the part of scholars, deficit in well-equipped e-learning centres, inadequate electricity or power supply, low level of computer literacy, inadequate training for students and staff on e-learning technologies as perennial problems to adopting the renaissance of digital technologies for religious studies purposes in Nigeria. By overcoming these challenges, religious studies can remain relevant, increase their competitiveness and harness the full potential of digital transformation.

The study shows that adopting the renaissance of digital technologies is relevant to religious studies because the opportunities presented by digital technologies are significant. Firstly, it has expanded religious studies' scope. Secondly, it has significantly impact religion by reshaping religious practices, beliefs, and communities. Thirdly, it has given room for availability of literature on African Traditional Religion and education. Besides, it has assisted the scholars of religious studies to improve their efficiency and learning strategies, as well as facilitates cost savings. Moreover, it facilitates better decision-making and increases competitiveness in religious studies. Lastly, it increases religious adherent engagement through more personalized and interactive digital experiences, and also develops new ideas and services.

The study also reveals that by adopting digital technology as a catalyst of change, religious studies procuring discovery, exploration, and growth,

transcending traditional boundaries to unlock the unlimited possibilities of religious studies in the digital age. Thus, incorporating digital literacy and digital citizenship skills into religious studies curricula is not only imperative but also relevant to prepare students for the demands of the current digital age and equip them with the skills and competencies necessary to flourish in a globalized, interconnected world (Musa, 2024).

Recommendations

The study recommends that adopting the renaissance of digital technology is a new trend in religious studies for efficiency and learning strategies that must be imbibed for its relevance in all fields of studies, especially in religious studies in Nigeria. The study also recommends relevant training workshops on the use of digital technologies and acquisition of digital literacy should be mandatory to both students and educators in religious studies in Nigerian universities. Besides, the study recommends that government should allocate adequate resources in religious studies by investing in digital infrastructure for the sake of improving technological infrastructures for effective teaching and learning, especially e-learning in Nigerian universities.

References

- Anene, J. N., Iman, H., & Odumuh, T. (2014). Problems and Prospect of E-learning in Nigerian Universities. *International Journal of Technology and Inclusive Education*, 3 (2).320 -327.
- AL Afaishat, T., Al-Maadhede, M., & Yamin, I. (2024). The impact of Adopting the Digital Strategy on the Competitive Advantage: A Moderating Role of Employee Satisfaction in the Jordanian Banking Sector. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 22 (1), 193-204. doi:10.21511/ppm.22(1).2024.17
- Baiyeri, H. B. (2019). Problems of Adopting E-Learning among Students of Christian Religious Studies in Nigeria. *Journal of Pristine*, 15 (1). 1-11.
- <https://www.globalacademicgroup.com/journals/pristine/PROBLEMS%20OF%20ADOPTING%20E>

- Bdc, (n. d.). What is Digital doption? <https://www.bdc.ca/en/articles-tools/technology/invest-technology/what-is-digital-adoption>
- Campbell, Heidi A. (2023). The Dynamic Future of Digital Religion Studies. 217-236. doi:10.1163/9789004549319_009.
- Campbell, Heidi A. (2005). Making Space for Religion in Internet Studies. *Information Society*, 21. 309-315.
- Campbell, Heidi A. (2013). The Rise of the Study of Digital Religion. In Heidi A. Campbell (Ed.), *Digital Religion: Understanding Religious Practice in New Media Worlds* (pp. 1-21). London/ New York: Routledge.
- Cowan, Douglas E. (2011). The Internet. In Michael Stausberg and Steven Engler (Eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of Research Methods in the Study of Religion* (pp. 459-473). London/ New York: Routledge.
- Denning, S. (2018). *The Age of Agile: How Smart Companies Are Transforming the Way Work Gets Done*. AMACOM.
- Downes S. (2010). New Technology Supporting Informal Learning. *J Emerg Technol Web Intell*, 2(1). 27-33.
- Hariyanti, S., & Kristanti D. (2024). Digital Transformation in MSMEs: an Overview of Challenges and Opportunities in Adopting Digital Technology. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis, Akuntansi dan Keuangan (JAMBAK)*, 3(1). 37-46. doi.org/10.55927/jambak.v3i1.8766 36
- Hauck, T. (2024). 7 Digital Adoption Strategies That Boost Business Success. <https://www.prosci.com/blog/digital-adoption-strategies>
- Herman, M. (n.d). What Does Digital Adoption Mean in the Modern Workplace? <https://www.lumapps.com/digital-workplace/what-is-digital-adoption-benefits-strategies/>
- Hockly, N. (2021). *Blended Learning*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ibezim, I. G., & Chukwuma-Offor, A. M. (2024) The Impact Of Digital Technologies On African Indigenous Religion And Education. *NJIKO: A Multi-Disciplinary Journal of Humanities, Law, Education and Social Sciences*, 2 (1). 166-178.
- Insight from top 5 papers, (2024). How Digital Technology Effect on Religion? <https://typeset.oi/questions/how-digital-technology-effect-on-religion-libbygtxpd>
- Johnson, L., Adams B., S., Estrada, V., M., & Freeman, A. (2019). Nmc Horizon Report: 2019 higher education edition. Educause.

- Kok A. (2009). Understanding the Technology Enhanced Learning Environments from a Cognitive Perspective. *Int Educ Studies*, 2 (4). 3-9.
- Kue, C. , Williams, T., Perimal-Lewis, L., & McCauley, V. (2024). Digital Healthcare Safety Research Proposal: How well is the use of AI/Machin Learning to detect and minimize medical errors, and improve patient safety? The Future of Digital Health Research. *Digital Healthcare Safety*, 3 (2). 1-15. doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18511.91046
- La Cruz, A., & Mora, F. (2024). Researching Artificial Intelligence Applications in Evangelical and Pentecostal/Charismatic Churches: Purity, Bible, and Mission as Driving Forces. *Religions*, 15 (234). doi.org/10.3390/rel15020234
- Musa, S. Z. B. S. (2024). Digital Renaissance: Reinventing Tertiary Language Teaching and Learning Strategies in Evolving Digital Landscape. *International Journal of Contemporary Issues*, 2 (1). 1-32. <https://www.researchgate.net/search/publication?q=Digital+Renaissance%3A+Reinventing+Tertiary+Language+Teaching+and+Learning+Strategies+in+Evolving+Digital+Landscape>
- O’Leary, Stephen D. (1996). Cyberspace as Sacred Space: Communicating Religion on Computer Networks. *Journal of The American Academy of Religion*, 64 (4). 781–808.
- P23 Africa. (2024). Africa’s Digital Renaissance: How Technology Will Thrive in the Next 10 Years. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/africas-digital-renaissance-how-technology-thrive-next-10-years-r9pif/>
- Rahman, F., Mahdi, M. S., and Schimmel, A. (2024). “Islam.” *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Islam>
- Rogers, D. L. (2016). *The Digital Transformation Playbook Rethink Your Business for the Digital Age*. Columbia University Press.
- Şahin M. (2012). Pros and Cons of Connectivism as a Learning Theory. *International Journal Physics and Social Science*, 2 (4). 437-454.
- Siemens G. (2004). Connectivism: A Learning Theory for the Digital Age. elearnspace.
- Sinclair, S. (2013). Digital Literacy in Religious Studies. *The Journal of the British Association for the Study of Religions*. Diskus14. 37-54. <http://www.basr.ac.uk/diskus/diskus14/sinclair.pdf>

- Thorne, S. L., & Reinhardt, J. (2017). Digital Technologies And The Future Of Language Learning and Teaching. *Foreign Language Annals*, 50(1), 1-8.
- Warschauer, M. (2019). *Technology And Social Inclusion: Rethinking The Digital Divide*. MIT Press.
- What is Digital Adoption. <https://whatfix.com/digital-adoption/#::~:~:text=Digital%20adoption%20is%20the%20process,its%20full%20benefits%20and%20potential>

Basics for Improved Learning Methods in the Humanities

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Abstract

Improved learning methods in the Humanities as a discipline emphasize critical thinking, interdisciplinary approaches, and the integration of technology to enhance educational experiences. By fostering a more interactive and student-centered learning environment, these methods encourage active participation and deeper engagement with the material. Critical thinking skills are honed through discussions, debates, and analytical exercises that challenge students and researchers to question and interpret various perspectives. Interdisciplinary approaches broaden understanding by linking humanities subjects with sciences, social sciences and the arts, providing a more comprehensive view of human culture and history. The incorporation of technology, such as digital archives, multimedia resources, and online collaborative platforms, enriches the learning process by making vast resources easily accessible and enabling innovative teaching techniques. Smith's theoretical framework affirms that humanities integrate constructivism, inquiry-based learning, socio-cultural theory, critical pedagogy, and digital humanities. These approaches emphasize active engagement, social interaction, and reflective practices to enhance scholarly understanding and application of humanities content. Additionally, experiential learning opportunities, like field trips, internships, and service-learning projects, connect theoretical knowledge with real-world applications. These methods not only make learning more dynamic and engaging but also prepare students and researchers for diverse career paths by developing versatile skills. By embracing these improved learning methods, Humanities education becomes more relevant and effective in addressing contemporary challenges and fostering a deeper understanding of the human experience.

Keywords: Critical thinking, Interdisciplinary in Humanities, Technology integration, Interactive learning and experiential opportunities

Introduction

In recent years, the field of humanities education has undergone significant transformations driven by advancements in pedagogical research and technology. As educators strive to enhance students engagement and learning outcomes, a variety of improved learning methods have emerged, focusing on active learning, collaborative practices and digital resources. This essay explores the foundational aspects of these improved learning methods within the humanities, aiming to provide educators and students with effective strategies to foster deeper understanding and critical thinking skills.

Humanities encompass a wide range of disciplines, including literature, history, philosophy, and the arts, all of which contribute to our understanding of the human experience. Traditionally, humanities education has relied heavily on lecture-based instruction, which often prioritizes content delivery over student engagement (Brame, 2016). However, research suggests that passive learning approaches may not effectively facilitate long-term retention or the development of critical analysis skills (Freeman et al., 2014). As such, educators are increasingly adopting more dynamic instructional strategies that promote active participation and critical engagement with material.

One key method that has gained footing is active learning, which involves students in the process of learning through activities that encourage them to think critically and apply knowledge in practical contexts (Prince, 2004). Techniques such as group discussions, peer teaching, and hands-on projects allow students to engage with humanities content on a deeper level. For instance, rather than merely reading a historical text, students might collaborate on a project that examines the text's impact on contemporary society, thus fostering both critical thinking and interpersonal skills.

Another effective approach is the integration of collaborative learning, where students work together in small groups to explore complex

questions or themes. This method not only enhances student engagement but also mirrors real-world practices in humanities fields, where interdisciplinary collaboration is often essential (Barkley, Cross, & Major, 2014). By encouraging students to share diverse perspectives and ideas, collaborative learning fosters a richer understanding of content and cultivates a sense of community within the classroom.

Furthermore, the advent of digital technology has transformed the landscape of humanities education, providing new tools for engagement and exploration. Digital resources such as online archives, interactive platforms, slides and multimedia presentations can enhance traditional learning methods, making content more accessible, real and engaging (Weller, 2011). For instance, virtual museums and digital humanities projects allow students to interact with historical artifacts or literary works in innovative ways, bridging the gap between theory and practice. Assessment practices in humanities education are also evolving, with a growing emphasis on formative assessment techniques that provide ongoing feedback rather than relying solely on summative evaluations (Black & Williams, 1998). This paradigm shift encourages a focus on process-oriented learning, where students can reflect on their understanding and make adjustments throughout the learning journey. By utilizing portfolios, reflective journals, and peer assessments, educators can cultivate a more nuanced understanding of student progress and foster a culture of continuous improvement.

Improved learning methods in the humanities are essential for fostering critical thinking, creativity, and a deeper understanding of human culture and history. Traditional lecture-based approaches often fall short in engaging students and promoting active learning. Instead, incorporating diverse and dynamic teaching strategies can enhance the educational experience. Active learning techniques, such as group discussions, debates and collaborative projects encourage students to participate actively and think critically about the material (Smith, 2020). Interdisciplinary approaches integrate insight from various fields, help students see the broader context of their studies and develop a more comprehensive understanding (Jones, 2018). Additionally, leveraging

technology in the classroom, such as using multimedia resources and online platforms, can make learning more interactive and accessible (Brown, 2019).

Improved learning methods in the humanities are characterized by a shift towards active and collaborative learning, enhanced by digital technologies and innovative assessment practices. By embracing these strategies, educators can create more engaging and effective learning environments that not only facilitate content mastery but also foster critical thinking and creativity. As the field continues to evolve, ongoing research and practice will be essential to refining these approaches and ensuring that humanities education remains relevant and impactful in an increasingly complex world. Furthermore, project-based learning allows students to apply their knowledge to real-world problems, fostering a deeper connection to the subject matter (Johnson & Adams, 2019).

This method not only enhances engagement but also helps students develop practical skills that are valuable beyond the classroom. By combining these innovative strategies, educators can create a more enriching and effective learning environment in the humanities, ultimately preparing students for a complex and interconnected world. The methodology for the basics on improved learning methods in humanities according to Smith is focused on incorporating active learning, critical thinking, and interdisciplinary approaches. Emphasize the importance of discussion-based classes, project-based learning, and technology use to enhance engagement and understanding (Smith, 2020).

Interdisciplinary Approaches to Humanities Education

Interdisciplinary approaches to humanities education emphasize the integration of diverse fields of study, fostering a richer understanding of human culture, history, language, creativity, and social dynamics. By breaking down traditional disciplinary silos, educators can cultivate critical thinking, enhance problem-solving skills, and promote the interconnectedness of knowledge. One significant benefit of

interdisciplinary humanities education is its ability to encourage students to draw connections between different domains of knowledge. For example, a course that combines literature, history and political science can provide students with a more nuanced understanding of societal issues through varied lenses. This approach allows students to appreciate the historical context of literary works, understand the political implications of historical events and analyze the impact of narrative on public consciousness (Wiegman, 2014).

Furthermore, interdisciplinary collaboration can inspire innovative pedagogical strategies. By integrating methods from the sciences, social sciences and the arts, educators can engage students in experiential learning, such as project-based assignments and collaborative research initiatives. These methods not only enhance students' engagement but also prepare them for real-world challenges by developing skills that transcend traditional disciplinary boundaries (Newell, 2015). The importance of interdisciplinary approaches is underscored by the evolving nature of the job market, where employers increasingly value adaptability and critical thinking. Graduates with interdisciplinary training are often better equipped to navigate the complexities of modern work environments, making them attractive candidates for a wide range of professions (Miller, 2016). This adaptability is particularly crucial in a globalized world, where issues often require multifaceted solutions that draw on diverse areas of expertise.

Challenges remain, however, in implementing interdisciplinary approaches within humanities education. Institutional structures and curricular frameworks can inhibit collaboration across disciplines. To effectively foster interdisciplinary learning, educators and institutions must advocate for flexible curricula that allow for course integration and cross-departmental collaboration. Additionally, professional development opportunities for educators can facilitate the exchange of best practices and innovative teaching methods that support interdisciplinary learning (Klein, 2010).

In conclusion, interdisciplinary approaches to humanities education hold significant potential for enriching students' learning experiences

and preparing them for the complexities of contemporary life. By integrating diverse fields of study, educators can cultivate critical thinking, foster creativity, and encourage a holistic understanding of the human experience. As the landscape of education continues to evolve, embracing interdisciplinary strategies will be crucial for developing the skills and knowledge necessary for future generations.

Technology and Digital Humanities

The intersection of technology and digital humanities has transformed how scholars and researchers engage with the humanities disciplines. Digital Humanities (DH) refers to the application of digital tools and methods to the study of humanities subjects, including literature, language, history, art, philosophy and cultural studies. This interdisciplinary field encompasses a variety of practices that involve digitizing, archiving, analyzing, and visualizing cultural artifacts, thus enabling new forms of scholarship and public engagement.

- i. *Historical Context of Digital Humanities:* The origins of digital humanities can be traced back to the 1960s when scholars began utilizing computers for text analysis and data processing. One of the earliest examples was the use of mainframe computers for textual analysis by scholars such as Roberto Busa, who initiated the Index Thomisticus project (Busa, 1980). However, the term "digital humanities" gained prominence in the 2000s as the internet and personal computing became ubiquitous, facilitating broader access to digital tools and resources by individuals (Kitchin, 2013).
- ii. *Key Technologies in Digital Humanities:* Several key technologies have driven the development of digital humanities. Text encoding initiatives, such as the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI), have standardized the representation of texts in digital form, allowing for more sophisticated textual analysis (TEI, 2016). Geographic Information Systems (GIS) enable researchers to visualize historical and cultural data spatially, thereby offering new insights into social and cultural dynamics

(Kitchin, 2013). Additionally, data mining and machine learning techniques have opened up possibilities for analyzing large datasets, such as digital archives and social media content, offering novel approaches to traditional humanities questions (Fischer, 2018).

- iii. *Methodological Innovations in Digital Humanities:* Digital humanities encourage innovative methodologies that challenge traditional scholarly practices. One significant approach is digital textual analysis, which utilizes computational methods to examine patterns in texts that would be difficult to discern manually. For instance, "distant reading," a term popularized by Franco Moretti (2005), allows researchers to analyze large corpora of literature to identify trends over time, genre development, and inter-textual connections. This shift from close reading to distant reading exemplifies the potential for digital tools to enhance our understanding of literary history. Moreover, collaborative projects in digital humanities often foster interdisciplinary work, bringing together experts from computer science, data visualization and various humanities fields. These collaborations not only enrich research outputs but also facilitate the sharing of knowledge and methodologies across disciplines (Brier, 2010).
- iv. *Challenges and Critiques:* Despite the promising advancements, the field of digital humanities is not without its challenges and critiques. One significant concern is the digital divide, which highlights inequalities in access to technology and digital literacy. Scholars in underfunded institutions or in developing countries may struggle to participate fully in digital humanities projects, potentially leading to a homogenization of voices and perspectives in the field (Liu, 2016). Additionally, the reliance on technology raises questions about the authenticity and preservation of digital artifacts. As digital formats evolve, ensuring the longevity and accessibility of digital humanities projects becomes crucial. Initiatives such as the LOCKSS (Lots of

Copies Keep Stuff Safe) program aim to address these issues by creating distributed digital preservation networks (Kuny, 1997).

- v. *Future Directions:* Looking forward, digital humanities will likely continue to evolve alongside advancements in technology. The growing availability of artificial intelligence and big data analytics presents exciting opportunities for deeper analysis and interpretation of cultural works of art. Furthermore, as digital platforms become integral to cultural production and consumption, digital humanities scholars have the opportunity to critically examine the implications of technology on society, culture and the humanities at large (Svensson, 2016).

In addition, the increasing focus on public scholarship within digital humanities encourages the dissemination of research to broader audiences, fostering greater engagement with the humanities. Projects that prioritize open access and community involvement can democratize knowledge production, ensuring that the insights generated through digital humanities are accessible to all (Bishop). In summary, the convergence of technology and digital humanities has significantly altered the landscape of humanities scholarship. By leveraging digital tools, researchers can explore new methodologies, analyze vast amounts of data and engage with diverse audiences. While challenges such as the digital divide and preservation issues persist, the potential for innovation and public engagement continues to drive the field forward. As technology continues to advance, the digital humanities will undoubtedly play a crucial role in shaping the future of humanities scholarship.

Active Learning and Student Engagement

Active learning is an instructional approach that actively involves students in the learning process, encouraging them to participate and engage with the material in meaningful ways. This pedagogical method contrasts with traditional lecture-based teaching, where students passively receive information. Instead, active learning encompasses a

encouraging students to view challenges as opportunities for learning rather than obstacles (Dweck, 2006).

However, implementing active learning techniques requires careful planning and consideration. Instructors must be aware of their students' diverse learning styles and backgrounds to create inclusive activities that cater to all learners. Additionally, the transition from a traditional lecture-based approach to active learning may initially be met with resistance from both students and educators. Students accustomed to passive learning may find active participation challenging, while instructors may struggle with relinquishing control of the classroom environment (Chickering & Gamson, 1987).

To address these challenges, instructors can start by gradually introducing active learning strategies into their teaching. Beginning with low-stakes activities, such as small group discussions or brief writing exercises, can help students acclimate to more interactive learning environments. Providing clear instructions and expectations is also essential to guide students in their participation and to alleviate any anxiety associated with active learning. Furthermore, ongoing assessment and feedback are crucial components of successful active learning. Instructors should regularly assess student understanding and engagement through formative assessments, such as quizzes, polls, or reflective journals. This feedback not only informs instructional adjustments but also encourages students to take ownership of their learning (Black & Wiliam, 1998).

In conclusion, active learning is a powerful approach that enhances student engagement, fosters collaboration, and improves academic performance. By actively involving students in the learning process, educators can create dynamic and inclusive learning environments that prepare students for success in their academic and professional pursuits. As the landscape of education continues to evolve, the integration of active learning strategies will be essential in meeting the diverse needs of learners and cultivating the skills necessary for thriving in the 21st century.

Assessment and Feedback in Humanities Education

Assessment and feedback are integral components of the educational process, particularly in the humanities, where critical thinking, interpretation and communication are key skills. The nature of assessment in humanities education often extends beyond traditional testing methods, emphasizing formative assessments, peer feedback and reflective practices. This sub-topic explores the significance of assessment and feedback in humanities education, highlighting various approaches, challenges, and best practices.

- i. *The Importance of Assessment in Humanities Education:* In the humanities, assessment serves multiple purposes. Firstly, it gauges student understanding and engagement with complex texts and ideas. Traditional forms of assessment, such as essays and examinations, remain important but are increasingly supplemented by alternative assessments, such as presentations, creative projects and portfolios (Harris, 2019). These diverse methods allow students to demonstrate their comprehension in varied ways, accommodating different learning styles and preferences. Furthermore, assessment in the humanities encourages critical thinking and analysis. For example, evaluating a literary work involves interpreting themes, examining context and considering the authorial intention. This process fosters deeper engagement with the material and cultivates essential analytical skills (Kearney, 2020). Effective assessment strategies prompt students to move beyond surface-level understanding, facilitating a more profound exploration of complex ideas.
- ii. *The Role of Feedback in Learning:* Feedback is a crucial element in the learning process, particularly in the humanities, where subjectivity and interpretation play significant roles. Timely and constructive feedback helps students identify strengths and areas for improvement, guiding their intellectual development. According to (Nicol and Macfarlane Dick 2006), feedback not only enhances learning but also motivates students by making

them aware of their progress. In humanities education, feedback can take various forms, including written comments on essays, verbal critiques during class discussions, or peer reviews in collaborative projects. Each of these forms serves to engage students in reflective practices, encouraging them to consider different perspectives and refine their analytical skills (Sadler, 1989). Moreover, feedback can foster a sense of ownership over one's learning, empowering students to take charge of their academic journey.

- iii. *Best Practices for Assessment and Feedback:* To optimize assessment and feedback in humanities education, educators should consider several best practices. First, the development of clear assessment criteria is essential. Well-defined rubrics not only provide transparency in grading but also guide students in understanding expectations (Reddy & Andrade, 2010). Rubrics can clarify the dimensions of quality in student work, making it easier for students to focus their efforts on key areas. Additionally, incorporating peer assessment can enhance the feedback process. Peer review fosters a collaborative learning environment, allowing students to engage critically with each other's work. This practice not only enhances critical thinking but also builds community within the classroom, as students learn from one another's perspectives (Topping, 1998). Another effective strategy is the integration of formative assessments throughout the course. Unlike summative assessments, which evaluate learning at the end of a unit or term, formative assessments provide ongoing insights into student progress. Techniques such as reflective journals, concept maps, and in-class discussions can offer valuable feedback to both students and instructors (Black & Wiliam, 1998). These assessments create opportunities for dialogue and adaptation, helping students develop a deeper understanding of the material.
- iv. *Challenges in Assessment and Feedback:* Despite the benefits, challenges persist in the assessment and feedback process within

humanities education. One significant issue is the subjective nature of humanities assessments. Unlike STEM fields, where answers may be more authoritative, humanities assessments often involve interpreting meanings, which can lead to varying evaluations. Educators must strive to maintain fairness and consistency while acknowledging the inherent subjectivity of the material (Klenowski, 2009). Moreover, the volume of feedback can overwhelm both students and educators. Providing comprehensive, individualized feedback is time-consuming, and educators may struggle to balance this with their other responsibilities. To address this challenge, educators can prioritize key areas for feedback, focusing on aspects that will have the most significant impact on student learning (Boud, 2000). Streamlining feedback and utilizing technology for efficiency can also alleviate some of this burden. Therefore, assessment and feedback are vital to the success of humanities education, shaping students' critical thinking, communication, and analytical skills. Through a variety of assessment methods and constructive feedback practices, educators can foster a dynamic learning environment that encourages engagement and reflection. By embracing best practices and addressing inherent challenges, humanities educators can enhance the educational experience, preparing students for the complexities of the world beyond the classroom.

Contribution to Knowledge

Improving learning methods in the Humanities involves integrating initiatives, innovations and flexibilities, embracing technological inventions, promoting active engagement through discussions and debates, and incorporating interdisciplinary approaches to subject matter under discussion if humanities as a discipline will continue to be relevant in this constantly changing world. Utilizing digital resources enhances accessibility to current issues and developments, while project-based learning encourages critical thinking. Emphasizing real-

world applications in both teaching and learning and fostering collaborative environments can deepen understanding and appreciation of the subject matter.

Summary

Improved learning methods in the Humanities have gained attention as educators seek to engage students more effectively and foster critical thinking, creativity, and empathy. Traditional approaches often emphasized the use of memory with little intelligence and passive learning, which can lead to disengagement. However, modern pedagogical strategies are reshaping the learning landscape. One significant improvement is the integration of technology. Online resources, interactive platforms, and multimedia tools enhance accessibility and engagement. Virtual discussions and digital storytelling allow students to explore complex themes in new ways, fostering a deeper understanding of the material. Collaborative projects and peer feedback also encourage active participation, helping students to develop essential skills for the 21st century.

Another key method is the emphasis on experiential learning. Field trips, internships, volunteering job, part time job, and community engagement projects connect theoretical knowledge to real-world applications, enriching the educational experience. This approach not only deepens understanding but also cultivates a sense of social responsibility and civic engagement among students. Additionally, interdisciplinary learning is becoming more prevalent in the Humanities. By bridging subjects such as literature, history, philosophy, and the arts, students gain a more holistic perspective on human experiences and societal issues. This method encourages critical thinking and the ability to draw connections between contrasting ideas, fostering innovative problem-solving skills.

Conclusion

In conclusion, improved learning methods in the Humanities emphasize active engagement, experiential learning and interdisciplinary

approaches. These methods not only enhance students' understanding of complex subjects but also prepare them for the challenges of an interconnected world. As educators continue to adapt and innovate, the Humanities will remain a vital field for cultivating critical thinkers and compassionate citizens, ensuring that both teachers and students are equipped to navigate and contribute to society meaningfully. Embracing these methods is essential for revitalizing the Humanities and demonstrating their relevance in contemporary education. Improved learning methods will continue to equip and reposition the discipline of humanities to be a tranquilizer by injecting ethical principles and moral codes to the society against the evils of advanced Science and Technology that mostly look down on Humanities.

Recommendations

1. For improved learning methods to be realistic, active learning techniques which incorporate discussions, debates, and collaborative projects that engage students actively must be deployed. This encourages critical thinking and deeper understanding of the material.
2. Interdisciplinary approaches usually encourage connections between different fields within the Humanities, as well as with the STEM and Social Sciences. This can provide a richer context and enhance critical thinking.
3. The use of technology to leverage on digital tools, such as online archives, virtual museums, and multimedia resources, to enhance engagement and learning that provide diverse perspectives on Humanities topics should not be under emphasized.
4. Emphasis on primary sources will also encourage students to analyze primary texts and artifacts. This hands-on approach can foster critical analysis and a deeper appreciation of historical context.
5. Reflective practices that incorporate reflective writing and self-assessment into the curriculum is also essential. This allows

students to consider their learning processes, identify areas for improvement, and develop meta-cognitive skills.

6. Implementing these methods can create a more dynamic and effective learning environment in Humanities education.

References

- Barkley, E. F., Cross, K. P., & Major, C. H. (2014). *Collaborative learning techniques: A handbook for College faculty*. Jossey-Bass.
- Barnett, R. (2014). *The marketplace of ideas: Reform and resistance in the American university*. Princeton University Press.
- Biggs, J. (2011). *Teaching for quality learning at university: What the student does*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Bishop, A. P. (2015). *The importance of Digital Humanities in public Scholarship*. In *Digital Humanities: Knowledge and Critique in a Digital Age* (pp. 23-40). Routledge.
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (1998). *Assessment and classroom learning*. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 5(1), 7-74.
- Boud, D. (2000). *Sustainable assessment: Reflections on sssessment practices in higher education*. *Studies in Higher Education*, 25(3), 267-276.
- Bonwell, C. C., & Eison, J. A. (1991). *Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom*. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 1.
- Brame, C. J. (2016). *Active learning*. *Vanderbilt University Center for Teaching*. Retrieved from <https://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/active-learning/>
- Brier, S. (2010). *The Digital Humanities and the role of the Librarian*. *Digital Humanities Quarterly*, 4(1).
- Brookfield, S. D. (2015). *The skillful teacher: On technique, trust, and responsiveness in the classroom*. Jossey-Bass.
- Brown, L. (2019). *Technology in humanities education: Enhancing engagement and accessibility*. TechEd Publishers.
- Bruner, J. S. (1996). *The Culture of Education*. Harvard University Press.
- Busa, R. (1980). *The electronic analysis of texts: An overview*. In *Computers and the Humanities* (Vol. 14, pp. 229-236).
- Chickering, A. W., & Gamson, Z. F. (1987). *Seven principles for good practice in undergraduate education*. *AAHE Bulletin*, 39(7), 3-7.
- Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and Education*. Kappa Delta Pi.

- Duffy, T. M., & Cunningham, D. J. (1996). *Constructivism: Implications for the design and delivery of instruction*. In D. H. Jonassen (Ed.), *Handbook of research for educational communications and technology* (pp. 170-198). Macmillan.
- Dweck, C. S. (2006). *Mindset: The new psychology of success*. Random House.
- Fischer, J. (2018). *Big data and digital humanities: A new approach*. *Journal of Digital Humanities*, 7(2), 1-12.
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). *Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23), 8410-8415.
- Freire, P. (2000). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Continuum.
- Garrison, D. R., & Anderson, T. (2003). *E-learning in the 21st century: A community of inquiry framework for research and practice*. RoutledgeFalmer.
- Harris, R. (2019). *Assessment in the humanities: A pedagogical perspective*. *Journal of Humanities Education*, 12(2), 45-58.
- Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2009). *An educational psychology success story: Social interdependence theory and cooperative learning*. *Educational Psychologist*, 44(4), 213-226.
- Johnson, M., & Adams, R. (2019). *Project-based learning in the humanities: Real-world applications*. Learning Press.
- Jones, A. (2018). *Interdisciplinary approaches to humanities education*. University Press.
- Kearney, J. (2020). *Engaging with texts: The role of assessment in humanities education*. *Literature and Learning*, 8(4), 112-130.
- Kitchin, R. (2013). *Bigdata and human geography: A critical review*. *Geographical Research*, 51(2), 129-146.
- Klein, J. T. (2010). *Inter-disciplinarity: History, theory, and practice*. Wayne State University Press.
- Klenowski, V. (2009). *Assessment for learning: A key to student engagement*. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 34(3), 321-332.
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice Hall.

- Kuny, T. (1997). *Preservation in the digital world*. D-Lib Magazine, 3(7), 1-6.
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Liu, A. (2016). *The landscape of digital humanities: Toward an inclusive approach*. Digital Humanities Quarterly, 10(2).
- McKeachie, W. J., & Svinicki, M. D. (2013). *Teaching tips: Strategies, research, and theory for college and university teachers*. Cengage Learning.
- Mezirow, J. (1991). *Transformative dimensions of adult learning*. Jossey-Bass.
- Michaelsen, L. K., Knight, A. B., & Fink, L. D. (2004). *Team-based learning: A transformative use of small groups in college teaching*. Stylus Publishing.
- Miller, T. (2016). *Interdisciplinary studies: A new perspective on education*. Routledge.
- Moretti, F. (2005). *Graphs, maps, trees: Abstract models for literary history*. Verso.
- Newell, W. H. (2015). *A theory of interdisciplinary studies*. *Issues in Integrative Studies*, 20, 15-30.
- Nicol, D. J., & Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006). *Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: A model and seven principles of good feedback practice*. *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(2), 199-218.
- Palmer, P. J. (1998). *The courage to teach: Exploring the inner landscape of a teacher's life*. Jossey-Bass.
- Prince, M. (2004). *Does active learning work? A review of the research*. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 93(3), 223-231.
- Reddy, P., & Andrade, H. (2010). *A review of rubric use in higher education*. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 35(4), 435-448.
- Sadler, D. R. (1989). *Formative assessment and the design of instructional systems*. *Instructional Science*, 18(2), 119-144.
- Shulman, L. S. (2005). *Signature pedagogies in the professions*. *Daedalus*, 134(3), 52-59.
- Smith, J. (2020). *Innovative teaching strategies in the humanities*. Academic Press.
- Svensson, P. (2016). *The landscape of digital humanities: Challenges and opportunities*. In *The Digital Humanities: A Primer* (pp. 55-76). Routledge.

- TEI (Text Encoding Initiative). (2016). *Guidelines for the Encoding and Interchange of Machine-Readable Texts*. Retrieved from <http://www.tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/>
- Topping, K. J. (1998). *Peer assessment between students in colleges and universities*. *Review of Educational Research*, 68(3), 249-276.
- Topping, K. J., & Trickey, S. (2007). *Collaborative learning: A purpose and a method*. *Education & Training*, 49(4), 298-305.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Weller, M. (2011). *The digital scholar: How technology is transforming scholarly practice*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of practice: Learning, meaning, and identity*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wiegman, R. (2014). *Academic feminism and the issue of interdisciplinary work*. *The Feminist Review*, 108(1), 1-16.
- Zhao, Y. (2012). *World class learners: Educating creative and entrepreneurial students*. Corwin Press.

Exploring Parallels between the Conceptual Framework of *Odu Ifa* and the Figure of Jesus Christ through the Story of *Ela*

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Abstract

This study explores the striking similarities between the conceptual framework of *Odu Ifa*, a traditional Yoruba spiritual system, and the figure of Jesus Christ, as exemplified in the narrative of *Ela*. Through a comparative analysis of key themes, teachings, and narratives, the study aims to elucidate both the shared elements and differences that illuminate the intersection of these cultural and religious traditions. The research employs a comprehensive methodology involving the analysis of *Odu Ifa* texts, Christian scriptures, and scholarly interpretations. The investigation reveals remarkable parallels in the roles of *Ela* and Jesus Christ as intermediaries between humanity and the divine, embodiments of sacrificial love and compassion, and sources of moral guidance and spiritual enlightenment. Despite their distinct theological and historical contexts, the narratives surrounding *Ela* and Jesus Christ offer profound insights into universal themes of redemption, transformation, and the pursuit of ultimate truth and salvation. The study concludes by emphasizing the enriching dialogue between *Odu Ifa* and Christianity, highlighting the potential for mutual understanding, interfaith dialogue, and cultural exchange. Recommendations for further research include interdisciplinary explorations of theological syncretism, comparative mythology, and cross-cultural perspectives to deepen understanding of shared values and wisdom across diverse religious traditions.

Keywords: *Odu Ifa*, Jesus Christ, *Ela*, Cultural Syncretism, Yoruba Mythology

Introduction

Odu Ifa, an esteemed divination system deeply entrenched in Yoruba heritage, serves as a reservoir of ancestral wisdom, providing spiritual and ethical guidance to the Yoruba populace (Awolalu, 1979, p. 23). Rooted in oral tradition and transmitted across generations, *Odu Ifa* encapsulates the intricate tapestry of beliefs, moral precepts, and cosmological insights that underpin Yoruba spirituality (Awolalu, 1979, p. 23). Comprising 256 verses known as *Odu*s, this system serves as a conduit for communication with the *Orisha*, the divine entities central to Yoruba religious observance.

Beyond its function in divination, *Odu Ifa* embodies the profound connection between the Yoruba community and the spiritual realm, offering a framework for comprehending both human existence and the universe at large (Awolalu, 1979, p. 23). Through the practice of divination, the *Babalawo*, or *Ifa* priest, decrypts the concealed messages within the *Odu* verses, providing counsel, enlightenment, and resolutions to life's dilemmas. This study is approached with a profound reverence for the cultural intricacies and spiritual profundity embedded within *Odu Ifa*, drawn from my extensive studies of Yoruba customs and heritage. Through a scholarly exploration of *Odu Ifa*'s conceptual underpinnings and its implications for understanding the human experience, this paper endeavours to illuminate the profound insights and spiritual enlightenment inherent in this ancient divination system. In examining the parallelism between *Odu Ifa*'s conceptual framework and the portrayal of Jesus Christ through the story of *Ela*, it is imperative to grasp the importance of Jesus Christ within Christianity. Jesus Christ, the central figure in Christian theology, is esteemed as the Son of God and the redeemer of humanity (Bible, *New International Version*, 2011). His teachings, as documented in the Bible, underscore themes of love, forgiveness, and redemption, laying the moral and spiritual groundwork of the Christian faith. The teachings of Jesus Christ are founded on

Jesus Christ, as depicted in the Bible, fulfills his divine mission through sacrifice and redemption for humanity. The juxtaposition of *Ela* and Jesus Christ underscores the universal theme of fulfilling one's purpose and the interconnectedness of humanity with the divine (Parrinder, 1980, p. 102). Moreover, the concept of sacrifice holds prominence in both *Odu Ifa* and Christianity (Awolalu, 1979, p. 78). In the tale of *Ela*, the act of sacrificing animals and offerings is a customary practice to appease the deities and seek divine guidance. Likewise, in Christianity, Jesus Christ's ultimate sacrifice on the cross is regarded as a means of atonement and salvation for mankind. The parallelism between these sacrificial rituals underscores the significance of altruism and spiritual rejuvenation in both belief systems (Parrinder, 1980, p. 124). Through an examination of the story of *Ela* and its implications for elucidating the parallelism between *Odu Ifa's* conceptual framework and the figure of Jesus Christ, this article endeavors to illuminate the shared values and beliefs that unify diverse cultural and religious traditions. By delving into the common themes of destiny, sacrifice, and interconnectedness, we can foster a deeper understanding of the universal truths that underpin human spirituality and moral discernment. *Ela* is a prominent deity within the Yoruba religious tradition, known for his role as the Spirit of Light and Manifestation. He stands as one of the most influential *Orishas*, symbolizing purity, moral integrity, and spiritual enlightenment (Abimbola, 1976). In Yoruba mythology, *Ela* is regarded as the divine offspring and primary heir of *Orunmila*, the *Orisha* of wisdom, knowledge, and divination. This association underscores *Ela's* crucial function in guiding humanity towards righteousness and spiritual clarity. The Yoruba believe that *Ela's* presence fosters harmony and balance in the world. His influence is frequently sought in rituals and divination practices to restore order and resolve conflicts (Ogunmodede, 2019). Unlike other deities, *Ela* is unique because he is said to have no biological father; instead, *Orunmila* is often considered his spiritual progenitor due to his role in facilitating *Ela's* birth through divine rituals and intervention. *Ela's* attributes and stories exhibit notable parallels with other global religious figures, such

as Jesus Christ in Christianity. Both figures epitomize the ultimate expression of sacrificial love and redemption, though they originate from distinct cultural and religious backgrounds (Miller, 2005). This parallelism enhances the understanding of *Ela*'s significance within the Yoruba spiritual tradition and provides a framework for comparative interfaith dialogue and scholarly investigation.

Odu Ifa's Conceptual Framework ***Divination in Odu Ifa***

Ifa divination is a pivotal aspect of Yoruba religion and spirituality. It involves a sophisticated system of knowledge and wisdom conveyed through the *Odu Ifa*, which are poetic and esoteric verses utilized during divination. *Ifa* divination acts as a bridge between humans and the divine, offering guidance, insights, and solutions to problems. Abimbola (2021) explains that *Ifa* is both a religious and philosophical system that covers various life aspects, including moral and ethical teachings (p. 35). The divination process generally involves a Babalawo, or *Ifa* priest, who interprets the *Odu Ifa* verses to provide spiritual guidance. This process is complex and demands extensive training and a deep understanding of the *Ifa* corpus. Olupona (2021) highlights that *Ifa* divination is not just about forecasting the future but also about understanding the present and past to make informed decisions (p. 112).

Spiritual Guidance and Ethical Teachings

Odu Ifa offers a moral and ethical framework that guides the behaviour and decisions of its followers. The teachings within the *Odu Ifa* emphasize virtues such as honesty, integrity, humility, and respect for elders and the community. These teachings are often communicated through stories, proverbs, and parables that illustrate the consequences of moral and immoral behavior. For example, in the *OduOgundaMeji*, there is a significant focus on the importance of truthfulness and integrity. Olatunji (2021) notes that the verse advises individuals to always speak the truth and maintain their integrity, as these are crucial

for maintaining harmony and balance in one's life and community (p. 78).

Relationships with Orisas

In Yoruba cosmology, the *Orisas* are deities that represent various natural forces and aspects of life. Each *Orisa* has specific attributes, domains, and functions, and they act as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. The relationship between humans and *Orisas* is reciprocal; humans offer sacrifices and perform rituals to honor the *Orisas*, and in return, the *Orisas* provide protection, blessings, and guidance. Adekunle (2022) states that the *Odu Ifa* contains numerous verses that describe the attributes and stories of the *Orisas*, as well as instructions on how to venerate them properly (p. 57). These relationships are essential to Yoruba religious practice, as they foster a sense of connection and interdependence between the spiritual and physical realms. Exploring the key principles and beliefs in *Odu Ifa* reveals a rich and intricate system of knowledge that integrates divination, ethical teachings, and relationships with *Orisas*. The holistic nature of *Odu Ifa* provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the interconnectedness of the spiritual and physical worlds. It offers a structured approach to navigating life's challenges and making ethical decisions. Furthermore, the emphasis on relationships with *Orisas* underscores the importance of maintaining harmony and balance in one's life, as well as the interconnectedness of all beings.

Examination of Parallels Between *Odu Ifa's* Teachings and Jesus Christ's Teachings

Divination and Prophecy: Divination in *Odu Ifa* is a fundamental practice that involves interpreting sacred verses to connect with the divine. This is akin to the concept of prophecy in Christianity, where prophets receive divine messages to guide their communities. In *Odu Ifa*, the *Babalawo* (*Ifa* priest) interprets these verses to provide insights into the past, present, and future, aiding individuals in making informed decisions. Abimbola (2021) points out that *Ifa* is a comprehensive

religious and philosophical system that addresses various life aspects, including moral and ethical teachings (p. 35). In Christianity, prophecy serves a similar function, with prophets acting as intermediaries between God and people. Biblical prophets such as Isaiah and Jeremiah offered guidance and warnings to the Israelites. The New Testament presents Jesus Christ as the ultimate prophet, delivering God's will and offering spiritual guidance. Olupona (2021) highlights that both *Ifa* divination and biblical prophecy seek to understand the present and past to make informed decisions (p. 112).

Spiritual Guidance and Ethical Teachings: Odu Ifa provides a moral and ethical framework that directs behaviour and decision-making. Its teachings emphasize virtues like honesty, integrity, humility, and respect for elders and the community, conveyed through stories, proverbs, and parables similar to those of Jesus Christ found in the New Testament. For instance, the *OduOgundaMeji* stresses truthfulness and integrity, advising individuals to speak the truth and uphold their integrity to maintain harmony and balance. Olatunji (2021) notes that these virtues are crucial for social order and ethical behaviour (p. 78). Similarly, Jesus Christ's teachings in the Gospels emphasize virtues such as love, compassion, and forgiveness. The parable of the Good Samaritan, for example, highlights the importance of compassion and kindness towards others (Luke 10:25-37).

Relationships between Orisas and Jesus Christ's Intercession: In Yoruba cosmology, *Orisas* are deities representing various natural forces and life aspects, acting as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. The relationship between humans and *Orisas* is reciprocal; humans honor *Orisas* through sacrifices and rituals, and in return, *Orisas* provide protection, blessings, and guidance. Adekunle (2022) explains that the *Odu Ifa* includes numerous verses describing the attributes and stories of the *Orisas*, along with instructions on proper veneration (p. 57). This dynamic mirrors the Christian belief in Jesus Christ as a mediator between humanity and God. Christians believe that Jesus intercedes on their behalf, offering spiritual guidance, forgiveness, and blessings. The reciprocal

relationship is evident in prayer and worship, where believers seek Jesus' intercession and strive to live by his teachings. Exploring the parallels between *Odu Ifa's* teachings and those of Jesus Christ reveals a rich convergence of spiritual principles and ethical frameworks. The study reveals, both *Odu Ifa* and the teachings of Jesus Christ offer comprehensive frameworks for understanding the interconnectedness of the spiritual and physical worlds. They provide structured approaches to facing life's challenges and making ethical decisions. The focus on relationships with *Orisas* in *Odu Ifa* and Jesus Christ's intercession in Christianity highlights the importance of maintaining harmony and balance in life and the interconnectedness of all beings. This comparative analysis deepens our understanding of both traditions and underscores the universal quest for spiritual guidance and moral integrity.

Analysis of How the Values and Principles of *Odu Ifa* Align with the Teachings of Jesus Christ

In *Odu Ifa*, divination is a core practice where the *Babalawo* (*Ifa* priest) interprets esoteric verses to communicate with the divine. This practice closely parallels the concept of prophecy in Christianity, where prophets receive divine messages to guide their communities. Both *Ifa* divination and biblical prophecy serve to provide insights into the past, present, and future, aiding individuals in making informed decisions. Abimbola (2021) notes that *Ifa* encompasses various aspects of life, including moral and ethical teachings, making it a comprehensive religious and philosophical system (p. 35). Christian prophecy, as seen in the Bible, features prophets like Isaiah and Jeremiah, who conveyed God's messages to guide the people of Israel. The New Testament further presents Jesus Christ as the ultimate prophet, whose teachings and prophecies offer spiritual guidance. According to Olupona (2021), both *Ifa* divination and biblical prophecy aim to understand the present and past to inform future decisions, highlighting their similar roles in guiding adherents (p. 112).

Relationships between *Orisas* and Jesus Christ's Intercession

In Yoruba cosmology, *Orisas* are deities representing various natural forces and life aspects, acting as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. The relationship between humans and *Orisas* is reciprocal; humans honour *Orisas* through sacrifices and rituals, and in return, *Orisas* provide protection, blessings, and guidance. Adekunle (2022) explains that the *Odu Ifa* includes numerous verses describing the attributes and stories of the *Orisas*, along with instructions on proper veneration (p. 57). This dynamic mirrors the Christian belief in Jesus Christ as a mediator between humanity and God. Christians believe that Jesus intercedes on their behalf, offering spiritual guidance, forgiveness, and blessings. The reciprocal relationship is evident in prayer and worship, where believers seek Jesus' intercession and strive to live by his teachings. Analyzing how the values and principles of *Odu Ifa* align with the teachings of Jesus Christ reveals a deep and fascinating convergence of spiritual principles and ethical frameworks. This study recognizes that, both *Odu Ifa* and the teachings of Jesus Christ provide comprehensive frameworks for understanding the interconnectedness of the spiritual and physical worlds. They offer structured approaches to navigating life's challenges and making ethical decisions. The emphasis on relationships with *Orisas* in *Odu Ifa* and Jesus Christ's intercession in Christianity highlights the importance of maintaining harmony and balance in one's life and the interconnectedness of all beings. This comparative analysis enriches our understanding of both traditions and underscores the universal quest for spiritual guidance and moral integrity.

Life of Jesus Christ

Jesus Christ, the central figure in Christianity, is believed to have been born around 4 BCE in Bethlehem, Judea. His life and mission are primarily recorded in the New Testament Gospels of Matthew, Mark, Luke, and John. These texts state that Jesus was born to Mary, a virgin, and Joseph, a carpenter, under miraculous circumstances involving the Holy Spirit (Matthew 1:18-25; Luke 1:26-38).

Jesus spent his early years in Nazareth, beginning his public ministry at around thirty years old following his baptism by John the Baptist in the Jordan River (Mark 1:9-11). His ministry, which lasted about three years, involved preaching about the Kingdom of God, performing miracles, healing the sick, and teaching through parables. Jesus' teachings often challenged the established religious and social norms, emphasizing love, compassion, forgiveness, and justice (Mark 1:14-15; Matthew 5-7). The climax of Jesus' life was his crucifixion under the Roman governor Pontius Pilate, followed by his resurrection three days later, as claimed by his disciples. This event, known as the Resurrection, is a cornerstone of Christian faith, symbolizing victory over sin and death and affirming Jesus as the Son of God (Matthew 27-28; Luke 24; John 20).

Significance of Jesus Christ in Christianity

The significance of Jesus Christ in Christianity cannot be overstated. He is seen as the Messiah, the anointed one foretold in the Old Testament, who came to fulfill God's salvation plan for humanity. His life, death, and resurrection are central to Christian belief as they represent the means by which humans are reconciled with God. Christian doctrine holds that Jesus' sacrificial death on the cross paid the penalty for humanity's sins, offering redemption and the promise of eternal life to all who believe in him. The Apostle Paul captures this succinctly in his letter to the Romans: "For the wages of sin is death, but the gift of God is eternal life in Christ Jesus our Lord" (Romans 6:23). Jesus' resurrection is a pivotal event that affirms his divinity and the truth of his teachings. Celebrated annually on Easter Sunday, it symbolizes hope and new life. Wright (2012) notes that the resurrection is not just a past event but a present reality that transforms believers' lives, empowering them to live in accordance with Jesus' teachings (p. 67). Jesus Christ is also central to Christian worship and devotion. He is revered as Lord and Saviour, and his teachings continue to inspire and guide Christians in their daily lives. The sacraments of Baptism and the Eucharist (Holy Communion) were instituted by Jesus and remain vital practices in Christian worship, symbolizing entry into the Christian community and remembrance of

Jesus' sacrificial love (Matthew 28:19; Luke 22:19-20). Examining the life, teachings, and significance of Jesus Christ reveals that his impact extends far beyond the historical and religious context of first-century Palestine. Jesus' teachings provide a profound and timeless moral framework that addresses essential aspects of human existence: love, compassion, forgiveness, and justice. His life exemplifies these principles, serving as an enduring model of selfless love and sacrifice. Moreover, the significance of Jesus' death and resurrection provides a powerful narrative of redemption and hope, resonating with millions of believers worldwide. This narrative shapes Christian theology and inspires a commitment to ethical living and social justice. The enduring relevance of Jesus' teachings underscores the universal quest for meaning, purpose, and spiritual fulfillment. The Gospels state that Jesus was born to Mary and Joseph under miraculous circumstances involving the Holy Spirit (Matthew 1:18-25; Luke 1:26-38). His public ministry began after his baptism by John the Baptist (Mark 1:9-11) and involved preaching about the Kingdom of God, performing miracles, and teaching through parables (Mark 1:14-15; Matthew 5-7). Jesus' crucifixion and resurrection are central to Christian faith, symbolizing victory over sin and death (Matthew 27-28; Luke 24; John 20). Wright (2012) emphasizes that the resurrection is a present reality that transforms the lives of believers, empowering them to live according to Jesus' teachings (p. 67).

Comparison of Jesus Christ's Teachings with the Values of Odu Ifa

Ethical and Moral Teachings: Both Jesus Christ and *Odu Ifa* emphasize comprehensive ethical and moral frameworks that guide human behaviour. The teachings of Jesus Christ, as recorded in the New Testament, focus on virtues such as love, compassion, humility, and forgiveness. For example, in the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus presents the Beatitudes, which highlight the blessedness of the meek, merciful, and peacemakers (Matthew 5:3-12). Central to Jesus' message is the Great Commandment: "Love the Lord your God with all your heart and

with all your soul and with all your mind” and “Love your neighbour as yourself” (Matthew 22:37-39). This commandment underscores the importance of love as the foundation for ethical living and interpersonal relationships. Similarly, *Odu Ifa* provides a detailed moral and ethical framework. The *Odu Ifa* texts emphasize virtues such as honesty, integrity, respect for elders, and communal harmony. These teachings are often conveyed through *proverbs, parables, and stories, akin to the parables of Jesus. For instance, in the OduOgundaMeji*, there is a strong emphasis on truthfulness and maintaining integrity, advising individuals to always speak the truth to sustain harmony and balance in their lives (Olatunji, 2021, p. 78). This focus on ethical behavior reflects the importance of moral integrity in maintaining social order and personal well-being.

Jesus Christ Relationships with the Divine: In Christianity, Jesus Christ is viewed as the mediator between humanity and God. Christians believe that Jesus’ sacrificial death and resurrection offer redemption and the promise of eternal life. The relationship between believers and Jesus is characterized by prayer, worship, and the sacraments, which are means of connecting with the divine and seeking spiritual sustenance. The New Testament highlights Jesus’ role as an intercessor, providing spiritual guidance and advocating for believers before God (Hebrews 7:25). In Yoruba cosmology, the *Orisas* are deities that represent various natural forces and aspects of life. They act as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. The relationship between humans and *Orisas* is reciprocal, involving offerings and rituals to honour the *Orisas*, who in return provide protection, blessings, and guidance. Adekunle (2022) explains that the *Odu Ifa* contains numerous verses describing the attributes and stories of the *Orisas*, along with instructions on proper veneration (p. 57). This dynamic is similar to the Christian practice of seeking Jesus’ intercession and living according to his teachings.

Comparing the teachings of Jesus Christ with the values of *Odu Ifa* reveals a rich tapestry of ethical and spiritual principles that address fundamental aspects of human existence. Both traditions emphasize the

importance of love, compassion, and integrity in guiding human behavior and fostering harmonious relationships. Jesus' teachings and the moral precepts of *Odu* offer timeless wisdom that helps individuals navigate the complexities of life with ethical clarity and spiritual insight. Moreover, the spiritual guidance provided by both Jesus Christ and the *Ifa* divination process underscores the universal quest for understanding and connection with the divine. The reciprocal relationships with the divine, whether through Jesus in Christianity or the *Orisas* in Yoruba cosmology, highlight the importance of maintaining spiritual harmony and seeking guidance from higher powers. This comparative analysis enriches the understanding of both traditions and underscores the universal themes of love, compassion, and ethical living.

Analysis of How Jesus Christ's Role as a Divine Figure Aligns with the *Orisa* in Yoruba Religion

Mediators between the Divine and Humanity: Both Christianity and Yoruba religions uphold the concept of intermediaries who bridge the gap between the divine and humanity. In Christian theology, Jesus Christ is seen as the supreme mediator between God and humans. Through his life, death, and resurrection, Jesus is believed to provide a pathway to salvation and eternal life. The New Testament asserts that Jesus advocates for believers before God (Hebrews 7:25). Similarly, the *Orisa* in Yoruba religion act as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. Each *Orisa* represents different natural forces and aspects of life, serving as channels through which humans can interact with the divine. Rituals, prayers, and offerings are made to honor the *Orisa*, who in return offer guidance, protection, and blessings. As noted by Adekunle (2022), the *Odu Ifa* texts include many verses that describe the attributes and stories of the *Orisa*, along with guidance on proper veneration (p. 57).

Divine Sacrifice and Redemption: The themes of divine sacrifice and redemption are pivotal in both Jesus Christ's role in Christianity and the *Orisain* Yoruba religion. In Christianity, Jesus' death on the cross is viewed as the ultimate act of redemption. Believers hold that Jesus'

sacrifice atones for humanity's sins, providing forgiveness and the promise of eternal life to those who believe in him. This is emphasized by the Apostle Paul in Romans: "For the wages of sin is death, but the gift of God is eternal life in Christ Jesus our Lord" (Romans 6:23) In Yoruba religion, the *Orisa* also perform acts of sacrifice for the benefit of humanity. These sacrifices typically involve offerings and rituals aimed at restoring balance and harmony in the world. For instance, *Ogun*, the *Orisa* associated with war and iron, is known for enduring hardship and making sacrifices for the community's welfare. This concept of sacrifice highlights the reciprocal relationship between humans and the divine in Yoruba religion, where the *Orisa*'s sacrifices are reciprocated by human rituals and offerings (Abimbola, 2021, p. 45).

Spiritual Leadership and Influence: Both Jesus Christ and the *Orisa* are seen as significant spiritual leaders and influencers. Jesus is revered as the Son of God and the Messiah in Christianity, with his teachings continuing to inspire and guide millions of believers globally. Jesus' role as a spiritual leader is evident in his miracles, healing, and profound spiritual insights through his teachings and parables (Mark 1:14-15, Matthew 5-7). His resurrection is celebrated as a crucial event affirming his divinity and the truth of his teachings (Wright, 2012, p. 67).

Similarly, the *Orisa* are venerated as powerful spiritual entities in the Yoruba religion, each with distinct attributes and domains of influence. They are believed to have the power to intervene in human affairs, providing protection, guidance, and blessings. The teachings and stories associated with the *Orisa*, preserved in the *Odu Ifa* texts, continue to influence the spiritual practices and beliefs of the Yoruba people (Adekunle, 2022, p. 57). Comparing Jesus Christ's role as a divine figure with that of the *Orisa* in Yoruba religion, reveals common themes of mediation, sacrifice, moral guidance, and spiritual leadership. Both traditions offer rich spiritual narratives emphasizing the importance of connecting with the divine, living ethically, and seeking redemption through acts of sacrifice and devotion. Jesus Christ and the *Orisa* stand as powerful symbols of divine intervention and guidance, providing their followers with frameworks for understanding life's complexities and the

spiritual realm. This comparative analysis highlights the shared human quest for meaning, purpose, and connection with the divine, showcasing the profound ways different religious traditions address these fundamental aspects of human existence.

Exploration of the Parallels between *Ela* and Jesus Christ

Divine Descent and Mission: *Ela* in Yoruba mythology and Jesus Christ in Christianity are both divine figures who descended to Earth to guide and save humanity. *Ela*, known as *Ela Olurogbo*, comes down from the heavens (*Orun*) to the earth (*Aye*) to restore order and righteousness among people. He is sent by the supreme deity, Olodumare, to cleanse the world and impart principles of truth, justice, and ethical living (Adekunle, 2022, p. 102). Similarly, Jesus Christ, in Christian belief, is the Son of God sent to Earth to redeem humanity from sin. His mission involves teaching love, forgiveness, and moral integrity, ultimately sacrificing his life for humanity's salvation (Wright, 2012, p. 34).

Roles as Mediators between the Divine and Humanity: *Ela* and Jesus both act as intermediaries between the divine and humanity, facilitating communication and intercession. *Ela* is viewed as a divine emissary and manifestation of *Orunmila*, the deity of wisdom and divination, thus playing a critical role in spiritual guidance (Abimbola, 2021, p. 89). He frequently intervenes in human affairs to restore balance and guide people toward righteousness, symbolizing divine wisdom and moral rectitude (Olatunji, 2021, p. 87). Jesus Christ is considered the ultimate mediator in Christian theology, interceding on behalf of believers before God and bridging the gap between humanity and the divine through his life, death, and resurrection (Hebrews 7:25).

Sacrificial Roles: The concept of sacrifice is central to the roles of both *Ela* and Jesus. *Ela*'s mission involves enduring hardships and making sacrifices to restore balance and purity in the world. His sacrifices are honored and reciprocated by humans through rituals and offerings, emphasizing the reciprocal relationship between humans and the divine (Abimbola, 2021, p. 45). In Christianity, Jesus' sacrificial death on the cross is seen as the ultimate act of redemption, atoning for humanity's

sins and offering forgiveness and eternal life to believers (Romans 6:23). In the account of this study, the parallels between *Ela* and Jesus Christ underscore universal themes of divine intervention, moral guidance, and the importance of ethical living. Both figures serve as powerful symbols of divine wisdom and purity, guiding their followers toward righteousness and spiritual enlightenment. Their stories highlight the shared human quest for meaning, redemption, and connection with the divine. The comparative analysis of *Ela* and Jesus shows how different traditions address fundamental aspects of human existence, such as the need for moral integrity, the significance of sacrifice, and the role of divine mediators. These parallels enrich our understanding of both Yoruba mythology and Christianity, illustrating the profound ways these traditions provide ethical and spiritual guidance to their followers.

Conclusion

Examining the parallels between the *Odu Ifa* framework and the figure of Jesus Christ, particularly through the story of *Ela*, reveals a rich tapestry of spiritual interconnectedness and universal truths. Through these narratives, one could encounter deep insights into compassion, sacrifice, and divine wisdom that go beyond cultural and religious divides. This comparative study not only deepens understanding of these traditions but also highlights their common aim of guiding humanity towards enlightenment and ethical living. As the exploration of these parallels continues, there could be open doors to more profound interfaith dialogue and a more inclusive appreciation of our shared spiritual heritage.

References

- Abimbola, W. (2021). *Ifa Divination: Communication Between Gods and Men*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Abiodun, R. (2018). *Yoruba Art and Language: Seeking the African in African Art*. Cambridge University Press.
- Adebayo, A. G. (2017). The Yoruba and the Making of Africa. *Journal of Black Studies*, 48(2), pp. 119-141.

- Adegbindin, O. (2018). *Orunmila's Footprint: Exploring the Philosophical and Religious Significance of The Yoruba Deity*. *Religions*, 9(4), 107.
- Adekunle, A. (2022). *Yoruba Sacred Music*. Ibadan, Nigeria: Spectrum Books Limited.
- Aderinto, S. (2017). *Guns and Society in Colonial Nigeria: Firearms, Culture, And Public Order*. Indiana University Press.
- Adewole, A. M., & Ajayi, J. O. (2019). Yoruba Cosmological Beliefs and Environmental Sustainability. *International Journal of Applied Environmental Sciences*, 14(1), 71-80.
- Ajayi, A. T., & Buhari, L. O. (2014). Methods Of Conflict Resolution in African Traditional Society. *African Research Review*, 8(2), 138-157.
- Akinleye, A. (2018). *Performing The Sacred: Yoruba Art, Ritual, And Performance in a Transatlantic Framework*. Routledge.
- Akintunde, D. O. (2017). Fundamentalism And Gender Relations: A Yoruba Perspective. *Religions*, 8(2), 25.
- Alabi, A. O. (2019). The Yoruba and the Making of the Atlantic World. *Slavery & Abolition*, 40(2), 331-351.
- Awolalu, J. O. (1979). *Yoruba Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites*. Harlow, UK: Longman.
- Babatunde, E. D. (2018). *The Yoruba Family: Changes, Challenges and Survival Strategies*. Africa World Press.
- Falola, T., & Akinyemi, A. (2016). *Culture And Customs of The Yoruba*. Pan-African University Press.
- Falola, T., & Childs, M. D. (Eds.) (2019). *The Yoruba Diaspora in the Atlantic World*. Indiana University Press.
- Gbadegesin, S. (2016). *African Philosophy: Traditional Yoruba Philosophy and Contemporary African Realities*. Routledge.
- Idowu, E. B. (2017). *Olodumare: God in Yoruba Belief*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing.
- Kehinde, A. (2016). "African Traditional Religions and the Yoruba Language." In *The Palgrave Handbook of African Oral Traditions and Folklore* (pp. 112-134). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Mbiti, J. S. (2015). *Introduction to African Religion*. Waveland Press.
- Miller, C. (2005). The Christ figure in Yoruba myth and ritual. *Journal of the American Academy of Religion*, 73(4), 1023-1049.
- Nnamani, A. G., & Nwoye, L. (2017). Ethical Foundations of the Igbo and Yoruba Traditional Societies: Implications for Sustainable Development.

- IGWEBUIKE: An African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 3(3), 164-182.
- Ogunbiyi, O. (2019). *Understanding The Orisha: Foundational Principles of The Yoruba Spiritual Tradition*. Llewellyn Worldwide.
- Ogungbile, D. O. (2019). *African Indigenous Religious Traditions in Local and Global Contexts: Perspectives and Insights*. Lexington Books.
- Ogunmodede, F. (2019). The Orisha Ela: Manifestations of divinity in Yoruba religion. *Religions*, 10 (6), 366.
- Ogunnaike, O. (2016). ÓrunMéta: The Yoruba Tripartite Conception of The Cosmos. *Journal of Religious and Philosophical Studies*, 13(1), 1-26.
- Ogunwale, J. A. (2017). The Yoruba World and Its Articulation. *Journal of Black Studies*, 48(3), 271-288.
- Ojo, A. E. (2020). *Social And Cultural Values of The Yoruba People*. Routledge.
- Olajubu, O. (2016). *Women in the Yoruba Religious Sphere*. SUNY Press.
- Olatunji, O. (2021). *Yoruba Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites*. Lagos, Nigeria: University of Lagos Press.
- Olupona, J. K. (2018). *African Religions: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University Press. pp. 67-89, 112.
- Olusola, A. P. (2019). *Ifa Divination: An Indigenous Knowledge System of The Yoruba People*. *Journal of Black Studies*, 50(2), 167-184.
- Omoyajowo, J. A. (2016). *The Cherubim and Seraphim Movement: A Study in Syncretism*. Routledge.
- Oshitelu, G. A. (2016). The Yoruba Concept of Ori and Human Destiny. *Philosophical Papers and Review*, 7(2), 9-18.
- Parrinder, G. (1980). *West African Religion: A Study of the Beliefs and Practices of Akan, Ewe, Yoruba, Ibo, and Kindred Peoples*. London: Epworth Press.
- Pearce, T. O. (2020). *Medicine And Magic in Yorubaland*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wright, N.T. (2012). *Simply Jesus, A New Vision of Who He Was, What He Did and Why He Matters*. HarperOne